

A STUDY ON BEHAVIORAL BIASES AND ITS IMPACT ON FINANCIAL RISK TOLERANCE AMONG INVESTORS OF UTTAR PRADESH

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in

FIELD OF MANAGEMENT

by

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(Enrollment No. Ph.D./15/MGMT/1942)

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**to the
FACULTY OF MANAGEMENT**

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(Formerly Uttar Pradesh Technical University, Lucknow)

July, 2021

DECLARATION

I hereby declare that the work presented in this report entitled "A STUDY ON BEHAVIORAL BIASES AND ITS IMPACT ON FINANCIAL RISK TOLERANCE AMONG INVESTORS OF UTTAR PRADESH", was carried out by me. I have not submitted the matter embodied in this report for the award of any other degree or diploma of any other University or Institute. I have given due credit to the original authors/sources for all the words, ideas, diagrams, graphics, computer programs, experiments, results, that are not my original contribution. I have used quotation marks to identify verbatim sentences and given credit to the original authors/sources.

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The thesis embodies results of original work, and studies are carried out by the student herself and the contents of the thesis do not form the basis for the award of any other degree to the candidate or to anybody else from this or any other University.

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Date:.....

ABSTRACT

Investment decision these days play a crucial role in planning different life long events as well as financial contingencies. In Indian Investors, where an individual needs to allocate funds on yearly basis in accordance with different governmental policies, this task becomes much complex and difficult. In order to reduce this mental burden, every individual takes help from different consultancies, people, and other organizations. As seen in various financial decisions individual investors generally try to find his/her assets and liabilities and then do financial planning in accordance; but the most important criteria they generally omit is they are risk tolerance level.

The study where has been conducted with a primary objective to develop the financial model to profile and investors (belonging to different tolerance levels) according to different behavioural biases. However, the study has been conducted among investor of Uttar Pradesh Region only, the replication of results on a larger population needs to be analysed. The data has been collected from 500 individual investors (the absolute figure is 487 after data editing) in the form of a structured Questionnaire having closed ended questions. The questions related to behavioural biases have been developed on a 5 point Likert scale.

The results show that the investors of Uttar Pradesh are found to be affected by different behavioural biases which is prominently reflected in their irrational behaviour towards financial decision making. The study found 8 behavioural biases (as propounded by NM Waweru in the year 2008) namely representativeness, overconfidence, gamblers fallacy, availability bias, loss aversion, regret aversion, mental accounting, and herd behaviour. However, one biases named as anchoring bias does not seem to influence the investors of Uttar Pradesh. The results also categories the investors into five different categories of risk tolerance as conservative, above moderate, moderate, below moderate and aggressive one (as defined in GL-RTS model in the year 2015).

The study here attempts to generate an association between these biases and different risk tolerance levels. It is found that four biases (representativeness, over confidence, gamblers fallacy, availability bias) are strongly, positively associated with risk tolerance. However other 4 biases (loss aversion, regret aversion, mantel accounting, and herd behaviour) are strongly, negatively associated with risk tolerance level.

The study also claims that various demographical factors (gender, age, marital status, education, employment income, investment preference) do have an impact on the financial risk tolerance level of an individual and hence this must be taken into account while considering any financial alternative for an investment decision.

This study will help an investor to construct his/her own behaviourally modified portfolio or to suggest it to others. However, future research with more behaviour biases and on a larger population will contribute much to the present study.

KEYWORDS: Financial contingency, risk tolerance, biases, behaviourally modified portfolio, irrational behaviour.

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SUSHMA
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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS AND SYMBOLS

List of Abbreviations	
BAPM	Behavioural Asset Pricing Model
BF	Behavioural Finance
BPT	Behavioural Portfolio Theory
CAPM	Capital Asset Pricing Model
EMH	Efficient Market Hypothesis
FD's	Fixed Deposites
FOREX	Foreign Exchange
FRT	Financial Risk Tolerance
GL-RTS	Grable-Lytton Risk Tolerance Scale
NBER	National Bureau of Economic Research
NSC	National Saving Certificates
PPF	Public Provident Fund
Rs. (₹)	Rupees
SCF	Survey of Consumer Finances
SPSS	Statistical Package for Social Sciences
Yr.	Year

INTRODUCTION

1.1 OVERVIEW

“The best investment you can make is an investment in yourself. The more you’ll learn, the more you’ll earn.”

-Warren Buffett

“Investments are subject to market risk, please read the offer document carefully before investing” This so-called quote act as a protection shield these days for various investment firms. These firms generally try to get rid of their social and moral responsibility of educating investors by providing this mandatory disclaimer in their advertisement saying that the investment decisions are subject to various market risks, and ask the investor to thoroughly go through the offer document carefully before taking their final decision. The problem arises when an investor fails to understand the hidden meaning of the so-called disclaimer or till he understands the compensation of their decision becomes irrevocable.

Studies show a major portion of investors relies on the advice of their peer group or seniors in order to take their financial decisions. The cause for the same includes their level of confidence towards own analytical skills, the psychological traits of investor, behavioral factors, risk tolerance levels, and their demographic segmentation. The study also suggests that sometimes it is difficult to judge the sentiments of investors and alter them. It is human psychology that an individual always tries to justify their decisions and doesn’t really take much pain in finding the areas of error. The consultants and advisors take benefit of this human psychology and try to find out the loopholes in the system; which ultimately create compromised returns by investors.

The study here has been targeted on analyzing the behavioral aspect of the investors which make their financial decision biased. It will also help in understanding the pros and cons of this biased behavior that can have long-lasting and huge repercussions on the Indian financial market as well as the investment industry in the future.

Over the last 10 years, a mushroom growth in the finance industry has been prominently seen both in terms of volume as well as the number of investors. The number of Indian investors has been increasing at a compounded annual growth rate of 11% over the last decade. As per NSE (National Stock Exchange), the total investors count stands at 2.78 Cr. presently. There has been a spurt of the financial products having huge options available to lure the investor. The Indian financial sector is growing at a rate of approximately 8.5% per year these days. Studies show in India people generally invest their hard work and mind in earning money but they definitely don’t take the same pain

in investing this hard-earned to various investment avenues. The two important causes (as per study here) for the same are:

- 1) The poor analytical skill of investors, hence they rely on others for the same.
- 2) The psychological and Behavioral traits of investors towards risk.

It is seen that the investor is not interested in doing either technical or fundamental analysis before going to take investment decisions. The reason being; they don't want to invest time in doing the same and rely on other consultants; who may or may not suggest them the right option. They also have a doubt on their own analytical skills to select an optimal decision from various feasible options available and hence depend on others who can help them to do their financial planning.

The second reason is the Behavioral psychological traits of an investor. If the investor is risk-averse (not interested in taking high risk) he/she doesn't want to undergo into the investment avenues which are new to him. They generally follow either what their seniors and elders have done or what their peer group is doing. They want to be a part of herd group; as according to them its risk proof and safest option. And if the investor is a risk-taker (interested in taking high risk) then he/she generally goes for investments on the basis of their gut feeling or intuition but not on calculated risk.

Moreover, the investors instead of evaluating their previous financial decisions in order to find their past errors; are more inclined towards justifying their decisions and being hopeful for future. Being optimistic is not bad but the problem arises when the investor stuck between various emotions like greed, fear and hope. This suggests the irrational behavior of investors.

1.2 BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

Chaudhary and Kumari [35] inferred a significant influence of Behavioral biases on individual decisions. They had found that the investor most of the time tries to invest in various investment opportunities irrationally and also illogically. Investors do not take pain in considering or analyzing the repercussions of their investment decision.

There have been two clusters of economists; the first cluster has been supporting the traditional and standard financial models to be appropriate for evaluating investment decisions and support the rational Behavior of investors. They argue that the efficient market hypothesis fits best for stock prices and the fluctuations always reflect the information available to an investor. **Gupta et al. [98]**. The second cluster of economists favors and interprets the irrational Behavior of investors. **Chaudhary Amar Kumar [36]** found that Behavioral finance provides various explanations regarding the irrational Behavior of investors. He confirms that emotional as well as cognitive errors have an influence on investor's financial decisions. **Chandra Abhijeet [34]** examined how the psychology of individual and his behavioral traits influence the process of

decision making by an individual. He concluded that investor does not always involve in the rational and logical decision but is influenced by various psychological factors like greed, fear, emotions, heuristics, cognitive disparity, etc. This group of economists rejects the assumption regarding the maximization of expected utility and the presence of an investor who acts rationally in an efficient market. **Ritter Jay [196]**

One more paradigm exists that confers an investor to be neither fully rational nor fully Behavioral or irrational. An investor's rationality is a choice and sometimes it is costlier to be fully rational, as it requires a lot of mental floss. On the other hand, there are some benefits associated with rationality in terms of costs. **Mukherjee and De [166]**. According to **Ariely et al. [8]** there is one way to be rational, but many ways of being irrational.

Traditional finance is a cluster of concepts and theories that collaborate and summarize various underlying facts relying on the principle of rationality which an individual follows to take financial decisions. Standard finance theories lay their foundation on an assumption that an individual thinks objectively during the process of making their financial decisions. Also, the individual investor is assumed to behave rationally considering the risks as well as returns involved.

However, the other set of researches in psychology support the fact that the financial decisions taken by investors are often made in an irrational manner. Hence a new domain emerged as behavioral finance in the past few decades. The theories and concepts of behavioral finance try to explain how social, demographical, and psychological factors influence an individual to make their financial decisions.

1.3 DEVELOPMENT OF TRADITIONAL FINANCIAL THEORIES

All standard/ traditional finance theories rest on the basis of two important assumptions including risk and return in all financial decisions. Standard finance theories explain an individual as an investor who tries to maximize return and minimize risk to generate optimal decisions. These theories generally prove an investor to be very rational in their financial decision. According to traditional financial concepts, the financial decisions taken by an investor are based on pure mathematical and statistical calculations in accordance with their conditions and assumptions. Earlier studies had shown that traditional financial theories are primarily based on four assumptions:

1. The investor is always rational in nature.
2. The financial markets are very efficient.
3. The investors make their portfolio by calculating mean-variance of risk.
4. The risk and returns expected by investors have an inter dependability.

The foundation for traditional financial theories is assumed to be conceptualized in the mid of 19th century in the year 1844 when Mr. J. S. Mill has laid the foundation of a

rational economic man called as *homo economicus* who puts his effort to maximize his economic wellbeing within various constraints of life. According to **Mill and Stuart [161]**; the 3 important assumptions for these were:

1. Perfect rationality
2. Perfect self- interest and
3. Perfect information.

The above features later acted as a basis to lay the foundation for the traditional financial framework. This helped individuals to find the equilibrium solutions most suitable for them by maximizing their marginal utilities subject to their situational constraints. This concept later has been used in most of the economic theories that came up. Daneil Bernoulli in the year 1738 studied decision making under risk by comparing expected utilities of various individuals. **Bernoulli Daneil [23]**. Later Von Neumann and Morgenstern in 1944 studied and utilized this concept for developing a new theory named as “Expected Utility Theory”. They justified the assumptions regarding a rational individual who focuses to maximize his expected utility by calculating the multiplication of the weighted sum of utility values with their respective probabilities of occurrence.

Von and Morgenstern [251] in their theory also categorizes the investor in 3 different categories namely risk-averse, risk-taker and risk-neutral. In the year 1952, Harry Markowitz introduced a new portfolio selection model popularly called as “Markowitz portfolio theory”. The model helps an individual in the process of construction of their optimal portfolio by choosing a perfect combination of risky securities and risk-free securities in order to maximize their expected return and minimizing the risk. **Markowitz Harry [158]**. Later in the year 1962 a new concept emerged that helped in creation of CAPM, i.e. “Capital Asset Pricing Model” having few names associated as their contributors, such as W.F. Sharpe, J. Treynor, J. Mossin and J. Lintner. They collaboratively worked from 1962 to 1966 to contribute in the CAPM model. **Mossin J. [165]**. The model was quite simple to understand and use which gave this model an edge to be globally used and accepted as a popular asset pricing model. **Sharpe W. [214]**.

In spite of being one of the most popular theories still many traditional theorists were not supporting CAPM model because of different anomalies regarding market efficiency. **Lintner J. [148]**. In order to overcome these anomalies, a new asset pricing theory came into the market by Eugene Fama in the year 1970 which was known as “Efficient Market Hypothesis” (EMH). The hypothesis talked about the association between various types of information like news or verdict into a market with financial decisions. This theory was aimed at interpreting the market efficiency and its impact on expected return. **Eugene Fama [62]**. Mr.Fama has categorized the market efficiency into 3 categories:

1. A weak efficient market is one where even a small piece of news or information will have an impact on the market returns and create abnormalities in the market.
2. A market with semi-strong efficiency aims at utilizing all publicly available information but it fails to create extra superior returns.
3. A strong efficient market is one where even insider trading cannot provide abnormal returns.

According to **Fama and French [64]** the efficient markets are those places featured with a huge number of rational investors who compete accordingly, to maximize their profits by predicting future values of various securities at a place where all the relevant information is assumed to be available to all individuals easily. After EMH, one more economist named Stephen Ross came up with a concept of arbitraging in the year 1976. His concepts emerged a new theory named as “Arbitrage Pricing Theory”. The theory talked about the greed of investors where he tries to increase the returns by taking the benefit of price fluctuations at different places. According to this theory, the investor purchases a security from a place where it is cheaper and tries to sell it at a place where it is comparatively costlier.

According to **Ross and Roll [199]** the arbitrage pricing theory has indicated that the investor; instead of being influenced by statistics and calculations, he is more inclined towards emotional greed and wants. This fact attracted the minds of economists to judge the rationality of investors again with a new mindset and check whether the investor is still rational in his financial decision making or he is getting influenced by emotions, greed, hope, etc. and get involved in irrational decisions making. The **Figure 1.1** below provides a systematic snapshot of major milestones in standard financial theories.

Figure 1.1: Systematic Presentation of Traditional Financial theories.

Source: Compiled by researcher

1.4 DEVELOPMENT OF BEHAVIORAL FINANCE

Behavioral finance is a comparatively fresh and emerging prospective domain of finance that has shown its development in the recent past. This new domain emerged when the researchers from the field of psychology and finance together tried to explain the puzzling factors involved in stock market fluctuations. It studies the influence of various socio-psychological factors on asset price. The Behavioral and psychological insights together emerged as an application of economics that tries to clarify the irrational mindset of individual and financial decisions. It is a combination of psychology, sociology, and finance that collaboratively tries to explain why the assumptions of standard financial theories fail to explain different market anomalies.

Since the last few decades, the traditional financial theories have shown their importance in explaining the investor decision-making procedure but a setback came when these theories are not found to be able enough to justify the erratic and irrational behavior of the individuals. Various researchers studying stock market fluctuations have seen market bubbles at different times; which were difficult to be explained by these standard theories. Hence, the evolution of a domain into the field of finance took place, which tries to explain the psychology, emotions, irrationality, and biased behavior of individuals.

Behavioral finance lays its foundation on the assumptions that differ from traditional or standard finance. It assumes that:

- 1) The investors do behave irrationally at times
- 2) Investment markets are not always efficient and perfect
- 3) Investors don't always follow mean-variance rule for designing their portfolio
- 4) Risk and return are two independent entities having no inter dependability

Behavioral finance; in spite of being conflicting in nature, has attracted the minds of different scholars into a financial domain, psychology as well as neuroscience.

In the year 2007, **Mark Schindler [157]** defined Behavioral finance in the form of a model shown in **Figure 1.2** as a combining factor for sociology, psychology, and finance.

Figure 1.2: Behavioral finance model.

Source: Adopted from Mark Schindler (2007)

The studies in psychology earlier have interpreted that the human mind is the most complex thing to understand. The human brain is considered as a complicated organ with infinite thoughts moving around. Individuals sometimes act rationally during their decision-making process but at times also behave stupidly. Some people are aware of the weaknesses of others and they try to use it in exploiting them and hence came the concept of morality. Individuals generally have developed a peculiar system of observations and principles to differentiate between right and wrong as ethics.

It is in the mid of 18th century; in the year 1759 when a Scottish economist, moral philosopher, and professor from Stanford University explored his work on “Theory of Moral Sentiments”. His name was Adam Smith and he talked about morality and selfishness. **Adam Smith [228]** interpreted that individuals take the decision for their own benefit. Also, people love to be praised by others, and sometimes their decision-making depends on this psychology that whether that decision will be praiseworthy or not. The praiseworthy decision eventually gives them pleasure and hence they consider it as the correct decision.

“The Wealth of Nations” came out to be the next most popular work authored by Mr. Adam Smith; which was first published in 1776. This book by **A. Smith [229]** in various later editions offer descriptions regarding the nation’s wealth, which is still the

world's first collection of facts of this kind. Even today it is studied as the most important foundational work in the domain of economics.

Later in the year 1789, one more economist named Bentham J. emphasized emotions and sentiments (like pride, shame, insecurity, etc.) and highlighted the psychological aspects of individuals. **Bentham J. [21]** This work was later restrained till the mid of 20th century when various researchers opposed the logic behind *homo economicus* as they argued that any individual can't be completely informed in all situations to maximize their utility.

Later in 1955, an economist named Herbert Simon came up with a new set of concepts known as "Theory of the Bounded Rationality". This theory explains that the rationality of individuals depends on various information they have and their cognitive limitations. Bounded rationality explains that individuals have an upper and lower limit of constraints within which they try to maximize their utility and find an optimal way. This theory helped a lot of individuals to choose the best among the rest. **Simon H.A. [224]**

The credit for an ice-breaking and most important study in Behavioral finance goes to two Israeli psychologists named Daniel Kahneman and Amos Tversky. They are known as *Fathers of Behavioral Finance*. **Kahneman and Tversky [120]**. These two psychologists brought storm into the world of minds in decision science and field of psychology. **Kahneman and Tversky [122]** evolved the revolutionary "Prospect Theory" in year 1979 for interpreting decision-making under risk. This theory is assumed to be the most influential literature in the field of Behavioral economics. **Kahneman and Tversky [121]** in this theory tries to explain how an individual investigates his gain or losses under different situations.

According to this theory:

1. At times individuals show risk aversion Behavior and at times risk seekers. It depends on the conditions like the available prospective, relative probability of outcomes, etc. Hence, they act as risk avoider for decisions where they assume high chances of sure gains while becoming risk lover for decisions with a high probability of sure losses.
2. People assign conceptual value to gains and losses. They try to find out various alternatives (or prospects) they have and then they rank them according to rules of thumb (heuristics). Later **Tversky and Kahneman [249]** also evaluate these prospects in relation to one point of reference point that generally acts as a basis for comparing the gains and losses.
3. The theory by **Tversky and Kahneman [247]** says that the weightage of losses is always higher than the gains for the same denomination as the individuals are more averse towards losses as compared to gains. This concept is later known as "loss aversion". **Kahneman and Tversky [122]** later also introduced different behavioral biases that influence the financial decision-making of individuals.

In the year 1994 two economists named as Meir Statman and Shefrin developed a new pricing model called as “Behavioral Asset Pricing Model (BAPM)” replacing the concept of Capital Asset Pricing Model. **Shefrin and Statman [215]** in their model categorizes investors into 2 types as:

1. Informational traders and
2. Noise traders.

Information traders are those investors who follow the traditional capital asset pricing model for financial decisions; whereas the noise traders are those who don't follow the CAPM or traditional financial pricing. Later in the year 2000, they came up with the development of a new “Behavioral Portfolio Theory” based on behavioral economics. The Behavioral Portfolio Theory by **Shefrin and Statman [216]** considers various behavioral biases of the investors in order to construct their portfolios according to their associated risk tolerance.

In the year 1981 an American economist named Robert J Shiller in his study related to stock market volatility, tried to explain various movements in American stock market with the help of Behavioral economics approach for market movements. **Shiller Robert J. [219]** had also explained the impact of investor's perception, psychology and cultural factors in creating stock market bubbles during late 1990's.

Shiller Robert J. [221] presented various contradictions with traditional financial concepts in his work titled “*Irrational Exuberance*” and also received Nobel prize in economic sciences in the year 2013 for his key insights related to the irrational minds of an individual investor.

Another significant contribution towards explanation of market anomalies was given by Barberis and Richard Thaler in the year 2003. According to **Barberis and Thaler [14]** behavioral finance lay its foundation on two major building blocks:

1. One is the limit to arbitraging, which explains that it is difficult for full rational traders to ignore the dislocations created by less rational traders.
2. The second is psychology that supports and explains different types of deviations from full rationality.

They studied the trading behavior of individual investor in order to explain the implications of behavioral economics in the volatility of stock market average returns. Richard Thaler in the year 2008 coined a term known as “Nudge” in Behavioral economics that provides various suggestions for investors to influence their behavior. The theory is popularly known as “Nudge Theory”. He had also received Nobel Prize in economic sciences in the year 2017 for his major contribution that tried to bridge the gap between domains of economics and psychology.

The **Figure 1.3** below explains the systematic development in various Behavioral finance theories that act as milestones in this domain till the starting of 21st century.

Figure 1.3: Systematic Presentation of Behavioural Finance theories.

Source: Compiled by researcher

1.5 NEED OF THE STUDY

Behavioral finance is a financial domain grown to its heights in the last few decades. Behavioral finance tries to explain the logic behind the application of heuristics and mental shortcuts by investors to take investment decisions which still need to be extensively studied. There is a genuine need to shed specific light on the systematic evolution of the concept in order to understand various market anomalies and the psychology of individuals being affected by various Behavioral biases. As Behavioral biases are associated to the psychology of human beings therefore the implications are also very wide. Hence it is important to understand this concept by various financial practitioners seeking growth in the field of financial advisory. The study here will definitely help financial advisors to effectively understand their client's psychology and

will aid them to develop a behaviorally modified portfolio suit best to them. Behavioral finance concepts are going to help investment bankers to understand the market sentiments before going for public issues and will help them to make contingency financial strategists to handle adverse situations.

1.6 IDENTIFICATION OF RESEARCH PROBLEM

According to **Eugene Fama [62]** traditional finance has been conceptualized on the efficient market hypothesis, found its assumption based on the concept that investors can't earn abnormal returns by interpreting the publically available information.

In contrast to traditional finance theories, Behavioral finance challenges the concept that financial markets work perfectly well and the genuine information always get converted to security price fluctuations. **Shiller Robert J. [222]** Behavioral finance is a domain more concerned with the application of heuristics in order to analyze and interpret results to make financial decisions which ultimately induce Behavioral biases among investors and hence investor tends to commit errors.

According to **Thaler Richard [242]** economics must incorporate two different models; first the normative economic model, which helps to provide an optimal solution to specific problems and second the descriptive models that should guide how humans actually behave. The Indian individual investor is found to be more susceptible towards various psychological biases during investment decisions making, hence more precise study needs to be done keeping in mind the psychological factors, particularly in the Indian context. **Chandra Abhijeet [34]**

The problem statement surrounds around the locus of fact that different behavioral, demographical and risk factors found to have an association with investor's financial decision. The study here is an attempt to investigate the presence of behavioral biases and its influence on financial risk tolerance. Indian investment firms focus on understanding the pattern of investment of investor, associated with different risk profiles only, ignoring the psychological aspect. The results compiled here will provide them a model that can help these firms to have an insight of the irrational Behavior of investors and their psychic towards investment objectives. The study here is focused on seeking answers to the following questions:

1. How do investors behave towards various investment options available?
2. Why do investors behave; the way they behaved?
3. What is the association between behavioral biases and the financial risk tolerance of investors?

1.7 RESEARCH GAPS

Following gaps motivate the present study:

1. The domain of Behavioral finance is much newer as compared to those traditional financial concepts. In developed economies, behavioral finance concepts are widely used to understand the behavior of investors; however, the application of these concepts and theories has been limited in nature for less developed economies. This study here tries to fill this gap.
2. In the financial domain major research has been done focusing on standard financial theories, but comparatively less research has been done on Behavioral finance, which is an alternative but more relevant theory of finance.
3. As per reviewed literature, most of the Behavioral financial researches in our country are based on finding investment patterns of investors but less work has been done on finding the Behavioral biases of investors.
4. Most of the researches done; aimed at finding Behavioral factors affecting only those investing in the secondary market and comparatively less studies focus on creating a Behavioral finance model for every individual.
5. As per the literature reviewed; most of the researches regarding financial risk tolerance has considered demographic variables only as an affecting factor but the study here will bring Behavioral biases into consideration as well during the process of exploring financial risk tolerance.

1.8 SIGNIFICANCE OF STUDY

The study attempts to explore the irrational behaviour and reasons of biasness in investment decision making (if any). This can create a significant impact on those who are a part of the financial industry as well as the top-scale policy makers by making them aware of the role of behavioural aspects among different individuals.

Also, it is important to specify that the study here is location specific and it doesn't claim the replication of identical results over the larger demographical scale. Any change in location, area, population and size may alter the results presented here and hence it is suggested to quote the present results in similar sampling conditions and domain only. The expected impact towards different domains of the society is as follows:

1.8.1 Expected impact to the individual investors:

This research is going to act as a reference for various investors who are either thinking to enter or already investing in different investment avenues. The research provides an opportunity for them to understand more about risks involved and learn different aspects of investment Behavior. It will motivate

investors to consider and analyze all price trends before making any investment decision as well as consider their personal traits.

1.8.2 Expected impact to the investment industry:

The research here will provide various security organizations, a conceptual background of irrational decision-making that will help in prediction of future and hence will help them to provide more reliable information to their clients. This research will help the investment firms by providing them an overview regarding the investment Behavior of investors towards various investment opportunities available to them. The study will also help to understand various behavioral biases of investors associated with different risk tolerance which ultimately provide these organizations an opportunity to adopt various strategies in creating more customized portfolios for their clients.

1.8.3 Expected impact to Academicians:

The research here will help the academicians (specifically from psychology and finance domain) to understand various Behavioral aspects of an individual that influence an individual's personality which in turn will help them in understanding and molding their personality traits, if required. This research will also help the academicians to understand how the heuristic-driven biases and prospect factors impair the judgment process of various persons. The study will also expand the future scope for the academicians to explore new concepts and their dependence in the field of Behavioral economics.

1.9 RESEARCH DESIGN

The research design used here is a Descriptive one where a framework is developed to find reasons and to generate a causal relationship among dependent and independent variables. In order to generate comprehensive results hypotheses testing have been done. Hence a mixed approach of qualitative as well as quantitative techniques is to be used.

1.10 DATA COLLECTION

The data for this study has been collected from primary as well as secondary sources. Primary data has been collected from distributing well-structured questionnaires and collecting responses. Secondary data has been collected from different secondary sources (web links, journals, magazines, etc.)

1.11 SAMPLE DESIGN

1.11.1 Sample Area:

KAVAL cities (Kanpur, Agra, Varanasi, Allahabad, Lucknow) of Uttar Pradesh.

1.11.2 Sampling Technique:

The sampling technique to be used here is stratified non-random sampling, where the whole population has been divided into different strata based on population ratio.

1.11.3 Sample Size:

500 individual investors

Total population of KAVAL cities = 10219840 (As per Census 2011)

Critical Value (z) = 1.96 at 95%

Marginal error (E) = 5%

Response distribution (r) = 20%

1.11.4 Sample Frame:

A respective number of investors from each selected city of Uttar Pradesh is taken in the ratio of population, as per census 2011. It is shown in **Table 4-1** of chapter 4 in this thesis.

1.12 RESEARCH TOOLS AND ANALYSIS

Suitable statistical tools and techniques used for research purpose are:

1. Descriptive statistics for demographic variables.
2. Correlation analysis for finding a degree of relationship among variables.
3. Regression analysis in order to develop a linear model among DV and IDVs
4. Statistical tests for hypotheses testing (ANOVA, Chi square and cross tab)

By using SPSS, Version 21 the analysis of collected data has been done.

1.12.1 Defining Variables:

The **Table 1.1** shows the details of the variables considered in this study.

Table 1.1: Description of variables used in the study.

Name of Variable	Considered Scale	Measurement Type	Options Available
Gender	Nominal	Multiple Choice	<input type="checkbox"/> MALE INVESTOR <input type="checkbox"/> FEMALE INVESTOR

Age	Nominal	Multiple Choice Question	<input type="checkbox"/> UP TO 25 YR. <input type="checkbox"/> 26-45 YR. <input type="checkbox"/> 46-65 YR. <input type="checkbox"/> 65 YR. & ABOVE.
Education	Nominal	Multiple Choice Question	<input type="checkbox"/> GRADUATION/ DIPLOMA, <input type="checkbox"/> POST-GRADUATION, <input type="checkbox"/> DOCTORAL AND HIGHER EDU, <input type="checkbox"/> PROFESSIONAL COURSE.
Monthly Income	Nominal	Multiple Choice Question	<input type="checkbox"/> UPTO ₹30000 <input type="checkbox"/> ₹30001 - ₹60000 <input type="checkbox"/> ₹60001 - ₹80000 <input type="checkbox"/> ₹80000 AND ABOVE <input type="checkbox"/> NIL
Employment Structure	Nominal	Multiple Choice Question	<input type="checkbox"/> SELF-EMPLOYED <input type="checkbox"/> FULL TIME SALARIED <input type="checkbox"/> CASUAL/ PART TIME <input type="checkbox"/> UNEMPLOYED(HOUSEWIFE/RETIRED/STUDENT)
Marital Status	Nominal	Multiple Choice Question	<input type="checkbox"/> NEVER MARRIED <input type="checkbox"/> MARRIED WITHOUT CHILDREN <input type="checkbox"/> MARRIED WITH CHILDREN <input type="checkbox"/> WIDOW/ SEPARATED
Investment Preference	Nominal	Multiple Choice Question	<input type="checkbox"/> SAFE AVENUES <input type="checkbox"/> MODERATE RISK AVENUES <input type="checkbox"/> HIGH-RISK AVENUES <input type="checkbox"/> TRADITIONAL AVENUES <input type="checkbox"/> EMERGING AVENUES
Financial Risk Tolerance	Ordinal	Four Point Rating Score	<input type="checkbox"/> LOW(CONSERVATIVE) <input type="checkbox"/> BELOW MODERATE <input type="checkbox"/> MODERATE <input type="checkbox"/> ABOVE-MODERATE <input type="checkbox"/> HIGH (AGGRESSIVE)
Behavioral Factors	Interval	Five Point Likert Scale	HEURISTIC FACTORS - REPRESENTATIVENESS - OVERCONFIDENCE BIAS - GAMBLER'S FALLACY -AVAILABILITY BIAS PROSPECT FACTORS - RISK AVERSION - MENTAL ACCOUNTING -LOSS AVERSION HERDING FACTORS - HERD BEHAVIOR

Source: Compiled by researcher

1.13 OUTLINE OF THESIS

The study presented here is categorized into different chapters summed up below.

Chapter 1: Introduction to research topic

This chapter deals with the identification of research problem and introduction of the study being performed here. This chapter provides a snapshot of the whole study conducted here including the aim and significance of study, various research gaps identify and a review on research methodology being used.

Chapter 2: Review of Literature: Financial Risk Tolerance

This chapter deals with the literature available regarding the calculations and study risk tolerance scales. It provides a brief review of authored literature on financial risk tolerance.

Chapter 3: Review of Literature: Behavioral Finance

This chapter deals with the systematic arrangement of literature available regarding the evolution of Behavioral finance and various studies being reviewed by the researcher.

Chapter 4: Research Methodology

This chapter deals with the description of research process used and the methodology regarding research design, sampling design, and data collection methods. It also explains the statistical tests being used by the researcher.

Chapter 5: Data Analysis & Interpretation

The chapter includes the analytical portion of this research, where the collected data has been analyzed using various statistical tools and techniques, and the results found are also interpreted in order to ensure proper understanding.

Chapter 6: Findings and Conclusion

The chapter deals with the findings of preceding chapter and the summation of all the results found on a concluding note.

Chapter 7: Suggestions, Limitations & Future scope

This chapter is concerned with providing various suggestions regarding the research problem studied here and also highlights the future scope for academicians for further study in a similar domain.

FINANCIAL RISK TOLERANCE

2.1 GENERAL

The term “risk” is considered to be derived from an Italian word “risicare”, that mean “to dare”. According to **Bernstein P.L. [24]** risk is considered as a choice than as a fate. There are four different types of risks existing in the world of economists as ethical, social, physical and financial risks. According to **Koh and Fong [131]** the financial risk tolerance of an individual plays a very crucial role in making financial decisions to achieve financial goals and hence it acts as a primary determinant. Risk tolerance is inversely related to risk aversion, where tolerance is an economic term that depicts a person’s hesitant Behavior to accept a choice that has a level of uncertainty in the payoff whereas a second option is available that has a more certain outcome.

Koh and Fong [131] explained FRT as an extent to which an individual is psychologically receptive towards the situations which affect social, ethical, financial, and physical health by introducing decisions of uncertainty. Risk tolerance is a summarization of various situations involving the trade-off between emotions like greed, fear. According to **Su Y. [235]** risk is associated with two components, known as uncertainty and exposure. Uncertainty happens when the person is not aware of anything; it is a state of “not knowing something”. On the other hand, the exposure varies from person to person on their individual capability and capacity.

Risk tolerance is considered to be a dynamic process that keeps on changing over a period of time. The reason behind this dynamic nature is that, the level of risks a person bears and strategies he follows to overcome those risks keep on changing with personal, mental, and financial needs and circumstances. **Pieson J. [182]**

2.2 DEFINITIONS OF RISK TOLERANCE

1. The most popular and appropriate definition of Financial risk tolerance was proposed by Kogan and Wallach in 1964. They had defined FRT as the readiness of an individual to get engaged in behavior of the desired goal and the attainment of an uncertain goal that may accompany the loss possibility. **Kogan and Wallach [130]**
2. Financial risk tolerance can be illustrated as the agreeableness of an individual to get involved in behavior where the attainment of the desired goal is uncertain that may accompany with the possibility of loss as well. **Okun M. A. [176]**

3. Investor's FRT is referred as highest level of investment risk that an individual is comfortable in taking. Schaefer described risk tolerance relation in a way that two persons may agree on same risky gambles, but will never prefer the different ranks in accordance with their personal tolerance. **Schaefer R. E. [208]**
4. Risk is the existence of condition which is beyond the control of the decision maker which ultimately affect the outcomes of choices. Hence the level of risk acts as a dependent variable towards the size of decision maker's loss potential and the chances of that loss. **Roth and Mullen [204]**
5. **Weber et.al. [256]** explained tolerance of risk as the choice of a person towards the decision shift from aversion of risk to acceptance of risk, limiting a specified domain of financial decision making.
6. **Grable and Joo [82]** defined FRT as the maximum level of uncertainty that a person is ready to opt for while making any financial decision.
7. **Faff et al. [63]** referred FRT as the attitude of an investor towards risk which acted as the level of uncertainty or the volatility in the returns that the investor is ready to opt for while making any financial decision.
8. According to **Goldstein and McElligott [80]** risk tolerance has been defined as the cognitive behavior which motivates a person to encompass his limit of taking a risk. They suggested a way to measure it in a manner that it remains inside the boundary of risk appetite as well as it should be alterable enough to allow the increase in capacity of risk-taking.
9. FRT refers to the attitude of an individual towards different situations; who is interested in taking risk while considering any financial decision regarding investment of money. **Grable and Rabbani [87]**
10. Risk can be influenced by various aspects and physiognomies like control variables, human choice and prejudice to various constraints like socio-economic background, preferences and their perceptions. **Mabalane M.D. [151]**

2.3 DEVELOPMENT OF RISK-TOLERANCE MEASUREMENT SCALES

A lot of endeavors have been considered by the risk calculators to assess the FRT level of an investor formally. As per **Roszkowski and Grable [200]** there are different approaches followed by various researchers to access the financial risk tolerance. Those

who rely on consultants and other judgments of individual have a tendency to follow the assumption of others that bear the same risk tolerance as other have. The other alternative is to assume that individuals have different levels of risk tolerance as compared to those acts as judge.

One more approach exist which motivate the researcher to rely on various existing stereotypes to take a final decision. As per **Grable J. E. [81]** the use of heuristic or thumb rule act as an alternative to assess the risk tolerance. Heuristics help in creating the mental shortcut to solve a particular problem. However, heuristics sometimes lead to some miscalculations and later the incorrect categorization of investors into different risk-tolerance groups.

One of the most often used approaches is to assess the FRT levels is done by using an effective and trustworthy scale. However, in certain conditions, a valid scale is not available and needs plentiful time and resources to apply. In such situations, one item question is mostly preferred to assess risk tolerance. One of most popular risk tolerance assessment questionnaires which are extensively used among those who are concerned in assessing tolerance in consumer finances is SCF scale. This questionnaire is very popular among researchers as it includes the direct questions regarding risk-tolerance of investors to be asked in different national surveys of investors. **Chen and Finke [38]** explored one disadvantage of using such questions or the problem associated with such surveys is these questions sometimes don't produce a good substitute for investor's correct level of risk aversion.

Hanna and Lindamood [101] specified that the response pattern of using one item questions as given in SCF scale specifies that a big percentage of respondents replying the questions generally have zero risk tolerance. The conflict found with SCF scale is that the response pattern is skewed one which conflicts with the actual behaviors observed in normal financial situations. **Grable and Lytton [84]** observed that these questions are not an exact representation of spectrum of FRT. Also, these items are closely related to the investor's attitudes. The reliability of these items has also been calculated in order to compare it with other measures. **Grable and Schumm [88]** estimated the trustworthiness of these items by estimating cronbach's alpha which came out to be in between the range of 0.5 to 0.6 approximately. **Gilliam et al. [76]** also found that SCF scale represents a relatively high degree of reliability within these items.

The method by **Roszkowski et al. [202]** involves the assessment of risk tolerance with the help of a psychometrically designed scale. The credit for the milestone work goes back to **Kogan and Wallach [130]** who worked on the development of a choice-dilemma questionnaire used to measure the risk preferences of a person in normal day-to-day life situations. The choice-dilemma questions were frequently used to assess the risk-taking capacity from the last 3 decades.

Emphasis for the development of more precise scale to assess the risk tolerance level has been done in early 90s where the researchers tried to develop a scale that should include various pre-determined dimensions like propensity to take risk, speculations or gambling, gains/ losses and experience of investing. **Grable and Lytton [85]** involved these dimensions in his scale in order to make it multidimensional in nature.

A more reliable scale has been developed by **Roszkowski M.J. [203]** which is called as *Survey of Financial Risk Tolerance* that included both closed as well as open-ended questions. This survey includes 40 items question statements. He also found the reliability of this scale with the help of a coefficient that came out as 0.91, which is considered to be extremely high. The validity of these questions also came out to be high as per his analysis; however, there is lack of publically available data.

An open assess publically available scale that has been considered as the most recent and effective scale of calculating the FRT is a scale established by Grable and Lytton that includes 13 items. **Grable and Lytton [85]** tested this is a closed-ended, multiple-choice questions based scale and found it adequate on criteria of validity and reliability (cronbach's alpha = 0.75). GL-RTS also found to be best suited in the present scenario as per the study piloted by **Gilliam et.al. [76]** which is a comparative analysis of two most popular risk tolerance scales which is SCF i.e. a single question measurement scale and GL-RTS i.e. 13 item multidimensional measure given by Grable and Lytton. The later one found to be more adequate and the scale has also been re-assessed and examined in the year 2015 as well and found applicable and acceptable.

2.4 FACTORS AFFECTING FINANCIAL RISK TOLERANCE

There have been many factors identified by various researcher time to time that interpreted their association with risk tolerance of individuals. This area of study is of particular concern to various customers, investment consultants/advisers, researchers and policymakers as it involves understanding of all those factors found to be connected with risk tolerance of individuals which has a significant influence on individual's financial decision. For every individual who is directly or indirectly involved in the process of financial decision making, it is necessary to have an abstract knowledge regarding factors that affect risk tolerance.

According to **Campbell J.Y. [32]** lack of knowledge, familiarity and expertise create an impact on risk tolerance as well as risk-taking Behavior. There have been a number of demographics, socioeconomic, psychosocial factors that are found to be associated with FRT. **Sadiq and Ishaq [206]** investigated that various demographic factors had shown association with investor's decisions which are prejudiced by investor's risk tolerance level.

2.4.1 Irwin's Model:

The first and foremost theoretical model explaining factors impacting FRT level was developed by Irwin in the year 1993. **Irwin and Millstein [111]** in the year 1986 developed a cause effect model of risk-taking behavior for adolescent and based on the same Irwin created a framework illustrating a number of prejudicing factors that influence risk taking Behavior.

Irwin's model explained that different demographic, socioeconomic, attitudinal as well as psychological elements used to understand and explain risk tolerance level.

The **Table 2.1** explains the framework of variables adapted from the interference model developed by Irwin (1993) that explains the relationship between risk tolerance and its associated elements.

Table 2.1: Factors affecting risk tolerance.

Variable	Type	Characteristic	Relationship
Age	Biopsychosocial	Younger	Positive
Gender	Biopsychosocial	Male	Positive
Race/ethnic background	Biopsychosocial	Non-Hispanic White	Positive
Financial satisfaction	Biopsychosocial	Higher	Positive
Household income	Environmental	Higher	Positive
Net Worth	Environmental	Higher	Positive
Education	Environmental	Higher	Positive
Homeownership	Environmental	Own home	Positive
Marital status	Environmental	Single	Positive
Employment status	Environmental	Employed full-time	Positive
Financial knowledge	Environmental	Higher	Positive

Source: Compiled from model given by Irwin (1993)

2.4.1.1 Bio psychosocial Factors:

Bio psychosocial factors include traits related to age, gender, personality traits, marital status, language. As per Irwin, attitudes and perceptions help to forecast the behavioral outcome. Bio psychosocial factors are those inherent traits over which an individual has very little or no control.

2.4.1.2 Environmental Factors:

Environmental factors are those innate traits that are exclusive to every person and individual. These factors are developed because of changes in the community atmosphere that include household situation, socioeconomic status, and peer behavior.

According to Irwin, environmental factors together with bio psychosocial factors help in predicting FRT level of an individual.

2.4.1.3 Precipitating Factors:

Before assessing the individual's risky financial behavior, they are often exposed to precipitating factors. They are factors associated to an individual's life that impact his/her decision-making capability. It includes an individual's experience, knowledge, skills, emotional feelings that motivate them to adjust their core level of risk acceptance before getting engaged to risky behavior.

The **Figure 2.1** shows Irwin's model explaining the principal factors affecting the financial risk tolerance of individual investors.

Figure 2.1: Principal factors affecting financial risk tolerance.

Source: Compiled and adapted from Irwin' model (1993)

2.4.2 Loewenstein's Model:

A new model that caught attention of researchers studying risk tolerance was the one given by Loewenstein and his associates in his study known as “risk-as-feelings model” hypothesized in the year 2001.

Model by **Loewenstein et al. [149]** included factors like cognitive evaluation, feelings perceptions and individual's inclination to take risk. A brief snapshot of these factors is presented in **Figure 2.2**.

Figure 2.2: Risk as feelings model.

Source: Compiled and adapted from Loewenstein et al. (2001)

2.4.3 Grable's Model:

J.E. Grable and M.J. Roszkowski in the year 2008 identified various factors contributing towards financial risk tolerance and interpreted their relationship as well (as shown in **Table 2.2**). **Grable and Roszkowski [91]** identified risk tolerance as not being a static and fixed one but it's better to predict risk tolerance score and use it as an element to resolve the suitable risk and return trade-off. Risk acceptance can change when an individual's mood swings.

Table 2.2: Factors affecting financial risk tolerance.

Variables	Characteristic	Risk Tolerance
Gender	Male	High
Age	Younger	Moderate
Marital status	Single	Moderate
Income	High	Moderate
Net worth	High	High
Education Bachelor's	degree or higher	Moderate
Employment status	Employed full-time	Moderate
Occupation	Professional	Moderate
Income source	Business owner	High

Source: J.E. Grable and M.J. Roszkowski (2008)

Grable in the year 1997 studied various demographic factors and their association with risk tolerance through a questionnaire designed by himself which includes the closed-ended question regarding risk tolerance Behavior. He has identified various characteristics of investors and classified them into high and low risk-tolerant investors on the basis of those characteristics. The **Table 2.3** shows the categorization of individual Behavior into risk tolerance behavior.

Table 2.3: Relationship between Demographics and risk tolerance.

Characteristic	Low Risk Tolerance	High Risk Tolerance
Gender	Female	Male
Age	Older	Younger
Marital Status	Married	Single
Occupation	Clerical Workers and Laborers	Professionals
Self-Employment	Non-Self-Employed	Self-Employed
Income	Low	High
Race	Non-Whites	Whites
Education	Less	More

Source: John E. Grable (1997).

2.4.4 Demographical variables used in the study:

2.4.4.1 Gender and risk tolerance:

Gender has always been acted as a questioning factor in association with FRT however as per earlier studies done, gender has been cited as an essential factor affecting an individual's level of FRT. **Gibson et al. [75]; Grossman and Eckel [96]; John E.**

Grable [90]; Weber C.S. [255] inferred that men have been considered to be more risk-tolerant as compared to women. **Powell and Ansic [189]** explained his viewpoint of males being more risk-tolerant not only evident in financial risk tolerance but also in other types of risks like physical and social risk tolerances as well. **Grable J.E. [93]** illustrated the gender difference towards financial risk tolerance has also been found because of various factors like men usually incline to possess more confidence in their decisions as compared to women.

According to **Bernasek and Shwiff [22]** it is also affected by various cultural beliefs, environmental exposure of men, their education and financial knowledge which help in contributing to this mindset of gender differences towards risk tolerance. An individual's physical composition has been studied by various international and national researchers similar to **Barber and Odean [11]** with an objective to govern its effect on FRT levels. Similar results have been explored by **Gumede V. [97]; Metherell C. [160]; Ramudzuli and Muzindutsi [191]; Strydom and Metherell [234]; Sulaiman E.K. [238]** and **Yao et al. [260]** as well.

Deo and Sundar [54] in the year 2015 conducted a study on Indian investors and conclude that males are interested to consider more risk in comparison to females who are found to be involved in medium risk. **Grable J.E. [81]** reported that men are at higher financial risk tolerance level instead of the women respondents who preferred less risk. **Badunenko et al. [9]** in their study considered gender as a control variable and determined that male respondents are likely to invest in high risky assets as compared to female respondents. They also found that this association gets sturdier when the study is done for those respondents who have ownership and investment of directly held stocks.

Some studies interpreted some contrary results as well. The results of a study done by **Wasiuzzaman and Edalat [252]** can be explained and linked with the cultural differences or lesser responsibilities for unmarried females as per the researcher. The study on college students of Malaysia interpreted that females have high FRT levels than men. Prince in the year 1993 argued that however men and women both invest their hard-earned money with honor and supremacy; still, male respondents seem to be more involved in higher risks towards gain and expecting more wealth. Khan in the year 2017 has done a study on individual investor characteristics and their association with financial risk tolerance by using the questionnaire by Grable and Lytton as well as SCF scale. He also interpreted that gender has associability with risk tolerance levels.

To check the associability the hypothesis formulated is as follows:

H₀: There is no significant association between gender and financial risk tolerance.

H₁: There is a significant association between gender and financial risk tolerance.

2.4.4.2 Age and risk tolerance:

Age towards risk tolerance has been identified as two negatively correlated variables as per earlier studies done by different researchers. It means that low risk tolerance is associated with high age respondents and vice versa. **Finke and Huston [66]** interpreted that younger people tend to take more risk than older ones. **Jianakoplos and Bernasek[117]** found that there is a negative correlation coefficient found between age and FRT level. Similar results are shown by **Hallahan et al. [100]** and **Faff et al. [63]** as well.

However, some contradictory results are also found by **Hanna et al. [102]** in the year 2001 who claimed that age has no significant relationship with risk tolerance, but it just acts as a controlling factor, however, according to them the number of years of earning till retirement has shown an association with risk tolerance. Younger people being more aggressive in nature; are considered to have more time to cope up with possible losses they may incur due to risky investments. **Finke and Huston [66]** also determined the average age of those interested to consider high risk is 42 years as compared to those who take low risk with average age of 55 years.

Similar to most of the studies, the concept that aging make the investor more likely to become risk avoider has also been confirmed by **Alanko E. [4]** in his study done on Finnish investors. **Anbar and Eker [5]** found a negative significant relationship between age and FRT level explaining that old age people are less risk tolerant as compared to young individual investors. **Gibson et al. [75]** also found the similar association between age and FRT levels. **Grable and Joo [82]** also went through a research and investigated that the level of FRT is lowest for females who are unmarried, followed by females who are married then males who are married and lastly the males who are unmarried. This explained the lesser the age higher is the risk tolerance level.

Sriharsha and Mahapatra [231] showed some contradictions to the above findings as well. They interpreted a positive relationship between age and risk tolerance. They have justified this with the fact that older people have more savings of life as compared to younger people and hence they are ready to take more risk than lower age individuals.

In order to check the associability the hypothesis formulated is as follows:

H_0 : There is no significant association between age and financial risk tolerance.

H_1 : There is a significant association between age and financial risk tolerance.

2.4.4.3 Marital Status and risk tolerance:

Individuals who are married have always been considered to be more susceptible towards financial as well as social risks, as they need to fulfill the needs of the family at different contingency situations. **Roszkowski et al. [202]** explained that marital status

acts as an element that impact the risk tolerance level of an individual and their investment choice leads to low-risk tolerance as compared to a married one. Earlier **Lee and Hanna [140]** as well in their research have suggested that married individuals (specifically those having children) tend to possess a lower risk-taking capacity. According to **Grable et al. [94]**, the risk and return trade off decisions helps to interpret the dilemma of an investor. According to **Lazzarone B.G. [139]** the study conducted on investment consultants and agents; the marital status of an individual plays a significant part in deciding their risk as well as return preferences. Overall researchers have established that unmarried individuals prefer to take high risk as compared to same age married individuals or parent individuals.

However, some studies interpreted, there no significant relationship between marital status and risk tolerance similar to one conducted by **Haliassos and Bertaut [99]**. Various researches like one done by **Cooper et al. [45]** interpreted that belonging of marital status with financial risk tolerance has been found as undefined and indecisive. Similar results were given by **Xiao and Noring [259]** who analyzed individual risk behavior using SCF scale of risk tolerance interpreted that there is no association between marital status and risk tolerance.

In order to check the associability the hypothesis formulated is as follows:

H₀: There is no significant association between marital status and financial risk tolerance.

H₁: There is significant association between marital status and financial risk tolerance.

2.4.4.4 Education and risk tolerance:

Educational background or more specifically financial literacy is designated as an important element in the studies related to risk attitudes and investment related decisions. **Badunenko et al. [9]** in the year 2010 conducted study across Europe found the same. **Corter and Chen [46]** calculated the risk tolerance level of students with different educational backgrounds and found that financial awareness, correlates with risk tolerance. Those who belong to higher education level were more risk-tolerant as they generally go for calculated and higher risk, related with those who are having lesser education.

Nguyen L. [171] confirms his findings by showing a positive association between financial literacy and risk capacity. **Finke and Huston [66]** considered the SCF scale of risk tolerance and explained that education and FRT levels are positively correlated. As level of education increases, the financial literacy of a person also increases and these too show high degree correlation. The same result has also been interpreted by **Khan S.N. [129]**. It is being claimed by various authors that amplified levels of education allows an individual to assess more risk and analyze about future benefits more carefully as compared to an individual having lesser education. **MacCrimmon and**

Wehrung [152] elucidated that higher education encourages risk taking Behavior of an investor. **Larkin et al. [137]** have proven that FRT levels increase with increase in the level education of an investor. Even financial consultants agree with the fact that higher levels of education are linked with increased risk tolerance. Some of the studies have shown few contradictory results as well. However, some contradictory results also exist like the one given by **Heenkenda S. [103]** who explored that level of education has no significant relationship with FRT of individual investors.

In order to check the associability the hypothesis formulated is as follows:

H₀: There is no significant association between education and financial risk tolerance.

H₁: There is significant association between education and financial risk tolerance.

2.4.4.5 Employment and risk tolerance:

Employment status has been considered to be the primary activity for an individual that engages for pay and income. **Roszkowski M.J. [201]** in his research on investment consultants has determined that high ranking professional status is associated to high levels of investor's risk tolerance.

The study conducted by **MacCrimmon and Wehrung [152]** elucidated that self-employment status significantly tops in an individual at higher levels of risk-taking capacity. Self-employed individuals are generally ready to accept the amplified investment volatility in comparison with those who are dependent on others for their earnings and income.

In order to check the associability the hypothesis formulated is as follows:

H₀: There is no significant association between employment and financial risk tolerance.

H₁: There is significant association between employment and financial risk tolerance.

2.4.4.6 Income and risk tolerance:

Various researches have deduced how the income level influences an individual's level of FRT. Starting from the widely held Expected Utility Theory; which hypothesized that wealthier individuals can afford to take more risks. **Friedman B. [70]** in the year 1974 used econometric modeling techniques to conclude that people who receive high salaries generally show a relatively high degree of FRT as compared to those having lesser salary/income. **Cohn et al. [44]** analyzed data of 972 randomly selected investors and explored a positive association stating that investor's risk tolerance increases with the increase in income and wealth.

Blum S.H. [26] conducted a study on various risk-taking behaviors in collaboration with their income status and determined that individuals with higher income (annual incomes of 50000 dollars or more) were keen to endure more risks as compared to the

individuals with lesser incomes. **Cohn et al. [44]** specified that investors with comparatively high income are well-thought to be more risk-tolerant as compared to the investors with less income level. According to **MacCrimmon and Wehrung [152]**, high income group individuals are inclined to accept higher risks as compared to individuals with lower income group.

Not only individual investors, but some studies are also focusing on financial risk tolerance of various firms as well. **Bowman E.H. [28]** argued that problem-associated firms prefer and seek risk as compared to those unflustered and clean firms in order to create additional returns. **Schooley and Worden [210]** done a multivariate regression analysis and derived the conclusion that income or wage growth has a positive correlation with FRT level of an individual. **Ryack K. [205]** studied college youngsters and explored that income was found to be considerably associated with FRT.

Canner et al. [33] stated that the earning capacity of an individual plays a significant part in the study of FRT as it estimates the financial capacity of an investor towards his investments. According to investment consultants; an increased income level is related with access to additional resources. **O'Neill [173]** led a conclusion that high level of income motivates to accept amplified levels of risk tolerance. It is also believed that higher level of income provides the investor an ability and affordability to invest in those financial products featuring the increased financial risk tolerance levels; opposite to those belong to low income group who are generally accessed to less sophisticated financial products and therefore lower risky commercial stuffs.

Finke and Huston [66] explored that income plays a very important part in establishing how an individual consider financial risks related to his savings, expenses as well as investment decisions, whether this income is earned through salaries, revenues or collected over a period of time in term of wealth. The studies showing a relationship between income and FRT include different studies done by **Finke and Huston [66]**; **Grable and Lytton [84]** & **Hallahan et al. [100]**. They had interpreted that high income group individuals have more wealth to accept and incur high risk as compared to lower income group.

Hallahan et al. [100] justified the positive correlation between income and risk tolerance and explained that wealthy individuals have a capacity to afford huge losses easily that may have generated from risky investments and also their collected wealth may even be a replication of their preferred level of risk tolerance. Inversely the wealthy investors may also tend to behave more conservatively with their hard earned money and the poor individuals seek risky investments as a chance to make more money and thus become more keen to consider risk related investments. **Sulaiman E.K. [238]** conducted a study hypothesizing that “High income earners are more risk tolerant than lower income earners” and the results showed value of Pearson’s coefficient as 0.99, which is highly positive association. Income is found to be more realistic element in explaining the risk tolerance over the last few years. **Cooper et al. [45]** found that the

amount of earning an individual obtain, increases the expectation to spend and it absolutely influence them in shaping their risk tolerance attitude. Perceptions and expectations regarding higher income playing an important part in defining an individual's FRT level; as people are keen to get involved in more risk as they expect some sort of earning in future as compared to a condition where they are expecting less or no income in future. In the last few years various researchers namely **Cicchetti and Dubin [43]**; **Dohmen et al. [56]**; **Friedman B. [70]**; **Riley and Chow [195]** have interpreted a positive relationship between the income of investors and their FRT levels. In the year 2012, **Strydom and Metherell [234]** generated a positive relationship pattern between income of investor and their FRT level.

In order to check the associability the hypothesis formulated is as follows:

H_0 : There is no significant association between income and financial risk tolerance.

H_1 : There is significant association between income and financial risk tolerance.

2.4.4.7 Investment preference and risk tolerance:

Investment preference regards the different investment avenues available for the investors before taking any investment decision. Safe avenues include savings, bank FD's, PPF, NSC, Post office savings, and Government securities. Moderate risk avenues include Mutual funds, Life insurance, Debentures, and Bonds. High-risk avenues include Equity share market, Commodity market, FOREX market. Traditional avenues are those that form Real estate, Gold, Silver and Chit funds. Emerging avenues are those that form a part in Virtual real estate, Hedge funds, Private equity investment, Art, and Passion. **Cooper et al. [45]** inferred that investment avenues have a respective relationship with risk tolerance levels. The safer avenues are associated with low-risk tolerance while high-risk avenues correlate with aggressive investors having high-risk tolerance.

Contextual factors regarding a fact include those elements which are fixed and found to be the most stable one. Contextual factors establish the personality of an individual. It includes the psychological aspects, demographical factors, knowledge and attitude factors etc. Situational factors are the elements that keep on changing according to the change in situations and hence they are found to be unstable during any study. Situational factors are generally the influence of the external environment towards an individual. Studies have been elucidated that many contextual and situational factors influence financial risk tolerance capacity of an individual. Situational factors include the socio-economic status of the individual at a particular time horizon. A brief of various researches done in order to study various factors affecting financial risk tolerance has been provided in the **Table 2.4** below.

Table 2.4: Effect of contextual and situational factors on financial risk tolerance.

Researcher Name and Year	Findings
Levin et al. (1986)	Contextual and situational variables play a role in financial risk tolerance.
MacCrimmon and Wehrung (1986)	Risk tolerance in relation to demographics was limited
Roszkowski and Snellbecker (1990)	Contextual and situational variables play a role in financial risk tolerance.
Roszkowski et al. (1993)	Different occupations play an important role towards different financial risk levels
Sung and Hanna (1996)	Demographic variables play an important role towards different financial risk levels
Sulloway (1997)	Demographics, socio-economic status, attitudes about money and personality play a role in financial risk tolerance.
Wang and Hanna (1997)	Age, demographic and socio-economic factors has a relationship with financial risk tolerance and has investigating effects.
Carducci and Wong (1998)	Demographics, socio-economic status, attitudes about money and personality effect financial risk tolerance.
Grable and Lytton (1998)	Age, gender, marital status, occupation, self-employment, income, race, education play a role in financial risk tolerance.
Grable and Joo (1999)	Demographic and socio-economic factors effect financial risk tolerance.
Grable and Joo (2000)	Different variables (demographic, socio-economic and psychological factors) help to understand risk tolerance
Grable (2000)	Influence of demographical factors, socio-economic factors and attitudes pertaining to risk taking behaviour.
Hallahan et al. (2004)	Demographic, socio-economic and psychological, bio psychological and environmental factors help in understanding financial risk tolerance.
Kamiya et al. (2007)	Contextual and situational factors play a role in risk tolerance
Grable and Roszkowski (2008)	Found the role of psychology in risk tolerance
Gilliam and Chatterjee (2010)	Investigate high level of education plays a role in risk tolerance
S.Tabassum Sultana et al.(2011)	Socio-economic characteristics of an individual investor affect financial risk tolerance
Van de Venter et al. (2012)	Determined financial risk as a function of personal traits.
Dr. Ebrahim Kunju Sulaiman (2012)	Demographic variables have a significant effect on financial risk tolerance.
Sadiq and Ishaq (2014)	Demographic variables affect financial risk tolerance.
Stephen Kuzniak et.al. (2015)	Demographic and socio-economic factors affect the financial risk tolerance.

Source: Adapted and modified from Z.Dickason (2017)

To check the associability the hypothesis formulated is as follows:

H₀: There is no significant association between investment preference and financial risk tolerance.

H₁: There is a significant association between investment preference and financial risk tolerance.

2.5 INVESTOR PROFILING

Investors differ as per their financial goals, tolerances towards risk, personal circumstances and desires. It's just an act of balancing between risk and return in order to achieve personal objectives within a range of constraints. According to earlier studies, there have been various types of investors according to their risk profiles who exist in this world of investors.

2.5.1 BB & K Five-Way model (1986)

Thomas Bailard, David Biehl, Ronald Kaiser in his book "Personal Money Management" (1986) found a five-way approach that categorizes the investors based on their level of confidence to make emotional choices. The model, as shown in **Figure 2.3** defines five personalities:

- 1) **Adventurers** - strong-willed confident investors who are ready to take risks.
- 2) **Celebrities** - those who tend to pretend to be active investor but may not really have any clue as to how to control of their financial decisions.
- 3) **Individualists** - Methodical, careful, balanced, analytical and confident investors.
- 4) **Guardians** - Cautious investors who try to safeguard their wealth and are risk averse.
- 5) **Straight arrows** – Average risky investors who don't go into the extremes of the above categories and ready to take moderate risk.

Figure 2.3: BB & K Five-Way Model.

Source: Thomas Bailard, David Biehl and Ronald Kaiser (1986)

2.5.2 Barnwell Two-Way Model (1987)

Marilyn MacGruder Barnwell in the year 1987 developed a Two-Way Model that classified individuals as “passive” or “active” investor.

Passive investors are those belonging to high income group, whether it is by inheritance or by a profession. To these investor securities is more important than risk. These types of investors tend to trust their financial advisor for their financial affairs. They are generally risk avoider and are likely to get involved in diversified portfolios of investments. They tend to follow herd as it seems to be a safer option for them. According to Barnwell, **active investors** are one who have achieved significant prosperity during their lifetime and have hard earned money. They are generally ready to take risks by doing proper study and analysis. These individuals are highly risk tolerant. They got personally involved in decisions regarding their financial affairs.

2.5.3 Micheal M. Pompian Model (2016)

According to Pompian the most important factor an adviser needs to keep in mind is that the investors who are least risk tolerant as well as those who are most risk tolerant are always motivated by various *emotional* biases, while the investors who lie in the categories between these two extremes are generally influenced by *cognitive* biases. These investors are segmented on the basis of different levels of risk tolerance that an individual possess. This risk is generally found by estimating the difference between their original and anticipated income. On basis of amount of risk tolerance an individual possesses, Michael M. Pompian classified them into certain investor personalities.

Table 2.5: Association between behavioural biases and risk tolerance level.

	Conservative	Moderate	Growth	Aggressive
Risk tolerance	Low	Medium	High	Very high
Bias types	Primarily emotional	Primarily cognitive	Primarily cognitive	Primarily emotional
Biases	Endowment	Regret	Conservatism	Overconfidence
	Loss aversion	Hindsight	Availability	Self-control
	Status quo	Framing	Confirmation	Affinity
	Anchoring	Cognitive dissonance	Representativeness	Illusion of control
	Mental accounting	Recency	Self-attribution	Outcome

Source: Michael M. Pompian (2016).

Pompian's categorization the investor is shown in **Table 2.5** where they are segmented into 4 different categories.

- 1) Conservative Investor
- 2) Moderate Investor
- 3) Growth Investor
- 4) Aggressive Investor

2.5.3.1 Conservative Investor:

Conservative investor emphasizes on financial security as well as maintenance of their wealth, which may be either inherited or build wealth. Investors target to minimize their risk and estimated loss on investment. They are the investors who have earned wealth either by way of inheritance or by doing investments in less risky prospects. It is a kind of individual behavior of prudence to take on unnecessary risks. Hence the portfolio of such investors seems to be a monotonous one due to the nonexistence of facts or slow response towards market variations. Conservative investor's portfolio shows high expected return but least portfolio risk.

According to **Michael M. Pompian [184]**, the conservative investors are associated with low-risk tolerance, which means that the risk desire and ability to opt risk is low. Conservative investors are generally uncertain and uncomfortable to take decisions. They are the individuals who take care of the whole family and are interested in doing investments in education and home ownership as well.

2.5.3.2 Moderate Investor:

Moderate investors try to go for investments with an objective to decrease risk and escalate returns consistently. This group of individuals are deficient in their investment understanding and act as followers who follow the trends set by others. **Pompian M. Michael [186]** illustrated that these investors misjudge their risk tolerance and are involved in investment decisions without having any professional advice. They try to consider only those options which seem to be popular regarding investment purpose. Moderate investors are sometimes depressed and hopeless as they lack pleasure and have no skill of investment.

2.5.3.3 Growth Investor:

Growth investors lie within the range of medium to high levels of risk tolerance and their orientation towards the behavioral biases is a cognitive one. **Pompian M. Michael [183]** explored the personality of growth investors as strong desired and liberated one. They sometimes follow their gut, and are not constantly proficient in doing their own investigation. Growth investor possesses the qualities of self-assurance and they often appreciate their investments. They are relaxed in taking decisions involving risk. Growth investors sometimes aim to outperform in market with an objective to earn escalated returns than others on similar segment.

2.5.3.4 Aggressive Investor:

The most prominent characteristic related to aggressive investor is the preparedness to accept high risk and hence they are sometimes overconfident in nature. **Pompian M. Michael [187]**. They possess a readiness to accept substantially elevated risks to maximize returns. **Corter and Chen [46]** found that investors possess high risk tolerance and are inclined to score high in term of investment returns.

BEHAVIORAL FINANCE

3.1 GENERAL

Behavioral finance has been considered as a realm for analyzing the investor's financial decision making that contains psychological elements as well as help in generating new grounds to justify the questions regarding the use of conventional methods for interpreting the investor's Behavior. Over the last few decades, the domain of Behavioral finance has grown immensely to be used in order to guide people for better financial decisions regarding their investments. According to **Hirshleifer D. [107]** this can be done by applying the field of psychology into the financial decision-making of individuals. Market anomalies and inefficiencies led to the development of behavioral finance. **Zindel et. al. [263]** explained behavioral finance is assumed to be combining three domains, namely conceptual knowledge of finance, economics and psychology while making financial investment decisions. **Thaler and Johnson [241]** elucidated that the concept of behavioral economics was originated because of the act of irrationality that the investor show, which was difficult to be explained by traditional financial theories.

Linciano and Soccorso [146] have as observed in their study that individual selections under ambiguity are not found to be in pace with sensible decisions as per standard finance. **Lucarelli and Brighetti [150]** explored that behavioral finance tries to identify how an investor's psychology and emotions play an important part in investment decisions. It helps investors to find how individual make common mistakes in their financial decision by getting influenced by their emotions. It also helps to justify why the so-called rational people take some really irrational investment decisions.

If one wishes to take benefit from behavioral financial studies, then he needs to understand all psychological traps and the strategies to overcome them while making investment decisions as the stock doesn't know what you paid for it. Therefore, **Jordan et al. [119]** suggested that it is important that people should not get emotionally attached to their stocks.

3.2 HISTORY OF BEHAVIORAL FINANCE

The financial domain has been dominated by various standard financial theories till the mid of 1950s which were based on the conventions of investor's rational behavior and investment markets to be efficient. Behavioral economics appears to be a pleonasm at that time. Later a new mindset came into existence when various psychologists studied and found that different financial decisions are taken in an irrational way and hence, they challenged those assumptions of standard finance. Various perceptive and sensitive

biases influence the investors to opt for incorrect investment decisions that reflect their irrational behavior.

Hirschey et al. [106] explained these biases as situation when human brain interprets the statistics by using various shortcuts and emotional filters in financial decisions. As expected, the financial domain at that time was unwilling to accept this view of psychologists who had suggested the behavioral finance model to explain irrational behavior. Behavioral finance in its original version has been considered and accepted by psychologists and economists named Daniel Kahneman and Amos Tversky, who were awarded the Nobel Prize of Economics in 2002 for the same. This was the period when financial experts also started to consider that the investor behaves irrationally. However, in the recent years, the arena of behavioral finance has evolved to its heights and succeeded to explain how the individual and communal psychology influences financial verdicts of investors. Behavioral finance is a flourishing domain that came up to establish a new epoch of understandings regarding human sentiments, behavior and feelings; which was earlier being subjugated by the study of financial markets. The traditional models were focused principally in the direction of the efficient market hypothesis (EMH). According to **Statman Meir [232]** behavioral finance challenged this hypothesis given by “standard finance model” (as referred by Statman) of “how investor decision is inaccurate”, as it fails to implement the psychosomatic and emotional inclinations in financial calculations.

3.3 FROM EMH (EFFICIENT MARKET HYPOTHESIS) TO BF (BEHAVIORAL FINANCE)

Standard financial concepts are assumed to lay its foundation on the pillars of the arbitraging ideologies given by Modigliani and Miller, portfolio principles of Markowitz, capital asset pricing model of William Sharpe, Linter and Black, and option pricing model of Black, Scholes and Merton. Traditional financial concepts believe the markets to be ‘efficient’ and investors to be ‘rational’.

Standard Finance assumes that investor make unbiased decisions to maximize their earnings and wealth. According to **Jensen et al. [116]**, traditional finance theories are directly found to be associated with the perception of rational man, who is found to be much dissimilar from normal investors in Indian financial industry. The rationality is a Behavior that ensures the capability of investors to understand vast and huge data with complex puzzling factors to reach to infinite optimizations.

According to **Montier James [164]**, the prudence of investors and market participants nourish to one of the classical theories of standard finance, i.e. EMH. The efficient market hypothesis was established in the year 1960 by Paul Samuelson and Eugene Fama. It infers that market prices fully imitate all available information. In order to understand the evolution of Behavioral finance, one needs to have a look on efficient market hypothesis proposed by Fama in the year 1965, as behavioral finance domain

was developed from the contradictions of efficient market hypothesis. Fama (1965) posited the idea that stocks operating in an efficient market accurately display the intrinsic value of the stock, and the prices react almost instantaneously as the new information enters into the market.

Standard finance pricing model explains that people value their wealth and investor act carefully and objectively during the process of creating financial decisions. All standard financial economists favored that individual behave rationally, while making economic verdicts and focus on their expected utility. However, the investigators in psychology found that economic decisions are made erratically and absurdly. According to **Hirschey and Nofsinger [106]**, behavioral finance is the study of emotional and intellectual errors that investor make in their financial decisions”.

The basic assumptions of traditional finance are:

- ❖ Investors behave rationally and objectively.
- ❖ Investor considers all accessible market information before making investment decisions, as markets are efficient.
- ❖ Investor always pursues his self-interest in order to maximize wealth.

The standard finance focuses on maximized expected utility by accessing all available information. **Robert J. Shiller [220]** explored his views that, stock prices show haphazard movement through time and the price fluctuations are unpredictable in advance as they occur only in reaction to genuine and new information.

The pivotal work of Kahneman and Tversky (1971, 1979) and Slovic (1972) challenged the rationality assumption and served as a milestone in creating the foundation for modern financial theories. Behavioral finance scholars challenged and argued against traditional finance paradigm which failed to explain the occurrence of anomalies in financial market. Slovic (1969, 1972) studied different stock brokers and investors and stated that investment is a money game that includes a cluster of sentiments, prejudices and tremors. According to him a successful investor is one who is capable to speculate and have the skill to stop shortly when their instinct is about to mediate their investment decision.

Psychology professor Daniel Kahneman gave recognition to the arena of behavioral finance where he studied the detail of heuristics and biases involved while making decisions under uncertainty. His ice breaking work in economics domain was “Prospect theory” in the year 1979 for which he received Noble Prize as well. This work has motivated a series of trials that led to strong deductions regarding how individuals take decision and how they create their preferences. After various studies, even main stream financial economists realized that investor can behave irrationally.

The American Finance Association for the first time organized a session on behavioral finance at its yearly summit in the year 1984. Later **Debondt and Thaler [51]** in the

year 1985 published an article on Behavioral bias of overreaction towards investment decisions. They explained the overreaction hypothesis which contradicted EMH. They outlawed the assumption of regression to average of prices that traditional finance follows.

This concept was later followed by **Shefrin and Statman [218]** in the year 1985 itself that studied and published their work on disposition effect. Disposition effect interprets that the investors connect themselves to former conquerors differently than earlier losers. **Odean Terrance [174], [175]** & **Barber and Odean [12]** interpreted that investors are generally loss averse in nature, display disposition effect and are interested to trade frequently. In year 2000 **ShefrinHersh [217]** also defined how consciousness influences the meadow of finance.

Different studies regarding market anomalies inspected security prices and found that either markets are inefficient which contradicts the concepts propounded by various traditional theories or the asset pricing models are inadequate. Various researches and studies discovered that investors are largely prejudiced by psychological biases and perceptive errors. **Madrian and Shea [153]; Benartzi and Thaler [19]; Choi et al. [40]**. The two important building chunks of behavioral finance were found to be cognitive psychology and limits to arbitrage.

Ritter Jay [196] in the year 2006 and **Hilary and Menzly [105]** establish that market experts also act consistently with different psychologist view regarding human behavior. Behavioral finance opposes the traditional assumption of expected utility intensification of rational investors in an efficient market.

3.4 DEFINITIONS OF BEHAVIORAL FINANCE

- 1) **Linter G. [147]** in the year 1998 defined behavioral finance as a study of interpreting human behavior and perform according to accessible information in order to make investment decisions.
- 2) **Olsen Robert A. [177]** in the year 1998 infers that behavioral finance pursues to identify, understand and forecast the systematic financial market and its consequences on psychological decision-making process.
- 3) **Gilovich and Dale [77]** in year 1999 referred Behavioral finance as a combination of twin purviews namely psychology and economics in order to elucidate why and how individuals make an irrational or specious decision regarding money.
- 4) **ShefrinHersh [217]** in 2000 defined Behavioral finance as a swiftly growing domain that deals with impact of psychology on the behavior of financial individual. Behavioral finance is an application of psychology in to financial

Behavior. Behavioral Finance is the study of describing how psychology impacts financial decision-making process into financial markets.

- 5) **Brabazon T. [29]** in 2000 defined Behavioral finance as a learning of investors suffering from behavioral biases as heuristic driven where an individual investor through innate mental processes take decisions.
- 6) According to **Fromlet and Hubert [71]** in 2001 Behavioral finance conglomerates individual behavior with different market phenomenon and implements understanding from both psychological as well as financial domain.
- 7) **Frankfurter and McGoun [69]** in 2002 explained Behavioral finance is a subdivision of finance associated with psychology and sociology that attempts to determine and elucidate different phenomena considering individual's rational Behavior.
- 8) **Martin Sewel [212]** in the year 2010 defined Behavioral finance as a field that studies the impact of psychology on behavior of a financial specialist and later its repercussions on market. Behavioral Finance provides insight into why and how market responds towards irrationality in human Behavior.
- 9) **William Forbes [68]** in the year 2009 called behavioral finance as a science for the first time where psychology influences financial market. He interpreted that investors are prejudiced by various psychological factors and cognitive biases in their decision making.
- 10) According to **Martin Sewel [212]**, Behavioral finance represents a complete and integrated portrait of investor's irrational Behavior. It's an evolving domain that indicates how various psychological factors affect individual's decision making under circumstances of risk and ambiguity.
- 11) **Zindelet al. [262]** in 2014 labeled behavioral finance as a domain combining 3 different arenas namely finance, economics and cognitive psychology during the process of investor's decision making.
- 12) **Joo and Durri [118]** in the year 2015 demonstrated that behavioral finance is grounded on a concept of "Bounded Rationality" that helps to identify sensible picks including cognitive limitations of decision-maker. The constraints and limitations of human act as boundaries to their rational thinking pattern.

3.5 COMPARATIVE STUDY OF TRADITIONAL AND BEHAVIORAL FINANCE

- ❖ The founding father of behavioral Finance, Richard Thaler put a memorable remark in a conference organized by NBER to an economist named Robert Barro who was supporter of traditional approach; by saying that “The difference between us is that, you assume people are as smart as you are, while I assume people are as dumb as I am”. Behaviorists always argued that behavioral philosophies are required to justify market anomalies that can never be explained by traditional theories. However, the traditionalist explains the rational Behavior of investor by use of calculations and interpretations.
- ❖ Behavioral finance identifies the investor to employ thumb rules of heuristics to take financial decisions that involve different biases and in turn they commit mistakes. Contrarily traditional finance is based on processing facts correctly. Behavioral finance assumes that tolerance of risk and expected return generally changes as per circumstances and emotions or in other words they are having frame dependence. However traditional finance presupposes that people are transparent and objective in their decision-making regarding risk and return.
- ❖ Behavioral finance focuses on sentiments and instincts that play important part in manipulating financial decisions while traditional finance justifies individual decisions by reasons, logic and independent judgments. Behavioral finance explains that heuristic-driven prejudices and faults, emotions and communal influence create inconsistency in market prices on the other hand traditional finance argues the financial market to be efficient and security prices are an unprejudiced evaluation of their core value. Behavioral finance supports that prices are pushed in both directions by various investors. The optimists are disappointed while pessimists are surprised. Instead traditional finance based EMH explains that prices follow a random walk, they can fluctuate to extremes but came back to equilibrium on time.

3.6 INFLUENCING FACTORS OF BEHAVIORAL FINANCE

Market anomalies were the first and foremost area of concern that attracted the minds of economists to doubt and challenge various traditional financial theories. **Massol and Molines [159]** in the year 2015 studied various market anomalies. They found market anomalies to be associated with several factors like noise trading; where the investor makes a decision without doing proper fundamental analysis before investment, overconfidence, over optimism, herd Behavior and lack of attention of investors. Behavioral Finance is based on following assumptions:

- ❖ **Loss Aversion:** The selves of an individual investor to avoid losses more instead of increasing returns.

- ❖ Bounded Rationality: The way, an individual behaves, in order to limit his/her rationality.
- ❖ Risk Denial: Refusal of accepting the underlying risk even after knowing it.

According to **Linciano and Soccorso [146]** behavioral finance explains that people generally do not rely on the calculations and facts available correctly, but instead they trust on heuristics to understand composite situations in order to take decisions rapidly and proficiently. Behavioral finance indulges an individual into investment decision-making prejudices that create mental and affective process, with the help of various cognitive and emotional factors. Mental processes include cognitive factors involved with investor's preferences. While emotional processes include emotional factors involved with investor's social interactions. **Lucarelli and Brighetti [150]** described it as given in the **Figure 3.1 and Figure 3.2**

Figure 3.1: Factors contributing mental process.

Source: Lucarelli and Brighetti (2011)

Figure 3.2: Factors contributing mental process.

Source: Lucarelli and Brighetti (2011)

3.7 BEHAVIORAL BIASES

Psychologists have studied and created a framework of different behavioral factors that influence decision makers to form their investment opinions.

Table 3.1: Behavioral biases and their contributors.

Bias	Name of Contributors (Year)
Representativeness	Tversky and Kahneman (1974), Dhar and Kumar (2001), Kaestner (2005)
Overconfidence	Fischhoff, Solvic and Lichtenstein (1977), Alpert and Raiffa (1984), Tversky (1990), Wood (1996), Odean (1998), Daniel, Hirshleifer and Subrahmanyam (1998), Barber and Odean (2000), Gervais and Odean (2001)
Gamblers Fallacy	Kahneman and Tversky (1974), Richard Thaler (1999), Odean (1998), Barberis (2003), Gevaris et al. (2001), Holt and Laury (2002), Lucarelli and Brighetti (2011), Singh and Sudhir (2012)
Availability Bias	Tversky (1990), Odean (1998), Singh and Sudhir (2012)
Loss aversion	Rothschild and Stiglitz (1970), Kahneman and Tversky (1979), Tversky (1990), Lebaron (1999), Coval and Shumway (2003)
Regret aversion	Filbesk et al. (2005), Berkelaar and Kouwenberg (2008), Hwang and Satchell (2010)
Mental accounting	Thaler and Shefrin (1981), Shiller (1998), Tversky (1999), Barberis and Huang (2001), Rockenbach (2004)
Herding behaviour	Scharfstein and Stein (1990), Lakonishok et al. (1991), Christie and Huang (1995)

Source: Compiled by researcher

The studies show that various financial decisions are driven by an individual's emotions and are found to be associated with universal and unconscious needs, fears, greed etc. There have been various studies conducted at different time span to conceptualize these behavioral biases.

The **Table 3.1** shows a brief snapshot of various biases under study and their contributors. These biases are closely related to human psyche and play important role in creating human selves. Behavioral biases are found to influence almost all type of investors in one or the other way.

N.M. Waweru [254] in the year 2008 has categorized these behavioral biases into three main domains as shown in **Table 3.2** below.

- 1) Prospect theory and framing factor associated biases
- 2) Heuristics related biases
- 3) Other biases(Herding related)

Table 3.2: Grouping of Behavioral factors.

<i>Group</i>	<i>Behavioral variables</i>
Heuristic Theory	- Representativeness
	- Overconfidence
	- Anchoring
	- Gambler's fallacy
	- Availability Bias
Prospect Theory	- Loss aversion
	- Regret aversion
	- Mental accounting
Herding Effect	- Buying and Selling decisions of other investors

Source: N M Waweruet al.(2008)

3.7.1 Framing and Prospect theory factors:

3.7.1.1 Framing

Frame dependence explains that an investor's behavior rest on the way in which their decision regarding problems has been outlined. Evidences show that difference in the individual preference lead to variation in the options framing in terms of profits and losses. According to **Tversky and Kahneman [247]** in the year 1973 framing explains the systematic structuring of the questions and their evaluation. According to Modigliani and Miller approach, if an individual has one dollar in right pocket and transfer it to left pocket, he is not at all richer. Contrarily Mr. Franco explains "Frame Independent" investor as one who shows responsiveness towards fluctuations in his total capital.

Frame is a belief used to describe a particular decision problem to understand, how it has been framed. Frame dependence explains a behavior as relevant one. According to **ShefrinHersh [217]** frame dependence shows the combination of cognitive and emotional factors. The Cognitive aspect explains how people organize their information mentally; in order to incur losses and gains. The cognitive factors include those heuristics that consist of mental shortcuts which are taken by individuals in order to take financial decisions. According to behaviorists, the decisions that involve heuristics may lead to either above expected or below expected results. **S. Singh [225]** in year 2012 studied that irrational behavior of investors is subjected to different cognitive illusions.

3.7.1.2 Prospect Theory:

This theory was a milestone benchmark in the field of behavioral finance. It was developed by economists namely Daniel Kahneman & Amos Tversky in the year 1979. Prospect theory is associated with human behavior. It explains how an individual or a group behaves in the sphere of uncertainty. Prospect theory describes how people frame and value their decisions regarding their investments. The Prospect theory explains that an individual focus on his outcomes regarding any decision. The theory talks about an individual's financial picks in terms of prospective gains or losses towards a particular reference point. According to economists, an individual sense more intensely towards the pain from loss as compared to pleasure from same gain. Prospect theory is a statistical illustration of the average behavior of individuals. The exclusive criteria of prospect theory are:

- Prospect theory considers that individual choices rely on the subjectively towards a reference point, which is independent of an individual's situation of wealth.
- These reference points create a frame towards prospect, which ultimately affect the choice selection.
- An individual weighs his losses as twice as that of gains.

The **Figure 3.3** explains the Prospect value function as given in the theory.

Figure 3.3: Prospect value function.

Source: Daniel Kahneman & Amos Tversky (1979)

3.7.1.2.1 Mental Accounting:

Mental accounting concept was proposed by Richard Thaler in the year 1985. Traditional finance explains every financial decision to be based on rational calculations however in reality people neither possess such computational skills nor have will power to evaluate their decisions. People usually divide their wealth into different mental accounts having different significance. Mental accounting elucidates the human tendency to place different events into separate mental accounts on the basis of perceived attributes. According to **Richard Thaler [243]** these “mental accounts” are generally separated on the basis of risk into separate buckets. This is done on the basis of different subjective criteria such as source of earning and intend of each account which later contribute to irrational Behaviors.

“Mental accounting” infers how an individual integrate his wealth into different parts of his mind. This biased nature is a result of either under monitoring or over monitoring of portfolios. Every individual makes his mind regarding his wealth and its segregation into different heads of expenses according to the varying degrees of risk tolerance and circumstances in order to achieve overall objective. The life experiences of any individual are grouped into separate mental sections and in future it influences the decisions as well as investment Behavior. Hence mental accounting is a process to keep a check on all gains and losses incurred by an individual, and then reminding and re-examining it at the time of relevance. According to **Richard Thaler [242]** an individual has three categories of mental accounts:

1. Consumption account (for normal expenses)
2. Income account (for keeping revenues)
3. Wealth income (to keep track on different sources of earnings)

According to **Lucarelli and Brighetti [150]** mental accounting results in creation of outcomes that ignore the association between different mental accounts and their effect in generation of financial choices of investors. As per **Jagongo and Mutswenje [113]** the theory of mental accounting says that if an individual earlier incurs losses of returns below expectations then he generally wishes to remain in a cautious position to trade his stocks even in the period of normal returns as well. Mental accounting bias has shown its association with different demographic variables (used in the study). It has been studied here with the help of the hypothesis below:

H_0 : There is no significant association between Mental Accounting bias and demographics.

H_1 : There is significant association between Mental Accounting bias and demographics.

3.7.1.2.2 Loss Aversion:

Loss Aversion is a behavioral phenomenon seen in the decision making of individuals, under risk and ambiguity. Individuals suffering from loss aversion are found to be more sensitive towards losses in comparison with gains. **Tversky and Kahneman [249]** explained loss aversion as a crucial aspect of Prospect Theory. People suffering from this bias found themselves not able to accept losses.

ShefrinHersh [217] calls this Behavior as “*Get-even-itis*” where an individual assumes that the market will operate according to their benefits and when the market start falling then they will move out of investments before incurring losses. Loss aversion evaluates that the mental penalty associated with a loss is much higher than the mental reward associated with similar gain. According to **Robert Shiller [220]** it is a human tendency to go to extreme in order to avoid losses which ultimately inhibits their success rate. The human attitude towards risks and rewards can be much different than it is towards losses.

Loss aversion bias may encourage investor towards other biases as well like herd Behavior, where the investor unknowingly invests in fraudulent companies just because they carry insurance against losses. **Odean Terrance [174]** argues that loss aversion is a common bias which can be seen in investor’s Behavior, but it leads to an incorrect and bad decision-making which directly affects the wealth of investor. Loss Aversion bias has shown its relation with different demographic variables (used in the study). It has been studied here with the help of hypothesis below:

H₀: There is no significant association between Loss Aversion bias and demographics.

H₁: There is significant association between Loss Aversion bias and demographics.

3.7.1.2.3 Regret Aversion:

Regret aversion bias is an emotional tendency of an individual to avoid the pain associated with a wrong/poor decision. **Tversky and Kahneman [248]** had explained that every decision is lastly associated with two different emotions: one is regret and second is rejoice. Regret describes the displeasure while rejoice explains the happiness of taking a particular decision.

Regret aversion bias make an individual risk averse. **Michael M. Pompain [184]** explored that how an individual try to avoid taking risky decisions as it will lead to give them a feeling of displeasure or disappointment. In accordance to Regret-Theory, people started fearing that if their decision will turn out to be wrong and hence they start omitting those alternatives in decision making process. Regret Aversion bias has shown its relation with different demographic variables; which has been studied here with the help of hypothesis below:

H₀: There is no significant association between Regret Aversion bias and demographic variables.

H₁: There is significant association between Regret Aversion bias and demographic variables.

3.7.2 Heuristics:

Heuristics is generally found to be associated with those decisions centered on investment regarding most recent available information. Here the contextual facts are not available which lead to incorrect interpretations. **M. Kannadhasan [124]** in the year 2015 and **Abreu M. [2]** in the year 2014 explored that the judgements regarding recent accessible information may result in possible decrease in investment returns.

Lucarelli and Brighetti [150] the decisions involving heuristics motivate an investor to take investment decisions typically by trial & error and hence lead to creation of thumb rules. According to **Brabazon T. [29]** heuristics generally happen when an investor found himself indulged into difficult judgments including complex statistical calculations and hence majority of them utilize their limited heuristics, that can reduce this decision-making task in to simpler one. **Tversky and Kahneman [247]** in the year 1973 viewed heuristics as a situation when people recall the occurrence of an event and they tend to do it same as it comes to their mind. **Slovic Paul [227]** explored that heuristics create the biased assessments in decisions. These decisions involve those mental shortcuts which ultimately result in an incorrect interpretation.

3.7.2.1 Representativeness:

Representativeness infers the decision making on the basis of stereotyping. It makes individual to seek things the way others are seeing. Studies suggest that the investment decisions including this bias are based on perceptions of patterns which may or may not exist in real life. According to **M. Kannadhasan [125]**, representativeness can better be understood as a situation where the investor tends to purchase the ‘hot’ stocks (which were currently in news because of their performance) and avoid the poor performing stocks. **DeBondt and Thaler [50]** described that this behavior provides an elucidation for investor’s overreaction. **Statman Meir [232]** mentioned representativeness as the “law of small numbers”. Sampling theory concludes that an arbitrary sample resembles to the population very closely. Investors suffering from this bias generally follow the law of small numbers while dealing with investments. **S. Singh [225]** concludes that representativeness makes individual believe that the recent trends are repetitive in nature and hence the investor tends to overreact.

According to **Tversky and Kahneman [248]** representativeness is a Behavior that predicts how people judge the probabilities related to different events as A, B and vice versa. This bias results to creation of different thoughts regarding events which are acquainted to them. The bias can be identified with the help of following actions:

- ❖ Investors try to generate patterns regarding recent investment data.
- ❖ Investor tries to forecast or extrapolate past returns.
- ❖ Investors go for investments having good previous track record as they are a representative of well-performing funds.
- ❖ Investors show over-optimism towards past winners.
- ❖ Investors suffer from good company-good stock syndrome.

According to **N. Barberis [15]** representativeness makes an individual judge the events on the basis of popularity they have gained in the recent past. For instance, the share prices of a company keep on increasing if they book high returns in last quarter because the investor tend to infer future growth as well on the basis of past trends. Representativeness bias has shown its association with different demographic variables as per the hypothesis given below:

H_0 : There is no significant association between Representativeness bias and demographics.

H_1 : There is a significant association between Representativeness bias and demographics.

3.7.2.2 Gambler's fallacy:

The name of this effect was originated from the notion that gambling in general is assumed to be associated with Behavior, where an individual is confident that he will definitely outperform in any situation. In investment perspective, it is a bias where an individual incorrectly foresees the previous trend movements and expects for their future reversals. Here the investor thinks that the occurrence of an event may repeat itself in future again. **Barberis and Thaler [14]** explained gamblers' fallacy is a bias that generates when an individual inappropriately predicts a trend to show its reverse trend. **Kempf and Ruenzi [127]** explored that this thought process leads the investor to anticipate either positive or negative market returns.

It is a general belief that gamesters can outperform in any market at majority of the times. Gamblers fallacy is an outcome of "gambling behavior" of the investors that fails to predict market movements accurately and results in failure to outperform in market. **S. Singh [225]** explained that gamblers are extremely buoyant towards their capabilities to outperform, that they even go for betting on forthcoming trends of the market. Gambler's Fallacy bias has shown its association with different demographic variables as per the hypothesis given below:

H_0 : There is no significant association between Gamblers Fallacy bias and demographics.

H_1 : There is significant association between Gamblers Fallacy bias and demographics.

3.7.2.3 Overconfidence:

The word “confidence” is described as “belief in oneself and one’s abilities with full conviction”. However, the word “overconfidence” takes this Behavior to one step further and takes reliant Behavior to the extremes. **Ricciardi and Simon [193]**. People generally have the inclination to overvalue their skills and capabilities to ensure success. Studies show that some persons are overconfident in their decisions. Psychologists have found that overconfident people have a habit of misjudging the precision of their forecasts.

Overconfidence originates from a misapprehension of knowledge. The human brain is intended to infer the easily accessible information only. According to **Lichtenstein et al. [143]**, investments with overconfidence bias lead to inappropriate decisions. It causes investor to overestimate their skills and underestimate the market risks. They exaggerate their abilities to control market fluctuations. Overconfident people are habitually optimistic. Overconfidence individuals have faith in their abilities with strong persuasion. **V. Ricciardi [194]** found that overconfidence is seen and assumed as an overestimation of probabilities for occurrence of an event.

Overconfidence is a human tendency that involves miscalibration. The study explains 2 main facets of overconfidence are miscalibration and above average returns. First is the situation that arises when an individual assigns too narrow estimates of probabilities as confidence interval limit. Research by **Massol and Molines [159]** show that men are inclined to be more confident than women and this tendency decreases with increase in experience. According to the study of **Barber and Odean [13]** it is being identified that women are less confident than men and hence women invest less as compared to men. **Ngoc [170]** interpreted that overconfidence makes an investor to invest in high volume and prefer speculations of experts. **Robert Shiller [220]** in his research identified that overconfident people are inclined to underestimate their error margins.

Barber and Odean [11] argue individuals suffering from overconfidence bias are not rational investors as they are much confident about their own philosophies and verdicts. People, who misinterpret their abilities, have extreme confidence in accuracy of their knowledge and skills; consider them better than others. According to **Lucarelli and Brighetti [150]** individual suffering from overconfidence bias describe their success as their own contribution. According to **Bodie et al. [27]** in 2013, overconfidence is found to be associated with courage, but it sometimes deviates the human psychology to take correct decisions regarding investments. **Andersson and Eriksson [6]** explored that overconfidence bias creates illusions in the minds of an individual which lead them to overestimate their abilities and make them believe that they are best in their decisions.

Lewellen et al. [142] inferred that overconfident investors and found that they believe returns to be highly predictable and they expect high returns than less confident people. **Odean Terrance [175]** defined overconfidence as a tendency of individual to

overestimate their knowledge precision regarding the value of money. **Daniel et al. [48]** developed an idea regarding overconfidence among investors who overestimate their precision and concludes that it leads to price hitches. **Gervais and Odean [74]** generated a market model to assess overconfidence. According to them overconfidence is found in those individuals who have earlier experienced escalated returns, as an outcome they trade in high volume and frequency. **Montier James [163]** studied and found the presence of overconfidence bias even in financial professionals as well. According to him these professionals overestimate their ability to select a good performing stock. They go for comparison of their results with lay people and found that professionals are more overconfident than layman. The associability of Overconfidence bias with different demographic variables have been studied with the help of following hypothesis:

H₀: There is no significant association between Overconfidence bias and demographics.

H₁: There is significant association between Overconfidence bias and demographics.

3.7.2.4 Availability Bias:

Availability bias is the tendency to judge the probability of occurrence of an event on the basis of an ease to remember the related information. **Tversky and Kahneman [248]** had provided a way to get relevant information about an event is to note down all the connected and associated information in form of points that count about 8 and above. The investor is also affected by the fact that how readily they can assemble or gather all relevant information. For example: If an individual is reading about the highway accidents on a daily basis, he/she will try to avoid travelling through highways.

Investment decisions are also being affected by the information easily available in the market; this ultimately leads them to stick in the web of availability bias. **Tversky and Kahneman [248]** explained that the information being repeated a number of times get stuck in the mind and later impact the risk-taking capacity of an individual. Availability bias is the shortcut method used by the mind of investor relying on the recent available information while taking a particular decision. The associability of Availability bias with different demographic variables have been studied with the help of following hypothesis:

H₀: There is no significant association between Availability bias and demographic variables.

H₁: There is significant association between Availability bias and demographic variables.

3.7.3 Other Biases:

3.7.3.1 Herd Behavior:

Available literature shows different studies regarding herd behavior in stock markets. One of the pioneer investigations on herding is done by **Lakonishok et al. [134]**. They studied the herd behavior as a tendency of investors to mimic the investment activities of others at the same point of time. It can be seen as a tendency of buying the winning stocks while selling the losers. **Scharfstein and Stein [209]** examined the elements that lead to herd behavior in the investment decision making. They developed a model to categorize smart executives from biased executives; assumed as dumb. Smart executives are one who receive informative indications while biased managers receive noise indications. **Hwang and Salmon [109]** found that herd behavior is mostly seen during the time of market stress. The reason being that investor become anxious at this stage as the level of uncertainty is very high. In this situation they become doubtful about their own beliefs and tend to follow others to play safe. **Christie and Huang [42]** developed a measure to evaluate the degree of herding among individuals. They termed it as H-statistic which considers the fundamentals of an investment firm and the influence of market volatility.

Scharfstein and Stein [209] along with **Bikhchandani et al. [25]** explored that herding bias lead to speculative bubbles that cause substantial losses when the bubbles burst. Investors with herding bias make an individual to access only suboptimal information which results in irrational decisions. According to **De Bondt and Forbes [49]** herding behavior lead to a reduction in dispersion and escalation in mean of forecasts. This Behavior ultimately increases the unpredictability in the earnings. **N.M. Waweru [254]** in his study identified that, investors possess herd behavior as they are worried about what others will think regarding their decisions, in case they will incur losses.

Laoand Singh [136] examined herding pattern in Indian as well as Chinese stock markets and found that herding is high during extreme market situations (bullish or bearish) but the pattern may be dissimilar. In the Chinese market the herding behavior is high when the market is down (bear phase) while in India herding is high when market is at hike (bull phase). The Herd behavior of an investor is found to be related to the demographics with the help of hypothesis given below:

H_0 : There is no significant association between Herd bias and demographics.

H_1 : There is significant association between Herd bias and demographics.

3.8 SPECIFIC LITERATURE REGARDING BEHAVIORAL FINANCE ASSOCIATED WITH FINANCIAL RISK TOLERANCE OVER THE LAST FEW DECADES

3.8.1 Till the year 2000:

1. **Tversky and Kanheman [248]:** (1971): The study here describes the concept of gambler's fallacy which is generally misinterpreted as the laws of chance. The most prominent impact of gamblers fallacy can be seen on the financial market as the investors suffering from this bias are generally biased towards prediction of stock prices. Gambler's Fallacy bias arises when investor try to predict on the basis of trends inappropriately and hence create a contrarian thinking. Here the investor has a thought process based on a perception that errors in random events are self-recurring and self-correcting.
2. **Tversky and Kanheman [247]:** (1973): They explained about availability bias as the "phenomenon of illusory correlation". Author studied that the investor is said to use the heuristic when he assumes the possibility of any event by the chances of its occurrence or association with an event that strikes to mind very first time. Availability bias tries to explain various stock market anomalies financially.
3. **Werner DeBondt and Thaler [257]:** (1985): Authors here studied the Behavior of investors and identified that one of the most significant Behavior that investor has is to be overconfident in their judgments. They generally over-estimate the trustworthiness of their knowledge and expertise due to which the stock markets over-react and create huge market disturbances.
4. **Haliassos and Bertuat [99]:** (1995): The study here aims to find the influence of behavioral biases on depositor's financial decision making. Seven biases have been used for study namely overconfidence, confirmation, excessive optimism, illusion of control, loss aversion, mental accounting and status quo. It is seen that the first four biases have direct impact on decision making while the next three biases have no impact.
5. **Robert J. Shiller [198]:** (1999): According to Shiller investor doesn't behave rationally. Opposite to it they are generally motivated by greed and fear. They generally try to speculate stocks between impractical high and low values. Investors are normally deluded by excessive emotions, independent thinking and the voice of herd. Hence, they form unreasonable expectations for future performance of stocks and the inclusive economy therefore swing above and below fundamental values and create market anomalies.

6. **Richard Thaler [243]:** (1999): He defined mental accounting as a tendency of individuals where people separately divide their earnings into distinct accounts on the basis of various biased objectives. They keep on losing stock value and try to provide various reasons to justify their action; but the fact is that they are not willing to accept that they are actually incurring loss. Here investor has a mentality that they will incur loss only at the time of purchasing or selling the stocks, which is actually a mental accounting error.

3.8.2 From 2001 to 2010:

1. **Grable and Lytton [85]:** (1999b): They have explored all conceptual and empirical issues regarding the development of a financial risk-tolerance scale instrument. Risk tolerance is a major factor plays an important role in various household's financial decisions. Still very few valid and reliable scale of assessment are available to be used by financial service providers and educators. Authors contributed in development of a 13-item risk assessment scale that can act as the foundation for the development of a many more widely used scales and indexes.
2. **Shapira and Venezia [213]:** (2001): This study is focused on exploring disposition effect among investors of Israeli brokerage house. The aim was to compare and check whether this Behavioral bias exists only with individual investors or it holds with professional investors as well. For this the researcher used trading frequency and volume as variables and the result shows that disposition effect exists with professional investors as well. However, the effect is found to be significantly weaker for professional investors than for individual investors.
3. **Barber and Odean [11]:** (2001): The study here aims to find that whether men are different than women in their psychological trading Behavior. Men are found to be more overconfident and hence they overestimate their information as well as expected gains of trading. Men sometimes trade when the expected returns are negative. According to study men trade 45 percent more than women in overconfidence. Excessive trading reduces men's returns by 2.65 percentage points a year in comparison to 1.72 percentage points for women.
4. **Grable and Lytton [84]:** (2001): Their study regarding SCF reports findings to calculate and interpret financial risk tolerance. The researcher had done a comparative analysis between SCF assessment measure and a 13-item risk-tolerance assessment index. The results show SCF scale has few limitations over

13-item risk tolerance scale. However, more research is needed to confirm the results interpreted by the researcher.

5. **Chandra Abhijeet [34]:** (2008): Chandra attempted to explore the association between behavioral biases, investor's psychology and their decision making. He tried to examine the investor's attitude towards risk tolerance and behavioral factors. The researcher here also interprets that investors are not always rational in their decision making as explained in classical financial theories. Investors are influenced by various psychological factors like fear and greed, Cognitive Dissonance, heuristics, Mental accounting, anchoring etc. Hence, it's been suggested that these Behavioral factors must be considered along with various risk factors during investment decision making process.
6. **Michael M. Pompain [183]:** (2008): Author here identified that anchoring bias occurs when investors are influenced by purchase price levels at different places and try to take advantage of price change levels. They tend to get attracted with arbitrage pricing and rely mostly on available market information to decide between situations like "should I buy this or sell this stock now?"
7. **Jayen B. Patel [115]:** (2008): Researcher here studied two calendar effects found in the stock returns of Indian stock market. Author studied first effect known as the November-December effect where he concluded that mean returns for these two months are found to be significantly higher than those of the remaining ten months. He had also identified a second effect known as March-to-May effect where the mean returns for three months i.e. March, April and May are found to be significantly low as compared to those during the remaining nine months. Author also concluded that the two calendar effects studied are independent to each other.
8. **Subrahmanyam [236]:** (2008): The review study done by author is focused on empirical study regarding the theories of Behavioral finance and corporate finance. Author has reviewed the studies regarding trading activity of investors in order to judge their Behavioral pattern over last 2 decades.
9. **N.M. Waweru [253]:** (2009): He tried to find an association between anchoring bias and representativeness which is very prominently seen in recent experiences in stock exchange. If the investor gets anchored to the correct investment principle then it can save them from a lot mental mess but the problem arises when a correct investment principle doesn't guarantee abnormal returns. These principles generally help investors targeting long-term returns.

10. **Jason Potts [188]:** (2010): The study here reported a new framework of “Behavioral Innovation Economics” which helps an investor to take choice under behaviorally hard situations. The study provides an innovation system that help investor from being caught into Behavioral traps.
11. **Anbar and Eker [57]:** (2010): Anbar and Eker explored that FRT plays a major role as an element that need to be examined before making investment decision. In order to interpret the risk tolerance various determining factors like financial risk perception and other need to be considered. They generated an investment decision model that is based on four fundamental aspects for making any financial or investment risk plan. These factors are identified as goal, time limit, financial steadiness and levels of FRT. The results interpret that highly risk averse investor has lesser FRT and vice-versa.
12. **Kabra et al. [73]:** (2010): They have conducted a research titled “Factors Influencing Investment Decision of Generations in India: An Econometric Study”. The aim of the study was to identify the elements that affect investment Behavior and to establish a relationship with these factors towards investment risk tolerance and decision making. The study targeted different groups of males and females belonging to different age categories. The study confirms that every individual that may seem equal in all aspects can have different financial needs. Therefore, various demographics like age, gender etc. play an important part in accessing the risk taking capacity of investor.

3.8.3 From 2010 to till Now:

1. **Hemanathan and Anbalagan [104]:** (2011): This is a review paper which is focused on finding an overview of the new and upcoming field of psychology in finance i.e. behavioral finance. The paper includes summary of important heuristics in financial decision making. Also, it explores the ways that can help the industrialists in order to develop customer oriented policies.
2. **Chiraet el. [39]:** (2011): The researcher here had done a survey on graduate and undergraduate students with the help of 45 questions being asked from them. The results show that the students are overconfident and optimistic in nature. However, they do not follow illusion of control and familiarity heuristics. Some of the students are found to follow confirmation bias as well. After checking the risk tolerance students are found to be risk averse.
3. **Gaur et al. [72]:** (2011): Arti with co-authors conducted a study titled “Difference in Gender Attitude in Investment Decision Making in India”. The study is focused on importance of female investors in the investment market. The aim of this study is

to find the differences in the Investment Decision Making (IDM) process among various female and male investors. For analysis chi-square test has been used as statistical tool. The study tries to create level of awareness for females regarding various investment avenues as they seem to have low confidence in their investment decisions and have comparatively lesser satisfaction level.

4. **Lin Huei-wen [144]:** (2011a): The research here tries to find effect of rational decision making and demographics on various Behavioral biases. For study the author had considered 3 biases as disposition, herding and overconfidence bias. In order to check impact of rational decision making 3 factors are considered into account namely identification of demand, searching information and evaluation of various alternatives. For demographics 4 variables considered as gender, age, occupation and income. The analysis has been interpreted in the form of structural models.
5. **Lin Huei-wen [145]:** (2011b): This study is done on the investors from Taiwanese stock exchange. In order to find the relationship of rational decision-making process with Behavioral biases SEM analysis has been used by the researcher. Also, the effect of demographic variables has been studied towards various Behavioral biases namely disposition bias, herding bias and overconfidence bias.
6. **Jamshidinavid et al. [114]:** (2012): The study here explores the relationship among investor's personality traits and their demographics on financial Behavior. The survey has been conducted on investors of Tehran stock exchange. Big five personality traits have been used for the study. Three Behavioral biases namely overconfidence, herding and disposition are studied for creating a SEM model. The result shows strong and positive relationship among personality traits and investment biases, however there is a no significant relationship found among demographics and biases.
7. **Zaidi and Tauni [261]:** (2012): The study is aimed to identify the association between Investor's Personality Traits, Demographics and Overconfidence Bias in Lahore Stock Exchange (LSE). It shows age and education has no effect on overconfidence bias but investment experience does have an impact. It is found that there is a positive relationship between consciousness, extroversion and agreeableness traits with overconfidence bias. However, a negative correlation is found between neuroticism and overconfidence bias.
8. **Thomas and Rajendran [245]:** (2012): The researcher here investigated the investment Behavior of Indian investor with the help of BB & K 5-way model. The investor personalities have been described as adventurer, celebrity, individualistic, guardian and straight arrow. Delphi method has been used by the researcher in order

to collect data; the result shows the association between psychological trades of different investors and their investment choices.

9. **Rekik and Boujelbene [192]:** (2013): To find existence of various Behavioral biases among Tunisian investors this study has been performed in the form of a survey and factor analysis is used. The study reveals the presence of herding bias, representativeness, anchoring bias, loss aversion and mental accounting. However, the overconfidence bias was found to be absent in Tunisian stock market. The study also reveals an association between demographics and financial biases.
10. **Bashir et al. [60]:** (2013): Authors have performed a study that examines the relationship between demographics and personality traits. The risk tolerance of the investors has also been considered as a factor. The SEM-model has been developed. It has been concluded that overconfidence, herding bias and risk tolerance has no significant relationship while herding and disposition effect are found to be associated with risk taking Behavior.
11. **Lakshmi et al. [135]:** (2013): The study here aims to identify the difference in the Behavioral traits of long and short term stock investors. The researcher has used SEM method to interpret the results. In order to find Behavioral traits three biases are used for study namely overconfidence, Loss/Risk aversion and herding bias. Chi square techniques have been used which reveals the significant difference in the Behavior of long and short term trade investors.
12. **Bashir et al. [59]:** (2013): This study has been done to identify the variables having least and most influence on the investor's investment Behavior of individual investors of Pakistan. Factor analysis conducted results in creating five factors as self- image/firm image, neutral information, accounting information, personal financial needs and advocate recommendation.
13. **Bashir et al. [16]:** (2013): This paper examines the relationship among demographic variables, personality Traits (for which Big Five model has been used), investment biases and risk taking Behavior. Results suggest that personality traits influence the two investment biases i.e. overconfidence and herding bias. Also, personality traits have an impact on risk taking Behavior while demographics do not have significant relationship with investment biases and risk taking Behavior.
14. **Takeda et al. [240]:** (2013): The survey here has been done on investors of Japanese stock market in order to examine the effect of their investment literacy on their biases. It is found that there is a negative correlation between investment literacy and overconfidence bias which interprets that higher the investment literacy, lower the overconfidence bias.

15. **Ton et al. [246]:** (2014): The study shows the presence of psychology elements affecting investors' decision making in the Vietnam Stock Exchange. Five factors, namely overconfidence, optimism, herd Behavior, psychology of risk and pessimistic are found to be existed in Vietnamese investors.
16. **Mutswenje and Vincent [167]:** (2014): The study here aims to identify the factors which influence individual investors from Nairobi stock exchange. The researcher here found 5-factors named as self-image, accounting information, neutral information, advocate recommendation and personal financial needs. The study has been conducted on 42 investors where factor analysis has been done. The result shows an association with the factors on individual investment decision in the form of correlation coefficient.
17. **Kengatharan and Kengatharan [128]:** (2014): The study here has been conducted on investors of Colombo Stock Exchange in order to find Behavioral biases named Herding, Heuristics, Prospect and Market factors. It is found that heuristic factor has high influence while herding factor has low influence on investment decision. Among the Behavioral factors choice of stock and over confidence bias has negative influence on investment performance. Anchoring bias has a positive influence on investment performance. All other factors found to have no influence on investment performance.
18. **Hon Tai-Yuen [108]:** (2015): The study here aims to identify Behavior of small investors from Hong Kong stock market. The researcher has used factor analysis in order to find five major factors as reference group, monitor investments, personal background, reaction to announcements and cognitive style. The study concluded only first two factors i.e. reference group and monitor investments, as most significant.
19. **Sukanya and Thimmarayappa [237]:** (2015): The study aims to identify various Behavioral biases affecting portfolio investment decisions. It tries to find the difference between traditional and modern theories of investment decision making. The study reveals that there are some common mistakes done by investor because of their irrational Behavior. Author has also given some measures to overcome these mistakes by making systematic investments.
20. **Ahmad et al. [3]:** (2015): The study here aims to ascertain the influence of behavioral biases on investment decisions and in turn investment satisfaction. The Behavioral factors are found to be associated with psychological variables and risk Behavior. The psychological variables used here for study are grouped into heuristics, prospect and herding categories. Risk Behavior had considered risk perception, attitude and the propensity of risk.

21. **Islamoğlu et al. [112]:** (2015): The study tries to discover the factors that impact individual investor Behavior and for the same a survey has been done from various bankers in Bartın. The results show that during the process of financial decision making the investors of Bartın city are affected by various factors like income level, previous investment experiences, expert's opinions and financial stability. In order to reduce risk, the investors have alternative plans for their investment and hence have high self-esteem and overconfidence.
22. **Willows and Darron [258]:** (2015): The paper studies the difference in trading frequency and its impact on return generation among males and females. The study results that there is a negative association between trading frequency and returns. Also male respondents are found to trade more than female respondents. It is also seen that men have higher variability in their return generation.
23. **A.Charles and Kasilingam [1]:** (2016): The research here is done to check an impact of Behavioral biases on investors' investments in various investments avenues as well as in the equity market. In order to find biases, the researcher has used factor analysis which identifies 6 factors named as: Mood, Emotions, Heuristics, Frames, Gambling and Personality. SEM model has been used to find out the interdependence among Behavioral biases. The relationship between heuristics and personality is found to be the strongest one. Also, study shows that investor's emotion plays a lead role in determining their heuristic and framing.
24. **Chavali and Mohanraj [37]:** (2016): The study here tries to explore association between investment pattern and financial decision making of investors towards different risk tolerance level. Study reveals a significant relationship between investment pattern and risk tolerance towards gender of investor. However, age has no relation with risk tolerance as well as investment pattern as per study. Occupation of investor is found to be associated with risk tolerance but not with investment pattern.
25. **Kubilay and Bayrakdaroglu [133]:** (2016): The study here depicted that each personality faces different biases and each investor has different risk tolerances. It is important for investor to have knowledge of own personality and psychological biases. It has been determined that there is relationship between personality traits and psychological biases of investors. Also, the personality traits of an investor have an effect on their financial risk tolerances as well. Researcher has used five-factor personality model for classifying the personality traits and financial risk tolerance scale developed by Grable and Lytton in the year 1999.
26. **Mahmood et al. [154]:** (2016): The study here aims to identify the behavioral factors affecting investment decision of Pakistani investors. The study reveals three factors to have an association with investment performance. They are Heuristics,

Herding and Prospect. The study also reveals a significant relationship between these factors and investment performance. Heuristics and Herding factors are found to be positively correlated but Prospect factor is found to be negatively correlated with investment performance.

27. **Kannadhasan et al. [126]:** (2016): The study here has been focused on finding various psychological factors and its impact on FRT. The researcher had considered 3 independent factors as self-esteem, type of personality and sensation seeking. Self-esteem and sensation seeking are found to be positively correlated with FRT. This interprets people with higher self-esteem and sensation seeking is more risk tolerant. Type A personality is more risk tolerant than type B personality as they belong to higher income level.
28. **Parimalakanthi and Kumar [180]:** (2016): Researchers in the article found that the response of the salaried income group towards different savings schemes is poor. Their intention is only tax saving and hence the majority are having preference towards provident fund and life insurance policies. Authors suggest that steps should be taken to create awareness among the investors regarding other saving schemes and investment avenues. Also, financial institutions need to adopt a broad advertising strategy in order to enable the investors to identify and analyze various investment schemes.
29. **Anum and Ameer [7]:** (2017): The objective of study here is to discover the impact of Behavioral biases on investor's decision making and investment performance at Pakistan Stock Exchange. The factor analysis conducted here results four factors as heuristic, prospect, market and herding. The study concluded that factors have high impact on investor's decision making.
30. **Peón et al. [181]:** (2017): The study here deals with an inclusive taxonomy of various psychological biases of investors worldwide. The paper provides a systematic review literature of theoretical as well as experimental concepts regarding Behavioral finance. The study tries to identify the effect of various biases in creation of different market anomalies and later provide some policy implications as well.
31. **Chopde and Kulkarni [41]:** (2017). The research here is done to find the association between behavioral factors and investment decisions of individual investors of Mumbai. The researcher has used twenty biases which were earlier suggested by Michael Pompain in 2012 as variables and conducted factor analysis. The four factors found to have relationship with investment decision are named as: Erstwhile experience factor, Incongruity factor, Inducement factor and Dogmatic factor.

32. **Michael M. Pompain [184]:** (2017): Pompian had identified two different aspects of Cognitive Dissonance Bias as (1) Selective perception in which the investors only identify evidences which confirms their earlier philosophies and hence provide an incomplete sight of actual picture (2) Selective decision making where investors despite knowing that they are going wrong, probably strengthen the commitments that are previously made.
33. **Zandri and Sune [262]:** (2018): The study here attempts to create a linkage between risk tolerance, investor personality and Behavioral finance regarding South African investors. The study considered 5 heuristic factors and 3 prospect factors and identified that prospect factors corresponds to conservative and low risk tolerant investors. However, heuristics factors correspond to aggressive and high risk tolerant investors.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

4.1 THE STRUCTURE OF STUDY

The study presented here has various steps involved. The **Figure 4.1** shows the snapshot of study structure.

Figure 4.1: Structure of study.

Source: Compiled by Researcher.

Saunders et al. [207] in the year 2007 developed concept of research onion, in order to explain various stages that a researcher must go through during the process of formulating an effective methodology. This research onion is divided into various layers just like onion.

The first layer talks about the research philosophy being used by researcher. The second layer explains the appropriate research approach being adopted. In the third layer research type and in forth layer, the research strategy used in explained. The fifth layer identifies the time horizon of the research i.e. cross sectional or longitudinal. The sixth layer represents the data collection methodology considered by researcher. The research onion helps to create a series of processes performed at different stages and helps to illustrate the steps involved in the methodological study conducted. The research methodology adopted here for study is described in the **Figure 4.2**

Figure 4.2: Research methodology used for study.

Source: “Research Onion” concept, adopted from Saunders et al. (2007)

4.2 RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

4.2.1 Primary Objective:

It is to develop a financial model for various investment firms that will guide them in profiling their clients more accurately considering their Behavioral aspects towards various risk tolerance levels, and thus will help them to generate more customized portfolios for their clients.

4.2.2 Secondary Objectives:

1. To investigate various Behavioral biases that influence the decision making of investors in Uttar Pradesh.
2. To calculate different levels of FRT among investors of Uttar Pradesh using GL-RTS.
3. To analyze the effect of demographics on levels of FRT of investors.
4. To study and analyze the effect of demographics on behavioral biases of investors.
5. To determine the association between behavioral biases and levels of FRT among investors of Uttar Pradesh.

4.3 RESEARCH PHILOSOPHY

Bryman [31] explained research philosophy as set of beliefs and expectations concerned with the truth which is being investigated in the study. **Flick U. [67]** elucidated the underlying assumption concerned with particular research philosophy provide explanation for; in what way a research must be conducted. **Monette et al. [162]** defined two different frameworks under research philosophy as: positivism and constructionism. Positivism considers that the actual reality exists independently and argues that knowledge can be generated through scientific method. On the other hand, **Östlund and Kidd [179]** pronounced that constructivism supports the fact that a single methodology is not able to create knowledge.

4.3.1 Research Approaches:

4.3.1.1 Deductive Approach

Deductive approach is one which is based on development of hypotheses regarding a theory existing earlier and then formulates it, in order to test it. **Silverman D. [223]** Deductive approach is considered to be best suited to the positivist philosophy. **C.R. Kothari [132]** described deductive approach as development from general to particular.

4.3.1.2 Inductive Approach

The inductive approach is apprehensive with moving from specific observations to more generalized results. As per **Bryman and Bell [30]** in this approach, the data is collected with the help of interviews or questionnaires regarding a specific phenomenon and then the data is analyzed to examine the pattern of outcome.

4.3.2 Research Design:

Flick U. [67] described the research design as a framework which explains various underlying facts and answers to the questions like how the correct methodology is adopted, how the respondents must be chosen, how the data will be analyzed and so on.

4.3.2.1 Descriptive Research Design

Bryman A. [31] explored that a descriptive research design reflects the results of experiences of the respondents. It is strictly based on the literature reviewed and attempts to describe the concepts which have been established earlier.

4.3.2.2 Exploratory Research Design

W.L. Neuman [168] detailed the exploratory research design attempts to effectively elucidate different features of a particular inhabitants or the social phenomenon. **Saunders et al. [207]** defined exploratory study tries to explore any issue that took place in the social surroundings with an aim to open future scope for the subject.

4.3.3 Research Strategy:

As per **Flick U. [67]** there are 3 types of strategies to be used by the researcher. The first is quantitative research which is concerned with quantitative data analysis. It is based on statistical standards to be followed in order to generate a statistically significant result. **Goddard and Melville [79]**.

Banister et al. [10] in their book explained the qualitative research is based on researcher's own perception regarding particular social phenomena and comparing it with those of respondents. **M.Y. Feilzer [65]** explained qualitative research is generally concerned with examining a public phenomenon as a substitute of seeking a causal relationship among established variables. The mixed methods are a combination of both. It includes use of both qualitative and quantitative methodology in order to create a single dataset.

4.3.4 Time Horizons:

As per **Saunders et al. [207]** it is the time outline within which a study or research is intended to be completed. According to **Bryman A. [31]**, the 2 types of time horizons

are cross-sectional and longitudinal. The cross-sectional is one where the data is collected at a specific time for one time only. **Flick U. [67]**

Goddard and Melville [79] explained the longitudinal time horizon as a time period when the collection of data is done recurrently over and over again for an extended period in order to examine the change over time. As per **Saunders et al. [207]** longitudinal study generally helps to analyze the change and development that helps in quality control.

4.3.4.1 Time duration of the study:

The study conducted here is cross-sectional one in which whole data is collected once. The duration of this study is from 2015 to 2019.

4.3.5 Hypotheses Formulation:

The hypotheses and sub hypotheses formulated for the study are as below:

1(H₀):There is no significant association between demographics and financial risk tolerance.

1(H₁):There is a significant association between demographics and financial risk tolerance.

1.1(H₀):There is no significant association between gender and financial risk tolerance.

1.1(H₁):There is significant association between gender and financial risk tolerance.

1.2(H₀):There is no significant association between age and financial risk tolerance.

1.2(H₁):There is significant association between age and financial risk tolerance.

1.3(H₀):There is no significant association between marital status and financial risk tolerance.

1.3(H₁):There is significant association between marital status and financial risk tolerance.

1.4(H₀):There is no significant association between education and financial risk tolerance.

1.4(H₁):There is significant association between education and financial risk tolerance.

1.5(H₀):There is no significant association between employment and financial risk tolerance.

1.5(H₁):There is significant association between employment and financial risk tolerance.

1.6(H₀):There is no significant association between income and financial risk tolerance.

1.6(H₁):There is significant association between income and financial risk tolerance.

1.7(H₀):There is no significant association between investment preference and financial risk tolerance.

1.7(H₁):There is significant association between investment preference and financial risk tolerance.

2(H₀):There is no significant association between behavioral biases and demographics.

2(H₁):There is a significant association between behavioral biases and demographics.

2.1(H₀):There is no significant association between Representativeness bias and demographics.

2.1(H₁):There is a significant association between Representativeness bias and demographics.

2.2(H₀):There is no significant association between Overconfidence bias and demographics.

2.2(H₁):There is significant association between Overconfidence bias and demographics.

2.3(H₀):There is no significant association between Gamblers Fallacy bias and demographics.

2.3(H₁):There is significant association between Gamblers Fallacy bias and demographics.

2.4(H₀):There is no significant association between Availability bias and demographic variables.

2.4(H₁):There is significant association between Availability bias and demographic variables.

2.5(H₀):There is no significant association between Herd bias and demographics.

2.5(H₁):There is significant association between Herd bias and demographics.

2.6(H₀):There is no significant association between Loss Aversion bias and demographics.

2.6(H₁):There is significant association between Loss Aversion bias and demographics.

2.7(H₀):There is nosignificant association between Regret Aversion bias and demographic variables.

2.7(H₁):There is significant association between Regret Aversion bias and demographic variables.

2.8(H₀):There is no significant association between Mental Accounting bias and demographics.

2.8(H₁):There is significant association between Mental Accounting bias and demographics.

3(H₀):There is no relationship between Behavioral biases and financial risk tolerance.

3(H₁):There is a relationship between Behavioral biases and financial risk tolerance.

4(H₀):There is no significant impact of Behavioral biases on financial risk tolerance.

4(H₁):There is a significant impact of Behavioral biases on financial risk tolerance.

4.3.6 Data Collection:

4.3.6.1 Primary Data

According to **Bryman A. [31]** primary data is derived from first-hand sources, like from the respondents in the form of questionnaire survey or interviewed information. The primary data is the one composed and analyzed by researcher for the first time in such way.

4.3.6.2 Secondary Data

According to **I. Newman [169]** secondary data is one which is retrieved from the work, opinions and observations of other investigators. It includes the information and observations that has already been collected as well as analyzed by earlier researchers.

4.3.7 Sampling Design:

4.3.7.1 Sample:

Bryman A. [31] explained a sample is a demonstrative subdivision of larger population. The sample design constitutes the sample size, process of its selection, validity and reliability of the results. The important sample characteristics are explained below.

4.3.7.2 Sample Area:

The sample area selected for the study includes five important (demographically as well as population wise) cities belonging to the state of Uttar Pradesh. These cities are popularly known as KAVAL cities that represent Kanpur, Agra, Varanasi, Allahabad and Lucknow.

4.3.7.3 Sample Size:

I. Newman [169] elucidated that the sample size characterizes the number of respondents selected from the population that are used in the research. Sample size is more relevant in quantitative research as it plays crucial role in determining the reliability and validity of the results. The larger sample size is comparatively more reliable for the results.

The sample size considered here for the study is 500 individual investors. It has been considered on the basis of population data from the selected sample area; which is collected from the official site of the census of India survey for the year 2011.

Total population of KAVAL cities =10219840 (As per Census survey 2011)

Critical Value (z) = 1.96 at 95% (level of significance is 0.05)

Marginal error (E) = 5%

Response distribution(r) = 20% (as 5-point likert scale is used)

4.3.7.4 Sampling Techniques:

Bryman A. [31] explained the sampling technique as a procedure by which the data of sample is collected for the study. A random sample represents the sample where respondents are chosen at random, where non-random (or non-probabilistic) sample doesn't have identical chance of selection for each sample constituent.

The sampling technique used here in this study is stratified non-random sampling.

4.3.7.5 Sample Frame:

A convenient sample frame is important to decide in order to obtain an unbiased result. According to **P.J. Lavrakas [138]** the sample frame must include those respondents which met the certain criteria to be considered for the study like the geographical proximity, ease to accessibility and most importantly their willingness to participate and respond. In this study the sample frame has been developed on the basis of different strata where the respective number of investors from each KAVAL cities of Uttar Pradesh has been calculated on the basis of ratio of population as per census 2011 survey data, which is shown in **Table 4.1**.

Table 4.1: Sample frame.

S. No.	City Selected	Population (As per census 2011)	Population Ratio	Sample Size	Approx. Size
1	Kanpur	29,20,067	0.29	142.86	143
2	Lucknow	29,01,474	0.28	141.95	142
3	Agra	17,46,467	0.17	85.44	85
4	Varanasi	14,35,113	0.14	70.21	70
5	Allahabad	12,16,719	0.12	59.53	60
	TOTAL	1,02,19,840		500	500

Source: Compiled by researcher

4.3.7.6 Significance of selected sample frame:

Uttar Pradesh is India's most populous state as per last census survey (2011) of India. Uttar Pradesh is the fourth largest state of country in terms of land. The state is also considered as heart land as it comes under influence area of western as well as eastern freight corridors. The state has great heterogeneity in population as the citizens of nearby states migrate towards UP to a larger extent.

Despite of being highly populated the investment awareness level and financial literacy among investors is pretty low. As per the study conducted by **Vibhuti and Asthana [250]** the financial behaviour, financial attitude, and level of financial knowledge are lowest in UP as compared to other central zone states of the country. Hence, it is important to make an effort for studying this specific region in order to generate more awareness among investors.

The KAVAL cities (also in SMART cities) of Uttar Pradesh have found a special reference for study because of various socioeconomic factors present here. Being most populated cities with cultural and demographical differences, of the state they have been considered here for the study.

4.3.8 Instruments for collection of data:

Data collection using questionnaire is an important method used for primary data collection in the form of survey research, where the respondent gives his/her opinion. A questionnaire involves set of questions in structured form, which is filled by the respondents; among which it is distributed for research purpose. **Leedy&Ormrod [141]** explained in their research, about various characteristics and important points of consideration regarding a questionnaire that should be kept in mind during any research process. They are summed up as under:

4.3.8.1 Length of the questionnaire:

A.N. Oppenheim [178] explained that if the respondents are concerned with given research topic then they are ready to fill even long questionnaires as well. The length of the questionnaire should be of size keeping in mind the interest and domain of respondents. Also, it must include all necessary and sufficient information to be collected from respondent within shortest possible time.

4.3.8.2 Instructions:

According to **Leedy&Ormrod [141]** the instructions regarding questionnaire need to be stated clearly and precisely.

4.3.8.3 Language:

C.R. Kothari [132] in his book summarized that the questionnaire must be conversed in a language that is easily understood by the respondents concerned with the study. The researcher here has used English language for designing the questionnaire.

4.3.8.4 Formulation of questions:

A.N. Oppenheim [178] explained that the formulation and sequence of questions to be added in questionnaire plays an important role. He also explained certain principles that need to be followed during the process of construction and question framing in order to avoid any discrepancy.

The basic principles must be followed during question framing of the survey form are given as under:

1. The question statement must be specific, brief, short and clear.
2. The question framing should be done keeping in mind that the respondents must understand the vocabulary, style and order of sentence.
3. Questions with negative perspectives must be avoided. Researcher must avoid ambiguous questions and try to be more precise.
4. The abstract questions should be avoided
5. In order to avoid confusion, only one thought should be reflected per question.

4.3.8.5 Types of questions:

DeVos et al. [53] specified that the questionnaire should consist of two types of questions; one is open-ended and second is closed-ended question. Open-ended questions allow the respondents to give their thoughts in their own verses and they are free to express, whereas closed-ended questions have a pre-determined set of options available and the respondent need to choose from those options only.

In this study, the questionnaire consists all closed-ended questions where respondents need to select one of the specified options given by the researcher.

4.3.8.6 Questionnaire distribution:

Questionnaires were distributed to 500 investors from KAVAL cities of Uttar Pradesh.

4.3.8.7 Structure of questionnaire:

The questionnaire used in the study has been divided into 3 sections. The **Table 4.2** provides the description of refereed sources used to define variables (dependent and

independent) for the study. However, some of the options have been edited as per requirement of data analysis. The categorization of questionnaire distribution is as follows:

- ❖ Section A, belongs to the demographical variables namely gender, age, marital status, education, employment, monthly income and investment preference of individual investor.
- ❖ Section B, belongs to FRT related questions in accordance with the 13 item GL-RTS.
- ❖ Section C, comprises the closed ended questions related to Behavioral biases, which has been asked on a 5-point likert scale.

Table 4.2: List of refereed sources for variables used in study.

Variables	Scale used	Type of measurement	Category	Source
Demographics (Independent Variable)	Nominal	Multiple Choice Open Ended Question	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Gender – Age – Marital status – Education – Employment – Monthly income – Investment preference 	Stephen Kuzniak, John E. Grable et.al., “ <i>The Grable and Lytton risk-tolerance scale: A 15-year retrospective</i> ”, Financial Services Review 24 (2015) 177-192
Risk Tolerance (Categorical) (Dependent Variable)	Nominal	Four Point Scoring grid	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Conservative Investor – Below-average risk tolerant – Average/moderate risk tolerant – Above-average risk tolerant – Aggressive investor 	Grable, J. E., & Lytton, R. H. (1999). “ <i>Financial risk tolerance revisited: The development of a risk assessment instrument.</i> ” Stephen Kuzniak, John E. Grable et.al., “ <i>The Grable and Lytton risk-tolerance scale: A 15-year retrospective</i> ”, Financial Services

				Review 24 (2015) 177-192
Behavioral factors (Independent Variable)	Ordinal	Five Point Likert Scale	Heuristic Factors - Representativeness - Overconfidence - Anchoring - Gambler's fallacy - Availability bias	Satish Kumar, NishaGoyal, <i>Behavioral biases in investment decision making – a systematic literature review"</i> (2015).
			Prospect Factors - Loss aversion -Regret aversion - Mental accounting	Dr. HarshaVijaykumar, <i>To study the level of financial Literacy and its impact on investment Decision – an in-depth analysis of Investors in gujarat state</i> (2013)
			Herding Factors - Herd Behavior	Le phuocluong et al, <i>Behavioral factors influencing Individual investors' decision-making And performance</i> (2011) Dr. Bashir T et al., <i>Are Behavioral biases influenced by demographic characteristics & personality traits? Evidence from Pakistan</i> (2013)

Source: Compiled by researcher

4.3.9 Research Analysis Tools:

Various suitable statistical tools and techniques are used for research purpose are:

- ❖ Descriptive statistics for demographic variables.
- ❖ Correlation analysis for finding degree of relationship among variables.

- ❖ Regression analysis in order to develop a linear model among DV and IDVs
- ❖ Statistical tests for hypotheses testing (ANOVA, Chi square and cross tab)

4.3.9.1 Statistical Analysis:

The data collected has been analyzed using SPSS, Version 21 by IBM.

4.3.9.2 Result Analysis:

There have been various researches done earlier that has interpreted the similar results as it is found in the present study as well regarding various biases towards financial risk tolerance. The **Table 4.3** provides a snapshot for the same.

Table 4.3: List of refereed sources shown similar results as found in the present study.

Heuristic Variables		
Representativeness	Risk Tolerance is positively Associated	Anna Thorsell, YannMassol, Alexis Molines , “Determinants of risk tolerance and investment Behavior: A study of French and Swedish Business School students” ,18 May 2015
Overconfidence		Carrie H. Pan and Meir Statman, “Questionnaires of Risk Tolerance, Regret, Overconfidence, and other Investor Propensities” , The Journal of Investment Consulting, pp 54-62, Volume 13, No 1, 2012.
Gambler’s fallacy		Robert Faff, Daniel Mulino and Daniel Chai, “On the Linkage between Financial Risk Tolerance and Risk Aversion: Evidence from a Psychometrically-validated Survey versus an Online Lottery Choice Experiment” , Monash University, 2014
Availability bias		

Prospect Variables		
Loss aversion	Risk Tolerance is negatively associated	By MuskaanArora and SanthaKumari , “ Self -Esteem as Determinant of Investors Risk Tolerance: Mediating Role of Loss Aversion and Regret ”, IJSER, Volume 6, Issue 3, March-2015, ISSN: 2229-5518
Regret aversion		
Mental accounting		
Herding Variables		
Herd Behavior	Risk Tolerance is negatively Associated	Huei-Wen Lin, “ How Herding Bias could be derived from Individual Investor Types and Risk Tolerance? ” IJSBIE Vol-6, No-6, 2012
Demographic Variables		
Demographic Variables	Risk Tolerance has an Association	John E. Grable and Ruth H. Lytton, “ Investor Risk Tolerance: Testing the Efficacy of Demographics as Differentiating and Classifying Factors ”, FCP, Volume 9(1), 1998 Stephen Kuzniak, John E. Grable et.al., “ The Grable and Lytton risk-tolerance scale: A 15-year retrospective ”, FSR, Vol. 24 (2015) 177-192

Source: Compiled by Researcher

The **Table 4.3** presents only some of the researches shown similar results as generated in the study here however the dependent and independent variables in the above studies may differ but they explain similar association.

4.3.9.3 Research Model:

Creswell et al. [47] explained the research model as a way to describe the overall framework used to look in reality on the basis of research philosophy. The model developed is shown in **Figure 4.3**.

Figure 4.3: Research Model.

Source: Compiled and drawn by researcher

DATA ANALYSIS

5.1 OVERVIEW

Schurink et al. [211] explained data analysis as a systematic procedure which applies various statistical and logical techniques used to describe, illustrate and condense so as to evaluate the data collected. Data analysis brings order, structure, association and significance to the collected data.

According to **K. Maree [156]** in the year 2010, different procedures of analysis provide a way to conclude inductive inferences from the data collected. Data analysis provides a procedure to the researcher that can be applied to identify the arrangements in the data collected from the respondents. It also helps in purposeful collection of data from selected individuals in order to confirm or refute the information.

The study here is focused on exploring different factors having an impact on dependent variable i.e. FRT levels. The data has been gathered in the form of a structured questionnaire that has been distributed among 500 individual investors. After data editing 487 responses have been recorded for analysis purpose. The collected data has been analyzed using SPSS version 21. The data collected in this study has been categorized into 3 sections:

Section-A (Demographic variables):

The data has been collected from respondents regarding given 7 demographics.

- 1) Gender
- 2) Age
- 3) Employment Status
- 4) Marital Status
- 5) Education
- 6) Monthly Income
- 7) Investment preference

Section-B (Risk Tolerance):

Data has been collected on 13 items questionnaire given by John E. Grable and Lytton, where the investor is categorized into 5 categories, according to their response score.

- 1) High risk tolerant
- 2) Moderate to high risk tolerant
- 3) Moderate risk tolerant
- 4) Low to moderate risk tolerant
- 5) Low risk tolerant

Section-C (Behavioral Factors):

Data has been collected on a 5-point likert scale, in which 1 point represents strongly disagree and 5 points represent strongly agree.

- 1) Representative bias
- 2) Overconfidence bias
- 3) Gamblers fallacy
- 4) Availability bias
- 5) Herd bias
- 6) Loss aversion bias
- 7) Regret aversion bias
- 8) Mental Accounting bias

Data analysis and presentation can be done with the help of various statistical tools and techniques. It can be done in various ways, the most important include descriptive statistics and inferential statistics.

As per **DeVos et al. [53]** descriptive statistics is one where the numeric data is analyzed quantitatively using various statistical tools. However, inferential statistics is one where testing of hypotheses has been done statistically by the researcher as a part of data analysis.

5.2 DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS

The study here has considered various demographic variables for the purpose of analysis. The demographical information includes frequencies and percentages on **gender, age, education level, marital status, employment, level of income and investment preference.**

5.2.1 Gender Categories:

Table 5.1: Tabular presentation of gender of respondents.

		Gender			
		Frequency	Percentage	Valid Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
Valid	Male	300	61.6	61.6	61.6
	Female	187	38.4	38.4	100.0
	Total	487	100.0	100.0	

The **Table 5.1** shows the gender categories as male and female. The males comprise total of 61.6% with a count of 300 and females are 187 in number which is 38.4% of total data collected.

Figure 5.1: Graphical presentation of gender of respondents.

The **Figure 5.1** clearly represents that the number of males is comparatively higher (approximately 24%) than females in the data collected by the researcher.

5.2.2 Age Categories:

Table 5.2: Tabular presentation of age of respondents.

Age				
	Frequency	Percentage	Valid Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
Up to 25 years	59	12.1	12.1	12.1
26 to 45 years	221	45.4	45.4	57.5
Valid 46 to 65 years	32	6.6	6.6	64.1
65 years and above	175	35.9	35.9	100.0
Total	487	100.0	100.0	

The **Table 5.2** shows the highest percentage of 45.4% which belongs to the age category of 26 to 45 years. Next comes the category of 65 years and above that comprises 35.9% (175) of overall data collected. Third category counts 59 respondents i.e. 12.1% of whole data belonging to the category up to 25 years. The fourth category is of 32 (6.6%) respondents belonging to age of 46 to 65 years.

Figure 5.2: Graphical presentation of age of respondents.

The **Figure 5.2** clearly depicts the highest area of pie diagram belongs to 26 to 45 years and the lowest area of pie diagram belongs to the age group of 46 to 65 years. The figure infers that the people with age of 46 to 65 years participate in least number to the investment avenues. Also, the investors of age group 26 to 45 years participate most actively in investment avenues.

5.2.3 Education Categories:

Table 5.3: Tabular presentation of education of respondents.

Edu				
	Frequency	Percentage	Valid Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
Valid	Graduation/ Diploma	188	38.6	38.6
	Post-Graduation	164	33.7	72.3
	Doctoral & higher edu	39	8.0	80.3
	Professional Course	96	19.7	100.0
	Total	487	100.0	

The **Table 5.3** shows the highest percentage of 38.6% which belongs to the category of graduates or diploma holders. Next is the category of postgraduates that comprises 33.7% (164 in count) of overall data collected. Third category counts 96 respondents i.e. 19.7% of whole data belonging to the category of those involved in any professional course. The fourth category is of 39 (8%) respondents belonging to doctoral and higher degree holders.

Figure 5.3: Graphical presentation of education of respondents.

The **Figure 5.3** depicts the highest area of pie diagram belongs to the two categories of approximate similar size i.e. graduates/diploma holders and post graduates. The lowest area of pie diagram belongs to the category of doctoral and higher education.

5.2.4 Marital Status:

Table 5.4: Tabular presentation of marital status of respondents.

Marital_sta				
	Frequency	Percentage	Valid Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
Never Married	191	39.2	39.2	39.2
Married without children	67	13.8	13.8	53.0
Valid Married with children	207	42.5	42.5	95.5
Widow/Seperated	22	4.5	4.5	100.0
Total	487	100.0	100.0	

The **Table 5.4** represents the tabular presentation of data inferring the marital status of respondents. According to data the highest number of respondents are married and having children with a count of 207 comprising 42.5%. The second category is of unmarried respondents with 39.2% respondents having a count of 191. Next are the respondents who are married but not having children that represents 13.8% (67). Next category is of widow/seperated respondents having a number of 22 with share of 4.5%.

Figure 5.4: Graphical presentation of marital status of respondents.

The **Figure 5.4** clearly depicts the highest area of pie diagram belongs to those married with children and the lowest area of diagram belongs to those who are of widow/seperated category.

5.2.5 Employment Status:

Table 5.5: Tabular presentation of employment status of respondents.

Employ				
	Frequency	Percentage	Valid Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
Valid	Self Employed	225	46.2	46.2
	Full time salaried	180	37.0	83.2
	Casual/Part time	35	7.2	90.3
	Unemployed(Housewife/ Retired/ Student)	47	9.7	100.0
	Total	487	100.0	100.0

The **Table 5.5** shows tabular presentation of data inferring employment status of respondents. According to data the highest numbers of respondents are self employed with a count of 225 comprising 46.2 %. The second category is of full time respondents with 37% respondents having a count of 180. Next are the respondents who are having unemployment status that represents 9.7% (47 in count). Next category is of casual/part time students having a number of 35 with share of 7.2%.

Figure 5.5: Graphical presentation of employment status of respondents.

The **Figure 5.5** infers the highest and lowest area belonging to the categories of self-employed respondents and casual/part time respondents respectively.

5.2.6 Income Categories:

Table 5.6: Tabular presentation of income level of respondents.

		Income			
		Frequency	Percentage	Valid Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
Valid	Upto Rs. 30,000	118	24.2	24.2	24.2
	Rs. 30,001 to Rs. 60,000	99	20.3	20.3	44.6
	Rs. 60,001 to Rs. 80,000	21	4.3	4.3	48.9
	Rs. 80,001 and above	235	48.3	48.3	97.1
	Nil	14	2.9	2.9	100.0
	Total	487	100.0	100.0	

The **Table 5.6** shows the highest percentage of 48.3% which belongs to the category of respondents having monthly income of 80000 and above. Next comes the category of respondents having monthly income of up to 30000 that comprises 24.2% (118 in count) of overall data collected. Third category counts 99 respondents i.e. 20.3% of whole data belonging to the category of respondents having monthly income of 30001 to 60000. The fourth category is of 21 respondents (4.3%) belonging to the category of respondents having monthly income of 60001 to 80000. The fifth category is of respondents having nil income.

Figure 5.6: Graphical presentation of income level of respondents.

The **Figure 5.6** infers the highest and lowest area belonging to the categories of respondents having monthly income of 80001 & above and category of nil income respectively.

5.2.7 Investment Preference Categories:

Table 5.7: Tabular presentation of investment preference of respondents.

		Invest_aven			
		Frequency	Percentage	Valid Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
Valid	Safe avenues	65	13.3	13.3	13.3
	Moderate risk avenues	92	18.9	18.9	32.2
	High risk avenues	148	30.4	30.4	62.6
	Traditional avenues	99	20.3	20.3	83.0
	Emerging avenues	83	17.0	17.0	100.0
	Total	487	100.0	100.0	

The **Table 5.7** shows the highest percentage of 30.4% which belongs to the category of respondents whose preferred avenues is highly risky. Next comes the category of respondents having traditional investments preference that comprises 20.3% (99 in count) of overall data collected. Third category counts 92 respondents i.e. 18.9% of whole data belonging to the category of respondents having preference into moderate risky assets. The fourth category is of 83 respondents (17 %) belonging to the category of emerging avenues. The last and least number of 65 respondents i.e. 13.3% belongs to the category of safe avenues investment preference.

Figure 5.7: Graphical presentation of investment preference of respondents.

The **Figure 5.7** infers the highest and lowest area belonging to the categories of respondents preferred high risk investment avenues (30.39%) and safer investment avenues (13.35%) respectively.

5.3 DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS

Creswell et al. [47] explored descriptive statistics has been used in order to represent organized and unbiased information which has been collected from their representative sample in the form of a structured questionnaire.

5.3.1 Reliability of data:

Cooper et al. [45] explained the reliability as a measurement of degree of consistency between different variables. It directly relates with the accuracy of the measurement procedure. Reliability is concerned with degree of freedom and unstable error. Different reliable instruments can be used with confidence at different times under different situations in order to validate the data collected.

According to Leedy and Ormrod [141], reliability analysis helps to validate the data collected. It is important for the researcher to certify that the questions asked by him were user-friendly and respondents gave the answers as effortlessly as possible. De Voset al. [52] summarized that reliability helps the researcher to get an assurance that the instrument measures used were accurate.

Validity plays a crucial role in all types of primary researchers done by conducting a survey, as it measures the reliability of dependent and independent items. Most prominently used reliability measure is cronbach's alpha. Hair along with associates in year 2009 suggested the universally agreed lower limit for cronbach's Alpha is 0.6; however, it may go down to 0.50 in exploratory research.

The Table 5.8 shows the value of cronbach's alpha as 0.829 for whole final data and cronbach's alpha of 0.721 for pilot data collected which is more than the expected value of alpha of 0.6 for social researches that confirms the scales used are reliable enough to be used for further study.

Table 5.8: Reliability Statistics for data collected.

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.721	63

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.829	60

5.3.2 Data Reduction:

5.3.2.1 Factor Analysis:

The most interdependent technique to reduce large data is factor analysis. According to Luck and Rubin, factor analysis tries to detect the dimensions which can't be easily observed in a large set of data. This method finds the information from the data set in terms of relatively, which is known as "factor". The specific reasons for using factor analysis are:

1. To streamline a large set of data by dropping interrelated variables (which can cause in multicollinearity) and still hold most of the facts existing in the collected data.
2. To identify the structure of data on the basis of its inherent characteristics in the sample.

In the study here the data has been collected in the form of a well-structured questionnaire consisting 50 questions regarding Behavioral biases and 13 questions from Grable-Lytton scale of financial risk tolerance, along with some demographic variables. In order to reduce data, factor analysis technique has been used for those 50 items based on Behavioral biases which were measured on a 5-point likert scale.

5.3.2.2 Bartlett's test of Sphericity:

N. K. Malhotra [155] explored this test as a statistical tool considered to interpret the correlations among the variables. It is used to check the null hypothesis stating that variables have no correlation within the population.

As shown in **Table 5.9**, the value for Bartlett's test of sphericity value is significant at 5% level of significance. This indicates that the variables are not highly correlated and correlation matrix has significant correlation among other variables.

Table 5.9: KMO and Bartlett's Test.

KMO and Bartlett's Test	
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.	.922
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square
	df
	Sig.
	20361.828
	1225
	.000

5.3.2.3 Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Test for Sampling Adequacy:

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) Measure is an index used to examine the appropriateness of factors analysis, by checking the adequacy of sample. The KMO value varies from 0 to 1. According to **N. K. Malhotra [155]** higher KMO value (from 0.5 to 1) indicates the factor analysis to be appropriate. However smaller values of KMO statistic indicate that correlation among the variables cannot be described by remaining variables, meaning that factor analysis is not appropriate.

As shown in in **Table 5.9**, the KMO value for variables is found to be 0.922, which is closer to 1. Hence, this value is adequate and validates the suitability of factor analysis.

5.3.2.4 Variance explained:

The most important criteria in factor analysis is to recognize how many factors should be extracted from data collected for the study. It is needful that the scale developed or the components extracted must be able to describe maximum variance in the data. For this purpose, Eigen values are considered. **N. K. Malhotra [155]** explained Eigen values as the sum of the variances of the factor values. Eigen value explains the total variance clarified by every factor. Factors with a variance greater than 1 are considered significant, and the remaining factors are left as insignificant. The total variance contributed by different factors is evaluated by specified cumulative percentage of variance extracted by following factors. The objective is to ensure the significance of all derived factors with the specified amount of variance.

As per **N. K. Malhotra [155]** in social sciences generally a result that counts 60 percent or more of the total variance is considered as satisfactory. The **Table 5.10** shows the Eigen values of all factors extracted. It also shows the overall cumulative variance. The extraction of components ensures that maximum amount of variance is elucidated by minimum number of components. The factor whose Eigen value is greater than 1 has been extracted here.

Table 5.10: Extraction of factors.

Component	Total Variance Explained								
	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	26.563	53.126	53.126	26.563	53.126	53.126	22.356	44.713	44.713
2	6.599	13.198	66.324	6.599	13.198	66.324	10.079	20.158	64.871
3	2.655	5.310	71.634	2.655	5.310	71.634	2.901	5.803	70.674
4	1.859	3.718	75.352	1.859	3.718	75.352	1.883	3.767	74.441
5	1.334	2.668	78.020	1.334	2.668	78.020	1.475	2.951	77.392
6	1.193	2.386	80.406	1.193	2.386	80.406	1.231	2.463	79.854
7	1.113	2.227	82.633	1.113	2.227	82.633	1.214	2.429	82.283
8	1.028	2.056	84.689	1.028	2.056	84.689	1.203	2.405	84.689
9	.892	1.785	86.474						
10	.764	1.528	88.001						
11	.709	1.418	89.419						
12	.675	1.350	90.769						
13	.532	1.064	91.833						
14	.444	.889	92.721						
15	.429	.857	93.579						
16	.408	.815	94.394						
17	.347	.694	95.088						
18	.330	.660	95.748						
19	.269	.539	96.287						
20	.240	.481	96.768						
21	.204	.408	97.176						
22	.190	.381	97.557						
23	.150	.299	97.856						
24	.121	.242	98.098						
25	.118	.236	98.334						
26	.100	.201	98.535						
27	.085	.171	98.706						
28	.081	.162	98.868						
29	.076	.152	99.020						
30	.070	.139	99.159						
31	.053	.107	99.266						
32	.049	.098	99.363						
33	.040	.080	99.444						
34	.036	.073	99.516						
35	.030	.060	99.577						
36	.028	.057	99.633						
37	.026	.053	99.686						
38	.025	.049	99.735						
39	.022	.044	99.779						
40	.020	.039	99.818						
41	.017	.034	99.852						

42	.014	.029	99.881						
43	.014	.028	99.909						
44	.011	.022	99.931						
45	.009	.018	99.949						
46	.008	.017	99.965						
47	.007	.014	99.979						
48	.005	.010	99.989						
49	.004	.008	99.998						
50	.001	.002	100.000						
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.									

Here the factors extracted from 50 biases under study are 8 in number and together they contribute to 84.689% of total variance, which is a good percentage of variance explained. Hence, factor analysis results in reduction of Behavioral biases from 50 to 47 in number and extracting eight factors. These factors are named as representativeness, overconfidence, gamblers fallacy, availability bias, herding, loss aversion, regret aversion and mental accounting on the basis of questions been asked in questionnaire as per reviewed literature. Three items have been removed after extraction as the component loadings for them is less than 0.5. Principal component analysis has been used for extraction of variables.

5.3.2.5 Extraction of Factors:

The matrix including all components provides loadings of different variables. However, the initial or unrotated matrix provides the association between the factors still the factors may be found correlated with many other variables. Hence the rotation of factors is done where the rotated matrix is much simple and easy to interpret. **N. K. Malhotra [155]** explained the rotation of the factors improves the ambiguities that can arise in the initial unrotated factor matrix. The commonly used rotation method is VARIMAX, which is focused on factors having maximum variance. The **Table 5.11** shows the extracted factors after rotation with their corresponding factor loadings as well.

Table 5.11: Tabular presentation of factors extracted.

Factor	Items	Factor Loadings
Factor 1 Representativeness	You try to generate a pattern in your previous earnings and losses in order to use this trend for future decisions.	0.615
	You can do correct predictions about future returns on the basis of detailed past analysis.	0.614

	You believe that it was easy for you to predict the situations like global financial and economic crisis in advance.	-0.617
	In your opinion the correct forecast always depend on earlier investment studies.	-0.610
	You take investment decisions on the basis of your previously formed opinions regarding market trends.	-0.696
	Your predictions always proven you correct in case of financial investments.	0.632
Factor 2 Overconfidence	You trust your capabilities to start and manage new investment portfolios.	0.702
	Your previous successful investments have boosted your level of confidence.	0.829
	You feel that your earlier investment decisions often proven you correct.	0.898
	You believe that your investment options has always outperformed in past.	0.898
	You rely on your analytical skills to evaluate all your investment decisions yourself.	0.855
	You feel that your specific investment decision skills provide you an extra edge to earn more profits.	0.913
Factor 3 Gamblers Fallacy	Sometimes you invest just for the fun and excitement of proving your correct.	0.917
	At times you are willing to take substantially higher risks in greed of getting above-average returns.	0.914
	Your gut feeling and intuition help you to take correct decisions in confusing situations.	0.902
	You do not hesitate to use even illegal methods to earn more.	0.901
	You sometimes take advantage of loopholes in policies to maximize your profits.	0.904
	You never hesitate to try your luck in order to increase your earnings.	0.727
Factor 4 Availability Bias	You avoid investment options which are complicated and difficult to understand because of less information available.	0.729
	Sometimes you take shortcuts to earn higher returns quickly.	0.824
	You are more likely to invest in the instruments which are well known to you.	0.852
	You believe that your close friends and relatives are most reliable source for investment information.	0.812
	You try to opt for recently popular/in-news investment opportunities.	0.862
	You believe that most familiar investment instruments are safer one.	0.769

Factor 5 Herd Behavior	You get influenced by media reports while making an investment decision.	0.739
	You rely on expert's recommendations while making investments.	0.940
	The opinion of friends and family members is important for you to take investment decision.	0.815
	You try to copy the investment patter of successful investors as it is less risky.	0.895
	You collect all first-hand information before taking independent decisions.	0.919
	You feel yourself sensitive towards rumours regarding your investment instruments.	0.930
Factor 6 Loss Aversion	You would rather hold investments with negative returns instead of taking a loss.	0.894
	You hesitate to trying those instrument avenues which has given you poor returns in past.	-0.788
	You are more likely to invest more in those instruments which has given you higher returns earlier.	-0.772
	You are more likely to avoid risk than usual; after getting prior losses.	-0.900
	You generally adjust your investment instruments at the time of tax calculation in order to get tax benefits.	-0.891
	You found yourself more sensitive towards losses than gains.	-0.868
Factor 7 Regret Aversion	You sometimes regret your past investment decisions.	-0.861
	At times the losses on your investment decisions give you displeasure.	-0.641
	The profits on your investment decisions not always make you happiness.	0.744
	You sometimes invest more deliberately in avenues which were past gainers.	-0.819
	You try to avoid those investment avenues which were past losers.	0.957
	You are open to take help from investment consultancies after incurring losses.	0.799
Factor 8 Mental Accounting	You are more likely to differentiate between capital appreciation and regular income.	0.649
	You feel those investment options safer that provides good return in long run.	0.791
	You consider your entire investment options separately but not as whole portfolio.	0.762
	When you receive high profit margin, you tend to hold onto investment to receive even higher profits.	0.758
	If you get an amount as a gift, you try to invest it in comparatively high risky options.	0.829

5.3.3 Descriptive statistics of the extracted factors:

The **Table 5.12** shows the descriptive statistics of different factors extracted from the collected data set with the help of factor analysis.

Table 5.12: Descriptive statistics of the extracted factors.

	No.of Ques	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Deviation	Cronbach's Alpha	Cumulative %age Variance explained
Representativeness	6	1.83	4.17	1.83	3.12	0.909	44.713
overconfidence	6	1.33	4.33	1.33	3.08	0.857	64.871
Gamblers Fallacy	6	1.00	4.17	1.00	2.91	0.971	70.674
Availability Bias	6	1.00	4.67	1.00	3.00	0.945	74.441
Loss_aversion Bias	6	1.00	4.17	1.00	2.93	0.722	77.392
Regret Bias	6	1.33	4.33	1.33	2.91	0.719	79.854
Herd Bias	6	1.33	3.83	1.33	2.46	0.731	82.283
Mental Accounting	5	1.80	4.40	1.80	3.14	0.582	84.689

5.3.4 Level of Financial Risk Tolerance:

For evaluation of the levels of FRT among investors of Uttar Pradesh, the 13 items GL-RTS has been used. This scale includes 13 situational questions that have been asked from the investor, which contributes to different scores. Later the respective scores are summed up and on the basis of total score, each investor has been categorized. **Stephen et.al. [233]** has also done categorization of investors on basis of scoring. GL-RTS segments individual into 5 risk tolerant categories given as follows:

1. The score of 18 or below represents Low risk tolerance (i.e. conservative investor).
2. The score of 19 to 22 shows Below-average risk tolerance.
3. The score of 23 to 28 represents Average or moderate risk tolerance.
4. The score of 29 to 32 infers Above-average risk tolerance.
5. The score of 33 and above represents High risk tolerance (i.e. aggressive investor).

The **Table 5.13** shows the descriptive statistics (frequency count and percentage) of the collected data from respondents on the criteria of their total score regarding FRT questionnaire.

Table 5.13: Tabular presentation of risk tolerance level among investors.

		risk tolerance code			
		Frequency	Percentage	Valid Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
Valid	Conservative	54	11.1	11.1	11.1
	below moderate risk tolerant	82	16.8	16.8	27.9
	moderate risk tolerance	102	20.9	20.9	48.9
	above moderate risk tolerant	32	6.6	6.6	55.4
	Aggressive	217	44.6	44.6	100.0
	Total	487	100.0	100.0	

The **Figure 5.8** shows that highest percentage of 44.6% investors; belong to the category of high risk tolerant. Next is the category of respondents who are moderate risk tolerant that comprises 20.9% (102 in count) of overall data collected. Third category counts 82 respondents i.e. approximately 16.8% of overall data belonging to the category of respondents who are at below average level in risk tolerance. The fourth category is of 54 respondents (11.1 %) belonging to the category of respondents who are at low risk tolerance level. The last and least number of 32 respondents i.e. approximately 6.6% belongs to the category of above average level of risk tolerance.

Figure 5.8: Graphical presentation of risk tolerance level among investors.

5.4 INFERENCE STATISTICS

5.4.1 Hypotheses Testing: Cross Tabulation and Chi-Square tests

5.4.1.1 Association between demographic variables and financial risk tolerance

In order to test the significant association between demographic variables (such as investor's age, gender, education, income, employment structure and investment preference) and FRT levels, Chi-Square test has been performed. Chi-square test helps to understand the association between two or more attributes. According to **C.R. Kothari [132]**, Chi-square test determines whether the categorical data shows dependency or not.

5.4.1.1.1 Association between gender and financial risk tolerance:

Cross Tabulation: The **Table 5.14** shows the data regarding cross tabulation of gender and financial risk tolerance.

Table 5.14: Cross Tabulation.

Gender * risk tolerance code Crosstabulation

		Count					Total
		risk tolerance code					
		Conservative	below moderate tolerant	moderate tolerant	above moderate tolerant	Aggressive	
Gender	Male	6	20	41	27	206	300
	Female	48	62	61	5	11	187
Total		54	82	102	32	217	487

Chi-square test: The null and alternative hypothesis for examining the association between gender and financial risk tolerance is as under:

H_0 . There is no significant association between gender and financial risk tolerance.

H_1 : There is significant association between gender and financial risk tolerance.

Table 5.15: Chi-Square Tests.

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	234.882	4	.000
Likelihood Ratio	267.654	4	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	227.473	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	487		

As the result shown in the output **Table 5.15**, the test has been performed at 5% level of significance. The Pearson Chi-square significance value is 0.000 with degree of freedom 4. Therefore, the **null hypothesis is not accepted** which infers that there is a **significant association** found between **gender of investor and their financial risk tolerance**.

The associability between the dependent and independent variables can be identified by comparing means of both variables. As given in the **Table 5.16**, the comparison of means between gender and financial risk tolerance clearly depicts that **males are more risk tolerant than females**, as they are assumed to have high exposure towards various environmental situations and Indian males are brought up with a legacy of mind set to take correct decision in every situation and hence are not considered as wrong/poor decision maker.

Table 5.16: Mean Comparison.

risk tolerance code			
Gender	Mean	N	Std. Deviation
Male	4.36	300	1.071
Female	2.30	187	1.066
Total	3.57	487	1.464

5.4.1.1.2 Association between age and financial risk tolerance:

Cross Tabulation: The Table 5.17 shows the data regarding cross tabulation of age and financial risk tolerance.

Table 5.17: Cross Tabulation.

Crosstab

Count

	risk tolerance code					Total
	Conservative	below moderate tolerant	moderate tolerant	above moderate tolerant	Aggressive	
Up to 25 years	1	3	55	0	0	59
Age 26 to 45 years	2	3	0	32	184	221
46 to 65 years	0	0	13	0	19	32
65 years and above	51	76	34	0	14	175
Total	54	82	102	32	217	487

Chi-square test: The null and alternative hypothesis for examining the association between age and financial risk tolerance is as under:

H_0 . There is no significant association between age and financial risk tolerance.

H_1 : There is significant association between age and financial risk tolerance.

Table 5.18: Chi-Square Tests.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	588.228	12	.000
Likelihood Ratio	626.308	12	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	156.658	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	487		

As the result shown in the output **Table 5.18**, the test has been performed at 5% level of significance. The Pearson Chi-square significance value is 0.000 with degree of freedom 12. Therefore, the **null hypothesis is not accepted** which infers that there is a **significant association** found between **age of investor and their financial risk tolerance**.

The associability between the dependent and independent variables can be identified by comparing means of both variables. As given in the **Table 5.19**, the comparison of means between age and financial risk tolerance clearly depicts that **high level of risk tolerance is found among those investors who are of age 26-45 years. Low risk tolerant is those who lie in the age range of 65 years and above.**

26-45-year individuals are generally aggressive earners; they have comparatively lesser responsibilities and hence are risk-takers. The next category of 46-65 years has lesser risk tolerance as this age group is full of responsibilities, they need money for kids, family and other contingencies. Up to 25 years are less risk tolerance as they are starters and having lesser information regarding investments and income management so don't take much risk. 65 years and above are those who have earned lifelong and are now in a saver mode and therefore they don't go for challenging and exploring new opportunities.

Table 5.19: Mean Comparison.

risk tolerance code

Age	Mean	N	Std. Deviation
Up to 25 years	2.92	59	.337
26 to 45 years	4.78	221	.604
46 to 65 years	4.19	32	.998
65 years and above	2.14	175	1.092
Total	3.57	487	1.464

5.4.1.1.3 Association between marital status and financial risk tolerance:

Cross Tabulation: The Table 5.20 shows the data regarding cross tabulation of marital status and financial risk tolerance.

Table 5.20: Cross Tabulation.

Crosstab

Count

	risk tolerance code					Total
	Conservative	below moderate tolerant	moderate tolerant	above moderate tolerant	Aggressive	
Never Married	1	2	2	32	154	191
Married without children	2	4	24	0	37	67
Married with children	49	73	69	0	16	207
Widow/Seperated	2	3	7	0	10	22
Total	54	82	102	32	217	487

Chi-square test: The null and alternative hypothesis for examining the association between marital status and financial risk tolerance is as under:

H_0 . There is no significant association between marital status and financial risk tolerance.

H_1 : There is a significant association between marital status and financial risk tolerance.

Table 5.21: Chi-Square Tests.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	357.378	12	.000
Likelihood Ratio	435.976	12	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	227.439	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	487		

As per **Table 5.21**, the test has been performed at 5% level of significance. The Pearson Chi-square significance value is 0.000 with degree of freedom 12. Therefore, the **null hypothesis is not accepted** which infers that there is a **significant association** found between **marital status of investor and their financial risk tolerance**.

The associability between the dependent and independent variables can be identified by comparing means of both variables. As given in **Table 5.22**, the comparison of means between age and financial risk tolerance clearly depicts that **high level of risk tolerance is found among those investors who are never married. Low risk tolerant is those who are married and having children**.

Married individuals are inclined to take lesser risk than those who are never married reason being they have a burden of family members. Among married also, the one having no children are more risk tolerant and can take higher risk than those having children. The third category of widow/separated infers that these individuals generally wear the responsibility of family and kids single handedly and hence they are very selective and take financial risk judiciously.

Table 5.22: Mean Comparison.

risk tolerance code * Marital_sta

risk tolerance code

Marital_sta	Mean	N	Std. Deviation
Never Married	4.76	191	.575
Married without children	3.99	67	1.200
Married with children	2.33	207	1.079
Widow/Seperated	3.59	22	1.436
Total	3.57	487	1.464

5.4.1.1.4 Association between education and financial risk tolerance:

Cross Tabulation: The **Table 5.23** shows the data regarding cross tabulation of education and financial risk tolerance.

Table 5.23: Cross Tabulation.

Crosstab

Count		risk tolerance code					Total
		Conservative	below moderate tolerant	moderate tolerant	above moderate tolerant	Aggressive	
Edu	Graduation/ Diploma	53	56	62	0	17	188
	Post Graduation	0	0	37	31	96	164
	Doctoral & higher edu	1	26	2	1	9	39
	Professional Course	0	0	1	0	95	96
Total		54	82	102	32	217	487

Chi-square test: The null and alternative hypothesis for examining the association between education and financial risk tolerance is as under:

H_0 . There is no significant association between education and financial risk tolerance.

H_1 : There is significant association between education and financial risk tolerance.

Table 5.24: Chi-Square Tests.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	422.787	12	.000
Likelihood Ratio	483.143	12	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	173.109	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	487		

As the result shown in the output **Table 5.24**, the test has been performed at 5% level of significance. The Pearson Chi-square significance value is 0.000 with degree of freedom 12. Therefore, the **null hypothesis is not accepted** which infers that there is a **significant association** found between **education of investor and their financial risk tolerance**.

The associability between the dependent and independent variables can be identified by comparing means of both variables. As given in the **Table 5.25**, the comparison of means between age and financial risk tolerance clearly depicts that **high level of risk tolerance is found among those investors who had done any professional course. Low risk tolerant is those who are either graduate or diploma holder.**

Individual having professional course are high risk tolerant as they have been given all relevant information regarding sound decision making and they are confident enough to prove them correct. This capacity of taking risk keeps on decreasing as the level of education decreases. This can be explained by the fact that education boosts the confidence level of individuals.

However, the result shows one exception i.e. individual having higher education (Doctoral and above) show a low mean value of risk tolerance which may be because of the fact that there is less sample size of this category or this category individual are highly responsible and hence don't have freedom to take high risk.

Table 5.25: Mean Comparison.

risk tolerance code * Edu

risk tolerance code

Edu	Mean	N	Std. Deviation
Graduation/ Diploma	2.32	188	1.154
Post Graduation	4.36	164	.828
Doctoral & higher edu	2.77	39	1.307
Professional Course	4.98	96	.204
Total	3.57	487	1.464

5.4.1.1.5 Association between employment and financial risk tolerance:

Cross Tabulation: The

Table 5.26 below shows the data regarding cross-tabulation of employment and financial risk tolerance.

Table 5.26: Cross Tabulation.

Employ * risk tolerance code Crosstabulation

Count		risk tolerance code					Total
		Conservative	below moderate risk tolerant	moderate risk tolerance	above moderate risk tolerant	Aggressive	
Employ	Self Employed	0	2	14	26	183	225
	Full time salaried	47	65	56	0	12	180
	Casual/Part time	1	2	28	0	4	35
	Unemployed(Housewife/Retired/Student)	6	13	4	6	18	47
	Total	54	82	102	32	217	487

Chi-square test: The null and alternative hypothesis for examining the association between employment and financial risk tolerance is as under:

H₀. There is no significant association between employment and financial risk tolerance.

H₁: There is significant association between employment and financial risk tolerance.

Table 5.27: Chi-Square Tests.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	398.006	12	.000
Likelihood Ratio	449.304	12	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	96.307	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	487		

As the result shown in the output **Table 5.27**, the test has been performed at 5% level of significance. The Pearson Chi-square significance value is 0.000 with degree of freedom 12. Therefore, the **null hypothesis is not accepted** which infers that there is a **significant association** found between **employment of investor and their financial risk tolerance**. The associability between the dependent and independent variables can be identified by comparing means of both variables. As given in the **Table 5.28**, the comparison of means between age and financial risk tolerance clearly depicts that **high level of risk tolerance is found among those investors who are self employed. Low risk tolerant is those who are into a casual employment status or part time workers having no regular income.**

While talking about the level of risk tolerance in association with employment status, self-employed comes first as they are the one who are aggressive risk takers. They are business owners and don't depend on others for their timely financial needs. Next category is of unemployed (as per data result) which can be unexceptional and can be inferred to show high risk tolerance because of the reason that this category include student who are young and energetic risk takers, also retired individuals who, at this age, have fulfilled their responsibilities and can take risk at this life span. The third category is full time salaried and the fourth category of casual/part time individuals which shows a positive association between financial status and risk tolerance level.

Table 5.28: Mean Comparison.

risk tolerance code			
Employ	Mean	N	Std. Deviation
Self Employed	4.73	225	.612
Full time salaried	2.25	180	1.056
Casual/Part time	3.11	35	.796
Unemployed(Housewife /Retired/ Student)	3.36	47	1.538
Total	3.57	487	1.464

5.4.1.1.6 Association between income and financial risk tolerance:

Cross Tabulation: The Table 5.29 shows the data regarding cross tabulation of income and financial risk tolerance.

Table 5.29: Cross Tabulation.

Crosstab

Count

	risk tolerance code					Total
	Conservative	below moderate tolerant	moderate tolerant	above moderate tolerant	Aggressive	
Upto Rs. 30,000	44	70	0	0	4	118
Rs. 30,001 to Rs. 60,000	0	0	92	0	7	99
Income Rs. 60,001 to Rs. 80,000	4	4	0	0	13	21
Rs. 80,001 and above	0	0	10	32	193	235
Nil	6	8	0	0	0	14
Total	54	82	102	32	217	487

Chi-square test: The null and alternative hypothesis for examining the association between income and financial risk tolerance is as under:

H₀: There is no significant association between income and financial risk tolerance.

H₁: There is significant association between income and financial risk tolerance.

Table 5.30: Chi-Square Tests.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	821.067	16	.000
Likelihood Ratio	811.235	16	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	272.251	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	487		

As the result shown in the output **Table 5.30**, the test has been performed at 5% level of significance. The Pearson Chi-square significance value is 0.000 with degree of freedom 16. Therefore, the **null hypothesis is not accepted** which infers that there is a **significant association** found between **income of investor and their financial risk tolerance**.

The associability between the dependent and independent variables can be identified by comparing means of both variables. As given in the **Table 5.31**, the comparison of means between age and financial risk tolerance clearly depicts that **high level of risk tolerance is found among those investors who are having monthly income of ₹80,001 and above. Low risk tolerant investors are those who are having nil income or not earning at all.**

Level of income shows a positive association between income and financial risk tolerance. As the level of income increases, the level of risk tolerance also increases. Low income group corresponds to low risk tolerance.

Table 5.31: Mean Comparison.

risk tolerance code * Income

risk tolerance code

Income	Mean	N	Std. Deviation
Upto Rs. 30,000	1.73	118	.781
Rs. 30,001 to Rs. 60,000	3.14	99	.515
Rs. 60,001 to Rs. 80,000	3.67	21	1.770
Rs. 80,001 and above	4.78	235	.508
Nil	1.57	14	.514
Total	3.57	487	1.464

5.4.1.1.7 Association between investment preference and financial risk tolerance:

Cross Tabulation: The Table 5.32 shows the data regarding cross tabulation of investment preference and financial risk tolerance.

Table 5.32: Cross Tabulation.

Crosstab

Count

	risk tolerance code					Total
	Conservative	below moderate tolerant	moderate tolerant	above moderate tolerant	Aggressive	
Safe avenues	37	10	8	7	3	65
Moderate risk avenues	2	9	71	6	4	92
Invest_aven High risk avenues	3	3	9	8	125	148
Traditional avenues	6	53	8	4	28	99
Emerging avenues	6	7	6	7	57	83
Total	54	82	102	32	217	487

Chi-square test: The null and alternative hypothesis for examining the association between investment preference and financial risk tolerance is as under:

H_0 . There is no significant association between investment preference and financial risk tolerance.

H_1 : There is significant association between investment preference and financial risk tolerance.

Table 5.33: Chi-Square Tests.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	550.615	16	.000
Likelihood Ratio	461.840	16	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	59.655	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	487		

As the result shown in the output **Table 5.33**, the test has been performed at 5% level of significance. The Pearson Chi-square significance value is 0.000 with degree of freedom 16. Therefore, the **null hypothesis is not accepted** which infers that there is a **significant association** found between **investment preference of investor and their financial risk tolerance**.

The associability between the dependent and independent variables can be identified by comparing means of both variables. As given in **Table 5.34**, the comparison of means between age and financial risk tolerance clearly depicts that **high level of risk tolerance is found among those investors who go for high-risk avenues. Low risk tolerant is those who go for investment in safer avenues**.

Safer avenues include bank deposits, PPF, national saving certificates, post office and government securities which are assumed to be of low risk. Moderate avenues include mutual fund life insurance, bonds and debentures. High risk avenues are equity and commodity share market as well as highly risky FOREX investments. Traditional avenues include real state, gold/silver, chit funds etc. They are comparatively of lower risk. Emerging avenues include virtual real state, hedge fund, private equity, art and passion. They are of high risk.

Table 5.34: Mean Comparison.

risk tolerance code * Invest_aven

risk tolerance code

Invest_aven	Mean	N	Std. Deviation
Safe avenues	1.91	65	1.247
Moderate risk avenues	3.01	92	.655
High risk avenues	4.68	148	.841
Traditional avenues	2.95	99	1.402
Emerging avenues	4.23	83	1.310
Total	3.57	487	1.464

5.4.2 Hypotheses Testing: ANOVA tests

5.4.2.1 Association between Demographics and Behavioural biases:

Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) test is a procedure that helps to interpret if experimental results are significant. **C.R. Kothari [132]** explained one-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) as a statistical test used to check whether the means of two or more groups are statistically significant or not. ANOVA checks the impact of one or more factors by comparing their means.

5.4.2.1.1 Association between Demographics and Representativeness bias:

The null-hypothesis has been formulated in order to determine the association between demographic variables and representativeness bias. The associability has been determined by applying a one-way ANOVA at a confidence level of 95%. The null and alternative hypothesis is as under:

H_0 : There is no significant association between Representativeness bias and demographics.

H_1 : There is a significant association between Representativeness bias and demographics.

Table 5.35: ANOVA

		ANOVA				
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Gender	Between Groups	40.152	11	3.650	23.105	.000
	Within Groups	75.043	475	.158		
	Total	115.195	486			
Age	Between Groups	301.647	11	27.422	47.345	.000
	Within Groups	275.125	475	.579		
	Total	576.772	486			
Marital_sta	Between Groups	178.564	11	16.233	25.699	.000
	Within Groups	300.044	475	.632		
	Total	478.608	486			
Edu	Between Groups	173.147	11	15.741	17.225	.000
	Within Groups	434.056	475	.914		
	Total	607.203	486			
Employ	Between Groups	209.455	11	19.041	23.889	.000
	Within Groups	378.615	475	.797		
	Total	588.070	486			
Income	Between Groups	504.816	11	45.892	62.904	.000
	Within Groups	346.539	475	.730		
	Total	851.355	486			
Invest_aven	Between Groups	69.416	11	6.311	4.223	.000
	Within Groups	709.787	475	1.494		
	Total	779.203	486			

From the output **Table 5.35**, it is prominent that there is a statistically significant association found between Representativeness bias and demographics ($p < 0.05$). This results that null hypothesis is not accepted and the alternative hypothesis concluded.

5.4.2.1.2 Association between Demographics and Overconfidence bias:

The null-hypothesis has been formulated to define the association between demographic variables and Overconfidence bias. The associability has been determined by applying a one-way ANOVA at a confidence limit of 95%. The null and alternative hypothesis is as under:

H_0 : There is no significant association between Overconfidence bias and demographics.

H_1 : There is significant association between Overconfidence bias and demographics.

Table 5.36: ANOVA

		ANOVA				
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Gender	Between Groups	49.142	19	2.586	18.286	.000
	Within Groups	66.053	467	.141		
	Total	115.195	486			
Age	Between Groups	248.238	19	13.065	18.572	.000
	Within Groups	328.534	467	.703		
	Total	576.772	486			
Marital_sta	Between Groups	214.338	19	11.281	19.935	.000
	Within Groups	264.270	467	.566		
	Total	478.608	486			
Edu	Between Groups	191.770	19	10.093	11.346	.000
	Within Groups	415.433	467	.890		
	Total	607.203	486			
Employ	Between Groups	245.867	19	12.940	17.660	.000
	Within Groups	342.203	467	.733		
	Total	588.070	486			
Income	Between Groups	463.857	19	24.414	29.422	.000
	Within Groups	387.498	467	.830		
	Total	851.355	486			
Invest_aven	Between Groups	118.906	19	6.258	4.426	.000
	Within Groups	660.297	467	1.414		
	Total	779.203	486			

From the output **Table 5.36**, it is seen that there is a statistically significant association found between Overconfidence bias and demographics ($p < 0.05$). This infers that null hypothesis is not accepted and the alternative hypothesis concluded.

5.4.2.1.3 Association between Demographics and Gamblers Fallacy bias:

The null-hypothesis has been formulated in order to access the association between demographic variables and Gamblers Fallacy bias. The associability has been determined by applying a one-way ANOVA at a confidence interval of 95%. The null and alternative hypothesis is as under:

H_0 : There is no significant association between Gamblers Fallacy bias and demographics.

H_1 : There is significant association between Gamblers Fallacy bias and demographics.

Table 5.37: ANOVA

		ANOVA				
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Gender	Between Groups	55.477	14	3.963	31.320	.000
	Within Groups	59.718	472	.127		
	Total	115.195	486			
Age	Between Groups	307.192	14	21.942	38.418	.000
	Within Groups	269.580	472	.571		
	Total	576.772	486			
Marital_sta	Between Groups	239.157	14	17.083	33.673	.000
	Within Groups	239.451	472	.507		
	Total	478.608	486			
Edu	Between Groups	215.190	14	15.371	18.507	.000
	Within Groups	392.013	472	.831		
	Total	607.203	486			
Employ	Between Groups	267.140	14	19.081	28.063	.000
	Within Groups	320.930	472	.680		
	Total	588.070	486			
Income	Between Groups	526.370	14	37.598	54.606	.000
	Within Groups	324.985	472	.689		
	Total	851.355	486			
Invest_aven	Between Groups	157.003	14	11.215	8.507	.000
	Within Groups	622.200	472	1.318		
	Total	779.203	486			

From the output **Table 5.37**, it is prominent that there is a statistical significant association found between Gamblers Fallacy bias and demographics ($p < 0.05$). This results that the null hypothesis is not accepted and the alternative hypothesis concluded.

5.4.2.1.4 Association between Demographics and Availability bias:

The null-hypothesis has been formulated to determine the association between demographic variables and Availability bias. The associability has been determined by applying a one-way ANOVA at a confidence limit of 95%. The null and alternative hypothesis is as under:

H_0 : There is no significant association between Availability bias and demographics.

H_1 : There is significant association between Availability bias and demographics.

Table 5.38: ANOVA

		ANOVA				
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Gender	Between Groups	50.318	19	2.648	19.063	.000
	Within Groups	64.878	467	.139		
	Total	115.195	486			
Age	Between Groups	330.962	19	17.419	33.094	.000
	Within Groups	245.810	467	.526		
	Total	576.772	486			
Marital_sta	Between Groups	216.087	19	11.373	20.232	.000
	Within Groups	262.521	467	.562		
	Total	478.608	486			
Edu	Between Groups	220.596	19	11.610	14.025	.000
	Within Groups	386.607	467	.828		
	Total	607.203	486			
Employ	Between Groups	236.910	19	12.469	16.582	.000
	Within Groups	351.159	467	.752		
	Total	588.070	486			
Income	Between Groups	600.875	19	31.625	58.962	.000
	Within Groups	250.481	467	.536		
	Total	851.355	486			
Invest_aven	Between Groups	94.927	19	4.996	3.410	.000
	Within Groups	684.276	467	1.465		
	Total	779.203	486			

From the output **Table 5.38**, it is prominent that there is a statistical significant association found between Availability bias and demographics ($p < 0.05$). This results that the null hypothesis is not accepted and the alternative hypothesis concluded.

5.4.2.1.5 Association between Demographics and Herd bias:

The null-hypothesis has been formulated to determine the association between demographic variables and Herd bias. The associability has been determined by applying a one-way ANOVA at a confidence limit of 95%. The null and alternative hypothesis is as under:

H_0 : There is no significant association between Herd bias and demographics.

H_1 : There is significant association between Herd bias and demographics.

Table 5.39: ANOVA

		ANOVA				
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Gender	Between Groups	60.432	15	4.029	34.651	.000
	Within Groups	54.763	471	.116		
	Total	115.195	486			
Age	Between Groups	262.402	15	17.493	26.209	.000
	Within Groups	314.370	471	.667		
	Total	576.772	486			
Marital_sta	Between Groups	305.004	15	20.334	55.167	.000
	Within Groups	173.604	471	.369		
	Total	478.608	486			
Edu	Between Groups	258.429	15	17.229	23.266	.000
	Within Groups	348.775	471	.740		
	Total	607.203	486			
Employ	Between Groups	301.796	15	20.120	33.102	.000
	Within Groups	286.274	471	.608		
	Total	588.070	486			
Income	Between Groups	565.252	15	37.683	62.037	.000
	Within Groups	286.103	471	.607		
	Total	851.355	486			
Invest_aven	Between Groups	142.200	15	9.480	7.009	.000
	Within Groups	637.004	471	1.352		
	Total	779.203	486			

From the output **Table 5.39**, it is noticeable that there is a statistically significant association found between Herd bias and demographics ($p < 0.05$). As a result, the null hypothesis is not accepted and the alternative hypothesis concluded.

5.4.2.1.6 Association between Demographics and Loss Aversion bias:

The null-hypothesis has been formulated in order to determine the association between demographic variables and Loss Aversion bias. The associability has been determined by applying a one-way ANOVA at a confidence level of 95%. The null and alternative hypothesis is as under:

H_0 : There is no significant association between Loss Aversion bias and demographics.

H_1 : There is significant association between Loss Aversion bias and demographics.

Table 5.40: ANOVA

		ANOVA				
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Gender	Between Groups	50.718	18	2.818	20.452	.000
	Within Groups	64.477	468	.138		
	Total	115.195	486			
Age	Between Groups	251.583	18	13.977	20.115	.000
	Within Groups	325.189	468	.695		
	Total	576.772	486			
Marital_sta	Between Groups	227.193	18	12.622	23.495	.000
	Within Groups	251.415	468	.537		
	Total	478.608	486			
Edu	Between Groups	228.086	18	12.671	15.642	.000
	Within Groups	379.117	468	.810		
	Total	607.203	486			
Employ	Between Groups	255.250	18	14.181	19.940	.000
	Within Groups	332.820	468	.711		
	Total	588.070	486			
Income	Between Groups	454.783	18	25.266	29.816	.000
	Within Groups	396.572	468	.847		
	Total	851.355	486			
Invest_aven	Between Groups	114.380	18	6.354	4.473	.000
	Within Groups	664.823	468	1.421		
	Total	779.203	486			

From the output **Table 5.40**, it is noticeable that there is a statistical significant association found between Loss Aversion bias and demographics ($p < 0.05$). As a result, the null hypothesis is not accepted and the alternative hypothesis concluded.

5.4.2.1.7 Association between Demographics and Regret aversion bias:

The null-hypothesis has been formulated to check the association between demographic variables and Regret aversion bias. The associability has been determined by applying a one-way ANOVA at a confidence interval of 95%. The null and alternative hypothesis is as under:

H_0 : There is no significant association between Regret aversion bias and demographics.

H_1 : There is significant association between Regret aversion bias and demographics.

Table 5.41: ANOVA

		ANOVA				
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Gender	Between Groups	44.687	18	2.483	16.478	.000
	Within Groups	70.508	468	.151		
	Total	115.195	486			
Age	Between Groups	250.354	18	13.909	19.941	.000
	Within Groups	326.418	468	.697		
	Total	576.772	486			
Marital_sta	Between Groups	178.319	18	9.907	15.439	.000
	Within Groups	300.289	468	.642		
	Total	478.608	486			
Edu	Between Groups	222.810	18	12.378	15.071	.000
	Within Groups	384.393	468	.821		
	Total	607.203	486			
Employ	Between Groups	244.253	18	13.570	18.471	.000
	Within Groups	343.817	468	.735		
	Total	588.070	486			
Income	Between Groups	354.056	18	19.670	18.511	.000
	Within Groups	497.299	468	1.063		
	Total	851.355	486			
Invest_aven	Between Groups	142.729	18	7.929	5.830	.000
	Within Groups	636.474	468	1.360		
	Total	779.203	486			

From the output **Table 5.41**, it is noticeable that there is a statistical significant association found between Regret Aversion bias and demographics ($p < 0.05$). As a result, the null hypothesis is not accepted and the alternative hypothesis concluded.

5.4.2.1.8 Association between Demographics and Mental-Accounting bias:

The null-hypothesis has been formulated to check the association between demographic variables and Mental Accounting bias. The associability has been determined by applying a one-way ANOVA at a confidence interval of 95%. The null and alternative hypothesis is as under:

H_0 : There is no significant association between Mental Accounting bias and demographics.

H_1 : There is significant association between Mental Accounting bias and demographics.

Table 5.42: ANOVA

		ANOVA				
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Gender	Between Groups	29.304	13	2.254	12.414	.000
	Within Groups	85.891	473	.182		
	Total	115.195	486			
Age	Between Groups	73.572	13	5.659	5.320	.000
	Within Groups	503.200	473	1.064		
	Total	576.772	486			
Marital_sta	Between Groups	148.357	13	11.412	16.345	.000
	Within Groups	330.251	473	.698		
	Total	478.608	486			
Edu	Between Groups	137.242	13	10.557	10.625	.000
	Within Groups	469.961	473	.994		
	Total	607.203	486			
Employ	Between Groups	196.684	13	15.130	18.285	.000
	Within Groups	391.385	473	.827		
	Total	588.070	486			
Income	Between Groups	293.915	13	22.609	19.184	.000
	Within Groups	557.441	473	1.179		
	Total	851.355	486			
Invest_aven	Between Groups	111.679	13	8.591	6.087	.000
	Within Groups	667.524	473	1.411		
	Total	779.203	486			

From the output **Table 5.42**, it is clear that there is a statistical significant association found between Mental Accounting bias and demographics ($p < 0.05$). As a result, the null hypothesis is not accepted and the alternative hypothesis concluded.

5.4.3 Correlation Analysis:

The degree and direction of an association between two variables can be measured with the help of correlation analysis. It helps to understand how change in one variable influences the other variable. This can be done by calculating correlation coefficient. Pearson's correlation coefficient has been used widely in order to measure this degree of relationship between FRT and different behavioral biases.

C.R. Kothari [132] states that correlation coefficient helps to understand the strength of a relationship between variables. It depends on its value. If value of this relationship lies between 0.10 and 0.29 there is low strength relationship. If the value ranges between

0.30 and 0.49 it is referred as medium strength relationship and if the value is between 0.50 and 1.0 the variables have strong relationship.

This section concerns regarding the hypothesis between levels of FRT and behavioral biases. The null hypothesis is tested and conclusions are drawn in terms of relationships. The following hypothesis is set to test the relationship:

H₀: There is no relationship between Behavioral biases and financial risk tolerance.

H₁: There is a relationship between Behavioral biases and financial risk tolerance.

Correlation coefficient value signifies that a significant relationship is found between behavioral biases and financial risk tolerance ($p = 0.000$) which is less than 0.05 resulting that null hypothesis is not accepted. Hence it is inferred that alternative one is accepted at the 5% level of significance. The degree of relationship, however, is found to be positive as well as negative. The value of correlation coefficient “r” infers a strong strength relationship found between behavioral biases and financial risk tolerance.

The **Table 5.43** briefly describes the value of Pearson correlation coefficient (r). The relationship between financial risk tolerance and heuristics biases (representativeness, overconfidence, availability bias and gamblers fallacy) is found to be positive and strong one. While the relationship is found to be strong and negative in case of prospect biases (loss aversion, regret aversion, mental accounting) and herding bias in association with financial risk tolerance.

Table 5.43: Tabular presentation of correlation coefficients.

Dependent variable	Independent variable	Correlation coefficient
Financial Risk Tolerance	Representativeness	.799 (Positive)
	Overconfidence	.886 (Positive)
	Gamblers_fallacy	.897 (Positive)
	Availability bias	.795 (Positive)
	Herd	-.879 (Negative)
	Loss_aversion	-.733 (Negative)
	Regret aversion	-.769 (Negative)
	Mental_accounting	-.731 (Negative)

The value of the correlation coefficient above has been used to develop the curve between different Behavioral biases and financial risk tolerance.

Table 5.44: Correlation coefficient between representativeness bias and financial risk tolerance.

		risk tolerance code	Repr
risk tolerance code	Pearson Correlation	1	.799**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	487	487
Repr	Pearson Correlation	.799**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	487	487

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Figure 5.9: Correlation curve between representativeness and financial risk tolerance.

The **Figure 5.9** above infers that representative bias is found to present in the investors having pretty high risk tolerance, that is why they are confident about previous trends and believe they can generate profits again as generated in the past.

Table 5.45: Correlation coefficient between overconfidence and financial risk tolerance.

		Correlations	
		risk tolerance code	Over
risk tolerance code	Pearson Correlation	1	.886**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	487	487
Over	Pearson Correlation	.886**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	487	487

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Figure 5.10: Correlation curve between overconfidence and financial risk tolerance.

The **Figure 5.10** infers that overconfidence bias is also found in the investors having high risk tolerance, as they are very confident about their decisions and analytical capabilities and think them as best.

Table 5.46: Correlation coefficient between gambler’s fallacy and financial risk tolerance.

Correlations			
		risk tolerance code	Gamb
risk tolerance code	Pearson Correlation	1	.897**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	487	487
Gamb	Pearson Correlation	.897**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	487	487

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Figure 5.11: Correlation curve between gambler’s fallacy and financial risk tolerance.

The **Figure 5.11** infers that gamblers fallacy bias is found in the investors with high risk tolerance, as they believe on their intuition and gut feelings to take decisions.

Table 5.47: Correlation coefficient between availability bias and financial risk tolerance.

		Correlations	
		risk tolerance code	Avail
risk tolerance code	Pearson Correlation	1	.795**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	487	487
Avail	Pearson Correlation	.795**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	487	487

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Figure 5.12: Correlation curve between availability bias and financial risk tolerance.

The **Figure 5.12** infers that availability bias is found in the investors with high risk tolerance, as they believe that the information which is most readily available is most reliable.

Table 5.48: Correlation coefficient between loss aversion and financial risk tolerance.

Correlations			
		risk tolerance code	Loss
risk tolerance code	Pearson Correlation	1	-.733**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	487	487
Loss	Pearson Correlation	-.733**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	487	487

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Figure 5.13: Correlation curve between loss aversion and financial risk tolerance.

The **Figure 5.13** infers that loss aversion bias is prominently found in investors having low risk tolerance, as they avoid incurring losses.

Table 5.49: Correlation coefficient between regret aversion and financial risk tolerance.

Correlations			
		risk tolerance code	Regr
risk tolerance code	Pearson Correlation	1	-.769**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	487	487
Regr	Pearson Correlation	-.769**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	487	487

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Figure 5.14: Correlation curve between regret aversion and financial risk tolerance.

The **Figure 5.14** infers that regret aversion bias is mostly found in investors having low risk tolerance, as they regret to take higher risk in their decisions.

Table 5.50: Correlation coefficient between mental accounting and financial risk tolerance.

		Correlations	
		risk tolerance code	Mentl
risk tolerance code	Pearson Correlation	1	-.731**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	487	487
Mentl	Pearson Correlation	-.731**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	487	487

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Figure 5.15: Correlation curve between mental accounting and financial risk tolerance.

The **Figure 5.15** infers that mental accounting bias is also found in the investors having low risk tolerance, as they are also risk averse in nature and they go for investing their hard-earned money into safer investment avenues.

Table 5.51: Correlation coefficient between herding and financial risk tolerance.

		Correlations	
		risk tolerance code	Herd
risk tolerance code	Pearson Correlation	1	-.879**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	487	487
Herd	Pearson Correlation	-.879**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	487	487

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Figure 5.16: Correlation curve between herding and financial risk tolerance

The **Figure 5.16** infers that herding bias is found in the investors having low risk tolerance, as they don't have confidence on themselves. Hence, they generally follow the opinion of others, whom they think as best in investment decisions.

5.4.4 Regression Analysis:

5.4.4.1 Association between behavioral biases and financial risk tolerance:

Regression analysis is a statistical technique used to estimate the relationship among the variables through statistical modeling. Regression analysis helps to understand the changes in dependent variable if any one of independent variable changes. **C.R. Kothari [132]** explained regression analysis helps to develop the linear model by considering all the independent variables under study, which later helps to determine the impact of multiple independent variables simultaneously to predict the dependent variable.

In the study here regression analysis helps to develop a multiple linear model between different behavioral biases and financial risk tolerance. In order to check this association between various behavioral biases and FRT, the hypothesis has been developed, which is as under:

H₀: There is no significant impact of Behavioral biases on financial risk tolerance.

H₁: There is a significant impact of Behavioral biases on financial risk tolerance.

Table 5.52: ANOVA^a

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	952.471	8	119.059	638.651	.000 ^b
	Residual	89.110	478	.186		
	Total	1041.581	486			

a. Dependent Variable: risk tolerance code

b. Predictors: (Constant), Mentl, Repr, Avail, Repr, Herd, Loss, Over, Gamb

It is evident from the output **Table 5.52** that the value of F-statistic is significant at 5% level of significance ($p < 0.05$). This infers that the null hypothesis is not accepted and the alternative one is concluded, which means that there is a significant impact of Behavioral biases and financial risk tolerance.

To measure of strength of association coefficient of determination has been calculated which is denoted by R square. The **Table 5.53** explains the value of R square, which is 0.914. This interprets that approximately 91.4% of the total variance has been explained by the biases considered in this study. However, there is a scope for further addition of variables to explain the remaining 8.6% variance, which still remain as unexplained.

Table 5.53: Model Summary.

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.956 ^a	.914	.913	.432

a. Predictors: (Constant), Mentl, Repr, Avail, Repr, Herd, Loss, Over, Gamb

It is important to assess whether each of the independent variables included in the model make a significant contribution to the model. This can be done by evaluating the model fit and its significance as well. The **Table 5.54** provides the model fit for the linear model.

Table 5.54: Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	4.252	.320		13.301	.000
Repr	.206	.062	.095	3.335	.001
Over	.068	.071	.039	.959	.038
Gamb	.363	.058	.271	6.205	.000
1 Avail	.209	.049	.119	4.306	.000
Loss	-.115	.071	-.048	-1.628	.014
Regr	-.389	.057	-.180	-6.795	.000
Herd	-.614	.055	-.306	-11.114	.000
Mentl	-.078	.052	-.032	-1.515	.013

a. Dependent Variable: risk tolerance code

The **Eq. 5.1** elucidates the value of unstandardized coefficients (B) that help to generate the linear model between various Behavioral biases (independent variables) and financial risk tolerance (dependent variable). It is also evident from the output table above that the value of t-statistic is significant at 5% significance level as the value of p is less than 0.05 (95% confidence limit). The linear regression equation **Eq. 5.1** is as under.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Financial risk tolerance} = & (4.252) + (0.206)\text{representativeness} + \\ & (0.068)\text{overconfidence} + (0.363)\text{gamblers_fallacy} + \\ & (0.209)\text{availability} - (0.115)\text{loss_aversion} - (0.389)\text{regret_aversion} - \\ & (0.614)\text{herd} - (0.078)\text{mental_accounting} \end{aligned} \quad \text{Eq. 5.1}$$

FINDINGS AND CONCLUSION

6.1 FINDINGS (OBJECTIVES WISE)

The accomplishment of the research objectives contributed to the successful findings of this study. The findings as per research objectives are as follows:

6.1.1 Primary Objective:

The primary objective of the study was to develop a financial model considering the Behavioral aspects towards various risk tolerance levels. The **Figure 6.1** presents the model reflecting the association and impact of 8 behavioral biases (considered in this study) towards financial risk tolerance of individual investors.

Figure 6.1: Impact of behavioral biases on financial risk tolerance.

Source: Model developed by researcher

The regression analysis helps to generate the linear model between various Behavioral biases (independent variables) and financial risk tolerance (dependent variable). The linear regression equation has been formed which has already shown as Eq. 5.1 in chapter 5.

6.1.2 Secondary Objective 1: Investigation of Behavioral factors

To investigate the presence of various Behavioral factors among investors of Uttar Pradesh, a structured questionnaire (including 50 likert scale questions regarding different Behavioral biases) has been distributed among the investors of selected sample area. The responses of different respondents infer the presence of Behavioral biases among investors of Uttar Pradesh; which were later factorized into 8 different biases, identified as representative bias, overconfidence bias, gamblers fallacy bias, availability bias, loss aversion bias, regret aversion bias, mental accounting bias and herding bias.

6.1.3 Secondary Objective 2: Calculation of financial risk tolerance.

Next objective was to calculate the level of FRT among investors of Uttar Pradesh and for the same the risk tolerance scale given by Grable and Lytton has been used. The results infer that the investors belong to 5 different FRT levels, identified as conservative investor, below average risk tolerant, average (moderate) risk tolerant, above average risk tolerant and aggressive investor.

6.1.4 Secondary Objective 3: Effect of demographics on financial risk tolerance.

The effect of demographic factors on FRT was the third objective to be achieved. A null hypothesis was assumed in order to determine the statistical difference between demographics (age, gender, education, marital status, monthly income, employment, investment preference) and financial risk tolerance. It was evident from the results that:

- 1) Male respondents are found to show high risk tolerance than females.
- 2) Investors of age 26-45 years are high risk tolerant while those lie in the age range of 65 years and above are low risk tolerant.
- 3) High level of risk tolerance is found among those investors who are never married. Low risk tolerant is those who are married and having children.
- 4) Investors who had done any professional course show high level of risk tolerance. Low risk tolerant is those who are either graduate or diploma holder.
- 5) High level of risk tolerance is found in investors who are self-employed salaried. Low risk tolerant investors are those who are into a casual employment status or part time earners having no regular income.

- 6) Investors who are having monthly income between ₹80,001 and above are in high risk tolerance range. Low risk tolerant investors are those who are having nil income or not earning at all.
- 7) High risk tolerance is found among those investors who invest in high risk avenues while low risk tolerant investors go for investment in safer avenues.

6.1.5 Secondary Objective 4: Effect of demographics on behavioral factors.

The fourth objective was to find the effect of demographics on behavioral factors and for the same a null hypothesis was assumed in order to conclude the statistical difference between variables. The analysis of variance results in $p < 0.05$ at 5% level of significance (95% confidence level), which infers that demographic variables and different Behavioral biases are significantly associated.

6.1.6 Secondary Objective 5: Association between behavioral factors and financial risk tolerance.

The fifth objective was to find the strength of association between behavioral factors and financial risk tolerance and for the same correlation coefficient has been used as a statistical tool. The values ranging between 0.10 and 0.3 represent a weak strength relationship, from 0.30 to 0.5 a medium strength relationship and from 0.5 to 1 show a strong relationship between variables. The results infer that there is a positive and strong relationship found between financial risk tolerance and heuristics biases (representativeness, overconfidence, gamblers fallacy and availability bias). While the relationship is found to be strong and negative in case of prospect biases (loss aversion, mental accounting, regret aversion bias) as well as herding bias towards financial risk tolerance. The correlation coefficient has been used to find the behavioral biases and their corresponding level of financial risk tolerance as under:

- 1) Representativeness bias relates to moderate to high risk tolerance;
- 2) Overconfidence bias corresponds to moderate to high risk tolerance;
- 3) Gambler's fallacy corresponds to moderate to high risk tolerance;
- 4) Availability bias corresponds to moderate to high risk tolerance;
- 5) Loss aversion corresponds from low to moderate risk tolerance;
- 6) Regret aversion corresponds from low to moderate risk tolerance;
- 7) Mental accounting links from low to moderate risk tolerance; and
- 8) Herding bias corresponds to low to moderate risk tolerance.

The results presented above are found to be similar to various previous studies done by authors; who are referenced in **Table 6.1**.

Table 6.1: Details of supporting authors shown similar results.

Behavioral Biases	Risk Tolerance	Investor Type	Supporting Author
Loss Aversion	Low	Conservative	Pompian (2016)
Regret aversion	Low	Conservative	Bourse Securities (2016)
Mental Accounting	Low	Conservative	Jagongo and Mutswenje (2014)
Herding Bias	Medium	Conservative to moderate	Pompian (2017)
Representativeness	Medium	Moderate to aggressive	Pompian (2016)
Gamblers Fallacy	Medium	Moderate to aggressive	Lucarelli and Brighetti (2011)
Availability bias	High	Aggressive	Abreu (2014)
Overconfidence	High	Aggressive	Lake (2017)

Source: Compiled by Researcher.

6.2 CONCLUSION

The literature regarding behavioral economics has shown a mushroom growth in the recent years. It helped the researchers to get an insight regarding various market anomalies and the association of psychology with finance. Behavioral finance tries to explain the logic behind those unexplained market fluctuations which the standard financial theories fail. However, the application of heuristics and mental shortcuts taken by investors in their investment decisions still need to be extensively studied. Studies show that various investment firms in today's era think investors to be rational in decision making. Hence, they consider the investor's risk profiling only and no assessment of irrational behaviour has been included in risk profiling. Therefore, the study here will provide this extra component of risk tolerance along with behavioral psychology to get a more precise risk profile for potential investors. This will guide Indian investment companies specifically in Uttar Pradesh to become more conscious regarding behavioral biases that can possibly influence their client's investment decisions.

As per the primary objective of this research, the model developed here provides an association between different behavioral biases and FRT along with the effect of various demographic variables. This will surely provide a provision for evaluating the irrational investor's behavior which is associated risk tolerance in Uttar Pradesh region. The secondary objectives provide a way out to evaluate the financial risk tolerance and how different behavioral biases can be measured; also, the contextual framework for the same has been created. These secondary objectives in turn contributed towards the accomplishment of the primary objective. The research here concludes that the investors of Uttar Pradesh are not completely rational and are found to be influenced by various behavioral biases.

The research here interprets that individual investors do not necessarily act rationally during their investment decisions. They got influenced by different psychological, cognitive and emotional prejudices. These biases hugely affect an investor's decision-making. Heuristics such as representativeness, overconfidence, availability, gamblers fallacy as well as prospect factors like loss aversion, risk aversion, mental accounting and emotions like greed and fear; all influence investor's insight regarding risk decision making. It is apparent from the research that the financial decisions of investor depend on the level of risk these investors are willing to tolerate. This study will contribute towards those forthcoming frameworks that can be utilized by investment companies in reshaping the risk profiles of present and potential customers. The research explores that the levels of financial risk tolerance are subjected to demographics as well as behavioral factors of an individual.

This research will provide a lifeline to various financial practitioners as well as those seeking a growth in the field of financial advisory. It will definitely assist the financial advisors to understand their client's psychology and in turn aid them to develop a more

customized and behaviorally modified portfolio suits best for them. It will guide investment bankers and investors as well to understand the market sentiments before going for investment in public issues and other avenues. It will assist them to make contingency financial strategists as well, in order to handle adverse situations (if any).

As a concluding remark the **Figure 6.2** provide a snapshot of how different behavioral biases influence the FRT levels among investors of Uttar Pradesh.

Figure 6.2: Relationship between behavioral factors and financial risk tolerance.

Source: Developed by Researcher

The important findings of the research are summarized as under:

1. The investors of Uttar Pradesh are not rational in their financial decision making. They get influenced by various emotions (like greed and fear), biases (such as heuristics, prospect factors and herd) and their socio-economic status also contributes towards their decision making.

2. The financial risk tolerance of the investors varies from low (conservative) to high (aggressive), which is prominently seen to affect their investment pattern as well.
3. Individual investors, who are return lovers; are most susceptible towards Behavioral anomalies and mental errors. They even put their life savings at stake so as to earn money.
4. To follow advices of investment advisors and financial professionals may not always assist an investor to create above-average returns, as it will leave them to become a part of herd only.

SUGGESTIONS, LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE SCOPE

7.1 SUGGESTIONS

1. Every individual has different personal objectives at different time span of life. Hence it is suggested to look at the pocket first before taking risky decisions.
2. It is being suggested to every individual investor that before taking financial decision go through the previous records of the same investment (in the form of technical and fundamental analysis) but do not rely on the same fully as there may be change in situations and circumstances.
3. There is a necessity to start the financial education at earlier stage in the life in order to ensure the habit of savings and money management right from their childhood. It is suggested that financial education must be included as specific subject in the syllabus at primary and secondary education level by the policy makers.
4. At workplace it is suggested that employer should encourage the financial education programs to clear all dilemmas regarding investments.
5. The study reveals the influence of different behavioral factors towards financial risk tolerance as well as investment decisions. The investor therefore is suggested to not blindly follow others while thinking what is good for others must also be good for them.
6. Before following the advices of others, it is suggested for investor to literate them financially in order to critically evaluate various options available.
7. It is recommended that females must be provided the financial education to empower them and make them realize their importance in investment decision making at household level.
8. Financial literacy must be given in an unbiased manner. The companies should also emphasis on increasing awareness regarding financial literacy to the masses as their corporate social responsibility.

7.2 LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE SCOPE

This section of the study talks about the limitations and constraints faced by researcher in terms of time, location, financial assistance and availability of respondents. It also explains the scope for further studies regarding similar concepts. They are as under:

1. The sample taken for the study has been limited to Uttar Pradesh only. Considering the vast population and various cultural and demographic differences among the people of India, this is a smaller sample. Therefore, future studies focusing on larger samples and probably across the country may reveal a better and varied results.
2. The study here has been carried out among individual investors only. Hence, there is a scope for further research aiming at investment behavior of other types of investors like institutions, mutual fund managers, consultants, etc.
3. This study is carried out considering some selected biases identified by the researcher. However, there may exist other factors which may have significant impact on investor's decision-making. It may increase the robustness of the findings.
4. The study has evaluated various behavioral biases by using survey-based techniques that creates an opportunity for future researchers to use secondary data. Therefore, efforts can be made to discover the possible market indicators to predict the presence and impact of these biases considering the secondary data.
5. As the research is related to behavior and psychology domain which shows various fluctuations. Hence a longitudinal research can be carried out to study the behavioral changes over changing environment.
6. The study can provide scope for those international researches as well which are targeting to justify similar results.
7. As understanding, the risk tolerance is a complex process that goes beyond exclusive use of demographics. Hence more research is desirable to conclude effect of other factors as well like attitudes, family background, culture, financial stability factors etc. This can increase the explained variance in study.

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APPENDIX

QUESTIONNAIRE

Dear Respondent,
Seasonal Greeting!

I am SUSHMA, Research Scholar; Dr. APJ Abdul Kalam Technical University, Lucknow; pursuing a study in the area of behavioral finance for my PhD thesis. This questionnaire is a part of my research study. All answers will be handled anonymously and confidentially in study. Thanks in advance for sharing your precious and valuable time!

*Required

1. YOUR NAME PLEASE (Will be Kept confidential) *

(A) Demographic Profile

2. 1. Gender

Mark only one oval.

a) Male ()

b) Female ()

3. 2. Age

Mark only one oval.

a) Up to 25 years ()

b) 26 to 45 years ()

c) 46 to 65 years ()

e) 65 years and above()

4. 3. Marital status

Mark only one oval.

- a) Never married ()
- b) Married without children ()
- c) Married with children ()
- d) Widow/Seperated()

5. 4. Education

Mark only one oval.

- b) Graduation/ Diploma ()
- c) Post Graduation ()
- d) Doctoral and Higher edu()
- e) Professional Course ()

6. 5. Employment *Mark*

only one oval.

- a) Self employed()
- b) Full time salaried ()
- c) Casual/Part time salaried ()
- d) Unemployed[Housewife/Retired/Student] ()

7. 6. Monthly Income

Mark only one oval.

- a) UptoRs. 30,000 ()
- b) Rs. 30,001 to Rs. 60,000 ()
- c) Rs. 60,001 to Rs. 80,000 ()
- d) Rs. 80,001 and above ()
- f) Nil

8. 7. Investment Avenues

Mark only one oval.

- Safe avenues[bank deposits, PPF, national saving certificates, post office and government securities]()
- Moderate risk avenues[mutual fund life insurance, bonds and debentures]()
- High risk avenues[equity and commodity share market, FOREX] ()
- Traditional avenues[real state, gold/silver, chit funds] ()
- Emerging avenues[virtual real state, hedge fund, private equity, art and passion] ()

B) Risk Tolerance Profile

9. 1. Which type of risk taker

you are? *Mark only one oval.*

- A real gambler
- Willing to take risks after completing adequate research
- Cautious
- A real risk avoider

10. 2. If you are on a TV game show and given following options to play jackpot. Which one you opt?

Mark only one oval.

- Rs 100 in cash directly on winning (nothing to loose)
- A 50% probability at winning Rs 5,000
- A 25% probability at winning Rs 10,000
- A 5% probability at winning Rs 100,000

11. 3. You have just finished saving for a “once-in-a-lifetime” vacation. Three weeks before you plan to leave, you lose your job. You would:

Mark only one oval.

- Cancel the vacation
- Take a more tension free vacation
- Go as scheduled, reasoning you need to refresh to prepare for a new job
- Extend your vacation, because this might be your last chance

12. 4. If you unexpectedly received **Rs** 20,000 to invest, what would you do?

Mark only one oval.

- Deposit it in a bank account, money market account, or an insured CD
- Invest it in safe high quality bonds or bond mutual funds
- Invest it in shares at stock market.

13. 5. How comfortable are you investing in stocks? *Mark only one oval.*

- Not at all comfortable
- Somewhat comfortable
- Very comfortable

14. 6. What do you understand by the word “risk”?

Mark only one oval.

- Loss
- Uncertainty
- Opportunity
- Thrill

15. 7. You have your investments in safe government bonds but it's been predicted that prices of hard assets(land) are going to increase hence bond prices may fall. What would you do?

Mark only one oval.

- Hold the bonds
- Sell the bonds, put half the proceeds into money market accounts, and the other half into hard assets
- Sell the bonds and put the total proceeds into hard assets
- Sell the bonds, put all the money into hard assets, and borrow additional money to buy more

16. 8. Given the best and worst case of market returns of the four investment choices, which would you prefer?

Mark only one oval.

- Rs 200 gain at market hike case; No loss at market low case
- Rs 800 gain at market hike case; Rs 200 loss at market low case
- Rs 2,600 gain at market hike case; Rs 800 loss at market low case
- Rs 4,800 gain at market hike case; Rs 2400 loss at market low case

17. 9. You have been given Rs 1,000 and asked to gamble, which one you select:

Mark only one oval.

- A lottery with sure gain of Rs 500
- A lottery with 50% chance to gain Rs 1,000 and a 50% chance to gain nothing

18. 10. You have been given Rs 2,000 and asked to gamble, which one you select :

Mark only one oval.

- A lottery with sure loss of Rs 500
- A lottery with 50% chance to lose Rs 1,000 and 50% chance to loose nothing

19. 11. Suppose a relative inherited you Rs 100,000 conditioning that you invest ALL money in ONE option only. Which one you select?

Mark only one oval.

- A savings account or money market mutual fund
- A mutual fund that owns stocks and bonds
- A portfolio of 15 common stocks
- Commodities like gold, silver, and oil

20. 12. If you had to invest Rs 20,000 from salary, which one you select?

Mark only one oval.

- 60% in low-risk investments 30% in medium-risk investments 10% in high-risk investments
- 30% in low-risk investments 40% in medium-risk investments 30% in high-risk investments
- 10% in low-risk investments 40% in medium-risk investments 50% in high-risk investments

21. 13. Your trusted friend told you a venture which could pay back 50 to 100 times of investment if successful. If failed the entire investment is worthless. If success rate is only 20%, You will invest amount equivalent to:

Mark only one oval.

- Nothing
- One month's salary
- Three month's salary
- Six month's salary

C) Behavioral Biases Profile

(1 – Strongly Disagree, 2 – Disagree, 3 – Neutral, 4 – Agree, 5 – Strongly Agree)

22. 1. You try to generate a pattern in your previous earnings and losses in order to use this trend for future decisions.

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly Disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly Agree				

23. 2. You can do correct predictions about future returns on the basis of detailed past analysis.

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly Disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly Agree				

24. 3. You believe that it was easy for you to predict the situations like global financial and economic crisis in advance.

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly Disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly Agree				

25. 4. In your opinion the correct forecast always depend on earlier investment studies.

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly Disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly Agree				

26. 5. You take investment decisions on the basis of your previously formed opinions regarding market trends.

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly Disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly Agree				

27. 6. Your predictions always proven you correct in case of financial investments.

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly Disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly Agree				

28. 7. You trust your capabilities to start and manage new investment portfolios.

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly Disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly Agree				

29. 8. Your previous successful investments have boosted your level of confidence.

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly Disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly Agree				

30. 9. You feel that your earlier investment decisions often proven you correct.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree Strongly Agree

31. 10. You believe that your investment options has always outperformed in past.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree Strongly Agree

32. 11. You rely on your analytical skills to evaluate all your investment decisions yourself.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree Strongly Agree

33. 12. You feel that your specific investment decision skills provide you an extra edge to earn more profits.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree Strongly Agree

34. 13. Sometimes you invest just for the fun and excitement of proving your correct.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree Strongly Agree

35. 14. At times you are willing to take substantially higher risks in greed of getting above-average returns.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree Strongly Agree

36. 15. Your gut feeling and intuition help you to take correct decisions in confusing situations.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree Strongly Agree

37. 16. You do not hesitate to use even illegal methods to earn more.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree Strongly Agree

38. 17. You sometimes take advantage of loopholes in policies to maximize your profits.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree Strongly Agree

39. 18. You never hesitate to try your luck in order to increase your earnings.

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly Disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly Agree				

40. 19. You avoid investment options which are complicated and difficult to understand because of less information available.

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly Disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly Agree				

41. 20. Sometimes you take shortcuts to earn higher returns quickly.

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly Disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly Agree				

42. 21. You are more likely to invest in the instruments which are well known to you.

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly Disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly Agree				

43. 22. You believe that your close friends and relatives are most reliable source for investment information.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree Strongly Agree

44. 23. You try to opt for recently popular/in-news investment opportunities.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree Strongly Agree

45. 24. You believe that most familiar investment instruments are safer one.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree Strongly Agree

46. 25. You get influenced by media reports while making an investment decision.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree Strongly Agree

47. 26. You rely on expert's recommendations while making investments.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree Strongly Agree

48. 27. The opinion of friends and family members is important for you to take investment decision.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree Strongly Agree

49. 28. You try to copy the investment patter of successful investors as it is less risky.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree Strongly Agree

50. 29. You collect all first-hand information before taking independent decisions.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree Strongly Agree

51. 30. You feel yourself sensitive towards rumours regarding your investment instruments.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree Strongly Agree

52. 31. You would rather hold investments with negative returns instead of taking a loss.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree Strongly Agree

53. 32. You hesitate to trying those instrument avenues which has given you poor returns in past.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree Strongly Agree

54. 33. You are more likely to invest more in that instrument which has given you higher returns earlier.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree Strongly Agree

55. 34. You are more likely to avoid risk than usual; after getting prior losses.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree Strongly Agree

56. 35. You generally adjust your investment instruments at the time of tax calculation in order to get tax benefits.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree Strongly Agree

57. 36. You found yourself more sensitive towards losses than gains.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree Strongly Agree

58. 37. You sometimes regret your past investment decisions.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree Strongly Agree

59. 38. At times the losses on your investment decisions give you displeasure.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree Strongly Agree

60. 39. The profits on your investment decisions not always make you happiness.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree Strongly Agree

61. 40. You sometimes invest more deliberately in avenues which were past gainers.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree Strongly Agree

62. 41. You try to avoid those investment avenues which were past losers.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree Strongly Agree

63. 42. You are open to take help from investment consultancies after incurring losses.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree Strongly Agree

64. 43. You are more likely to differentiate between capital appreciation and regular income.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree Strongly Agree

65. 44. You feel those investment options safer that provides good return in long run.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree Strongly Agree

66. 45. You consider your entire investment options separately but not as whole portfolio.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree Strongly Agree

67. 46. When you receive high profit margin, you tend to hold onto investment to receive even higher profits.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Disagree Strongly Agree

68. 47. If you get an amount as a gift, you try to invest it in comparatively high risky options.

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly Disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly Agree				

69. 48. You always set a fixed target of returns before making any investment decision.

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly Disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly Agree				

70. 49. At times you are ready to take substantially high risk in greed of getting above average returns.

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly Disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly Agree				

71. 50. You always have presetted objectives befor taking an investment decision.

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly Disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly Agree				

List of Publications

1. Dr. Naela Jamal Rushdi, Sushma. “Establishing an association between risk tolerance and behavioural biases among Indian investors.” *International Journal of Engineering and advanced technology* 9, no. 2(2019): 1378-1382 [SCOPUS Indexed]
2. Dr. Naela Jamal Rushdi, Sushma. “A study on how behavioural biases of an investor act as antecedent in creating financial scams in India.” *MAIMT Journal of IT and Management* 12, no. 1(2018): 123-132 [UGC Listed]
3. Sushma, Dr. Naela Jamal Rushdi. “A systematic literature review on evolution of behavioural finance.” *ADHYAYAN: A Journal of management sciences* 8, no. 1(2018): 29-36 [EBSCO, Ulrich, Crossref Indexed]
4. Sushma. “Is gender act as an antecedent in developing behavioural biases among investors.” *National journal of MotilalRastogi school of management* 9, no. 1(2016): 1-5
5. Sushma. “A study on impact of behavioural biases on investor’s decision making with reference to gender.” In *UGC sponsored International Conference on Recent Trends in Business Finance and Economics*, UGC, 2015.
6. Dr. Naela Jamal Rushdi, Sushma. “Behavioural Finance: An insight to market anomalies and the irrational minds.” In *National Conference on Knowledge and Innovation for Sustainable Growth*, IIML-AHL(Lucknow), 2018.

Curriculum Vitae of Research Scholar

I, Sushma, Research Scholar, Dr. APJ Abdul Kalam Technical University, have been honoured to be a part of teaching fraternity from last 7 years approximately. I have been a part of different organizations and institutes and engaged into various researches time to time and have approximately more than 20 international and national publications.

I have a keen interest in sharing knowledge through different seminars, symposiums and conferences till now. I have always tried to upgrade my knowledge and skills with the help of different workshops and Quality Improvement Programs. I have attended Research Methodology workshop at Babasaheb Bhimrao Ambedkar University (BBAU) Central University Lucknow and a Quality Improvement Program at IIT Roorkee as well which was an enriching session. My keen interest in research led me to contribute various chapters for edited books as well.

I have served different responsibilities given to me wherever they have been assigned. I have been a part of different committees (cultural, anti-ragging and discipline) at institutes. I have served as an expert member at UPSEE 2014 also. I hope in future as well I will be able to continue to providing my knowledge to the needy. My achievements will surely help me to serve the society for the betterment in future.

Papers Published

International Journal of Engineering and Advanced Technology (IJEAT)
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Establishing AN Association between Risk Tolerance and Behavioral Biases among Indian Investors.

Naela Jamal Rushdi, Sushma

Abstract: Behavioral Finance Literature Has Shown A Mushroom Growth In The Recent Years. Literature Shed Specific Light On How The Concept Evolved And Later Developed To Various Stages Which Helped To Understand Various Market Anomalies And The Psychology Of Individuals Through Behavioral Biases. Behavioral Finance Tries To Explain The Logic Behind Applying Of Heuristics Or Shortcuts By Investors To Take Investment Decisions Which Still Need To Be Extensively Studied.

The Study Here Attempts For Identify Presence Of Different Biases In Individual Decision Making And Their Association With The Risk Tolerance Capacity. The Results Indicate That Heuristic Biases (I.E. Representativeness Bias, Overconfidence Bias And Gamblers Fallacy Bias) Are Linked To Moderate To High Risk Tolerant Investors. While Herd Bias And Prospect Biases (Loss Aversion Bias And Mental Accounting Bias) Are Found To Be Linked With Low To Moderate Risk Tolerance Levels Of Investors. Heuristics Are Positively Correlated With Risk Tolerance However; Prospect And Herd Are Found To Be Negatively Correlated With Risk Tolerance.

Keywords, Behavioral Biases, Herd Bias, Heuristics, Prospect, Risk Tolerance.

I. INTRODUCTION

From the past 20-30 years, different traditional theories of finance have played an important part in describing the investor decisions [3], [4], [5]. But the major setback came when theories fail to explain irrational behavior of investor, erratic price instabilities and market anomalies. Studies related to investment pattern elucidated that market bubbles were difficult to be understood with the help of standard financial theories. This inspired to the advent of a new field of finance known as behavioral finance, which explicated human psychology, irrationality and biased behavior of investors [8].

Behavioral finance is based on assumption that investor is not always rational in his decision making and they do behave irrationally sometimes [1].

Behavioral finance; also known as psychology of financing is a revolution in the field of finance came in the last 30 years. In 2007 Schindler explored behavioral finance as a coalescing factor of sociology, psychology and finance. Figure 1 below explain the model.

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Fig. 1: Behavioral Finance Model (Schindler, 2007)

II. SYSTEMATIC REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Neuroscience studies explored that human mind is a complex organ and it is considered as complicated to understand its thought process sometimes. At times people become rational in their decision making but also found to be irrational in many decisions [2].

In the year 1759 a Scottish economist and moral philosopher from Stanford University named Prof. Adam Smith in his work named "**Theory of Moral Sentiments**" talked about morality and selfishness [22]. He interpreted that people generally take decision for their own benefit. Also, people love to be admired by others and occasionally their decision making is subject to their psychology that whether that decision will be creditable or not. Praiseworthy decision gives them happiness and joy. Hence, they consider this decision as correct decision [23]. "**The Wealth of Nations**" came as another important work by Adam Smith; first published in 1776. The book is still considered as fundamental work in field of economics [24].

A new series of thoughts came out as "**Theory of the Bounded Rationality**" given by Herbert Simon in the year 1955. This theory assumes that rationality of individual depends on the cognitive boundaries of their minds. It says that every individual has an upper and lower limit of constraints within which he tries to maximize utility and find an optimal decision [21]. An ice-breaking seminal work in behavioral finance was

done by Israeli psychologists named Daniel Kahneman and Amos Tversky [25]. These two psychologists turned the world of decision science upside down by introducing "**Prospect Theory**" in the year 1979 [7]. This theory has been the most significant literature in the field of behavioral finance. It explains how individual evaluate gains or losses [26].

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According to prospect theory:

- ❖ People sometimes show risk aversion and sometimes risk seeking behavior depending on the nature of the predictions and likelihood of outcomes.
- ❖ People try to find out various alternatives (or prospects) they have and rank them on the basis of thumb rule or heuristics [27].
- ❖ The theory explained the concept of loss aversion. It says that the preference given to losses is always higher than the gains for the same amount [28].

❖ In the year 1981 an author named Robert J Shiller in his work named *Irrational Exuberance*, tried to explain the movements in US stock market by behavioral approach of market participants [20]. He explained the influence of investor's perception in creating the market bubble during late 1990's [19].

In the year 1994 two economists Meir Statman and Shefrin developed a new pricing model called as "*Behavioral Asset Pricing Model (BAPM)*". This model categorizes investor into informational traders and the noise traders. Information traders are the rational investors who follow the CAPM model whereas noise traders don't follow the CAPM i.e. traditional financial concepts [16].

Later in the year 2000 they also developed a new portfolio theory, named as the "*Behavioral Portfolio Theory (BPT)*". The Behavioral Portfolio Theory takes into account the behavioral biases of investors to construct their portfolios in relation with associated risk tolerance [17].

Michael Pompian in his book [13] explored different behavioral biases and categorized them into heuristics and prospect factors. He elucidated the association of these behavioral biases with different risk tolerance levels of the individual investor.

The figure 2 below explains the systematic development in available behavioral finance theories till the starting of 21st century, that contributed a lot in understanding the erratic and irrational behavior of individual investors which later contribute to creation of market bubbles, different anomalies and price fluctuations.

Fig. 2: Development of Behavioral Theories

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III. BEHAVIORAL BIASES

Hersh Shefrin in the year 2000 talked about various factors associated with psychology of investors, known as behavioral biases. He classified them into heuristic driven and frame dependent biases [18].

- ✦ **Heuristics** are defined as the rules of thumb. It includes overconfidence, anchoring, adjustment, reinforcement learning, excessive optimism and pessimism.
- ✦ **Frame dependent biases** influence people by the way they frame their mindset with the options available. It includes narrow framing, mental accounting and the disposition effect.

Michael M Pompian in the year 2011 also categorized the behavioral biases into two categories named cognitive and emotional biases [13].

- ✦ **Cognitive biases** are deviations from rationality. It includes overconfidence, representativeness, anchoring and adjustment, framing, cognitive dissonance, availability, mental accounting biases.
- ✦ **Emotional biases** are the behavioral pattern affected by a particular emotion that gives them pleasure. It includes endowment bias, loss aversion, optimism, herd behavior and status quo.

IV. RISK TOLERANCE

Grable and Joo, demarcated risk tolerance as the extreme level of uncertainty that an individual is ready to opt while making any financial decision [8]. Risk tolerance is the level of risk that an individual is ready to accept in selection of various choices during decision making. There have been various scales existing which help in calculation of risk tolerance like SCF scale GL-RTS scale and so on. The study here has used Risk tolerance scale given by Grable and Lytton, which has been found valid and reliable in the year 2015 as well. GL-RTS segments individual into 5 risk tolerant categories given as follows:

1. The score of 18 or below represents Low risk tolerance (i.e. conservative investor).
2. The score of 19 to 22 shows Below-average risk tolerance.
3. The score of 23 to 28 represents Average or moderate risk tolerance.
4. The score of 29 to 32 infers Above-average risk tolerance.
5. The score of 33 and above represents High risk tolerance (i.e. aggressive investor).

V. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

The study attempts to seek the fulfillment of following objectives:

1. To evaluate the presence of behavioural biases among individuals of Uttar Pradesh.
2. To determine the risk tolerance level among individual investors.
3. To examine the association (if any) between behavioral biases and risk tolerance of individual investors.

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VI. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A. Model: Present study consists of two main variables where behavioural biases act as independent variables and risk tolerance as dependent variable. The research model is presented below in figure 3.

Fig. 3: Research Model

B. Sample Size: The sample here is taken from 487 individual investors from Uttar Pradesh.

C. Calculation of variables:

- The behavioral biases have been calculated with the help of likert based questions where 1 represents strongly disagree and 5 represents strongly agree.
- The risk tolerance has been calculated with the help of 13 item questions based on the scale given by Grable and Lytton.

D. Data Calculation: The data used in the study is primary data, which are collected with the help of structured questionnaire.

E. Research Tools: Different statistical measures have been used for the study are:

- **Correlation:** To study the relationship between dependent and independent variables, correlation is used.
- **Regression:** The study here has generated a linear model of fit between dependent and independent variable. This has been done by drawing a linear regression line of association.
- **ANOVA test:** To test the hypotheses two-way ANOVA test is applied.

F. Hypothesis:

- H_0 : There is a no significant association between behavioural biases and risk tolerance.
- H_1 : There is a significant association between behavioural biases and risk tolerance.

VII. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

A. Descriptive Statistics: The mean, minimum and maximum values with standard deviation of different independent variables are presented in the Table I.

Table I. Descriptive Statistics

	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Dev
Representativeness	1	5	3.18	0.69
Overconfidence	1	5	2.96	1.09
Gamblers_fallacy	1	5	2.98	0.88
Herd	1	5	2.79	0.68
Loss_aversion	1	5	2.65	0.88
Mental_accounting	1	5	2.53	0.92

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B. ANOVA Test: Two-Way ANOVA has been applied to test following hypothesis.

H_0 : There is a no significant association between behavioural biases and risk tolerance.

H_1 : There is a significant association between behavioural biases and risk tolerance.

Table II: ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	960.428	6	160.071	946.780	.000 ^b
Residual	81.153	480	.169		
Total	1041.581	486			

a. Dependent Variable: risk tolerance code

b. Predictors: (Constant), mental_accounting, Representativeness, herd, loss_aversion, gamblers_fallacy, overconfidence

It is evident from the output table II, that the value of F-statistic is significant at 5% level of significance ($p < 0.05$). This infers that the null hypothesis is not accepted and the alternative one is concluded, which means that there is a significant impact of Behavioral biases and financial risk tolerance.

To measure of strength of association coefficient of determination has been calculated which is denoted by R square. The table III explains the value of R square, which is 0.922. This interprets that approximately 92.2% of the total variance has been explained by the biases considered in this study.

Table III: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.960 ^a	.922	.921	.411

a. Predictors: (Constant), mental_accounting, Representativeness, herd, loss_aversion, gamblers_fallacy, overconfidence

C. Regression Analysis: Regression analysis is used to test the impact of behavioral biases on risk tolerance of individuals of Uttar Pradesh. It is important to assess whether each of the independent variables included in the model make a significant contribution to the model. This is done by evaluating the model fit and its significance as well. Table IV provides the model fit for the linear model.

Table IV: Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	4.190	.290		14.430	.000
Representativeness	.183	.071	.086	2.583	.010
overconfidence	.224	.050	.167	4.523	.000
gamblers_fallacy	.279	.059	.168	4.723	.000
Herd	-.085	.065	-.039	-1.301	.019
loss_aversion	-.626	.053	-.377	-11.823	.000
mental_accounting	-.319	.055	-.201	-5.816	.000

a. Dependent Variable: risk tolerance code

Table 4 above elucidates the value of unstandardised coefficients (B) that help to generate the linear model between various Behavioral biases (independent variables) and financial risk tolerance (dependent variable). It is also evident from the output table above that the value of t-statistic is significant at 5% significance level as the value of p is less than 0.05 (95% confidence limit). The linear regression equation is as under.

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Eq. (1)

$$\text{Financial risk tolerance} = (4.19) + (0.183) * \text{representativeness} + (0.224) * \text{overconfidence} + (0.279) * \text{gamblers_fallacy} - (0.085) * \text{herd} - (0.626) * \text{loss_aversion} - (0.319) * \text{mental_account}$$

D. Correlation Analysis: Correlation is concerned with describing the strength of relationship between two variables. In this study correlation co-efficient analysis is under taken to find out the relationship between behavioral biases and risk tolerance. Table V briefly describes the value of Pearson correlation coefficient (r). The relationship between risk tolerance and heuristics biases (representativeness, overconfidence and gamblers fallacy) is found to be positive. The relationship is found to be negative in case of prospect biases (loss aversion, mental accounting) and herding bias in association with risk tolerance.

Table V: Summarized result of correlations coefficients

Dependent variable	Independent variable	Correlation coefficient
Risk Tolerance	Representativeness	.741 (Positive)
	Overconfidence	.797 (Positive)
	Gamblers fallacy	.710 (Positive)
	Herd	-.638 (Negative)
	Loss aversion	-.782 (Negative)
	Mental accounting	-.768 (Negative)

VIII. FINDINGS

- As per first objective the study revealed the presence of six behavioral biases namely representativeness, overconfidence, gamblers fallacy, loss aversion, mental accounting and herd bias.
- According to second objective the individual investors has been categorized into 5 categories. The statistics of these categories is given in table VI below.

Table VI: Tabular presentation of risk tolerance level among investors

risk tolerance code	Frequency(f)	Percentage
low risk tolerance	54	11.1
below average risk tolerance	82	16.8
moderate risk tolerance	102	20.9
above average risk tolerance	32	6.6
high risk tolerance	217	44.6
Total	487	100

- The third objective was to find the association between dependent and independent variables. It is found that the 3 biases namely representativeness, overconfidence and gamblers fallacy are found to be positively associated with risk tolerance. The other 3 biases loss aversion, mental accounting and herd bias are found to show negative association with risk tolerance.

IX. CONCLUSION

Behavioral finance is still evolving and the research done in India is lesser in comparison to that at global level. As behavioral biases are associated to the psychology of human beings therefore the implications are also very wide. Hence, it is going to help a lot to the financial practitioners as well

as those seeking a growth in the field of financial advisory. It will definitely help financial advisors to effectively understand the client's psychology and will aid them to develop a behaviorally modified portfolio best suits them. Behavioral finance concepts are going to help investment bankers to understand the market sentiments before going for public issues and will help them to make contingency financial strategists to handle adverse situations.

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A Systematic Literature Review on Evolution of Behavioral Finance

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ABSTRACT:

Traditional finance is a knowledge base that summarizes the concepts and theories based on principle of rationality to take financial decisions. Standard finance theories are based on an underlying concept that investor act carefully and objectively while making their financial decisions. In addition, individual investor is assumed to behave rationally keeping in mind the risk and return involved. However, the researchers in psychology interpret that the financial decisions are often made in an irrational manner. Therefore, a new field of behavioral finance has evolved in past few decades to explain how personal, social and psychological factors help an individual to make their financial decisions.

Behavioral finance; an emerging and prospective field has been developed with the input taken from the field of psychology and finance which tries to explain the puzzling factor in stock market fluctuations. It is defined as "study of the influence of socio-psychological factors on asset price". The behavioral and psychological insights have emerged as an application of economics with psychology, which seeks to provide an explanation for people's irrational financial decisions. It is a combination of psychology, sociology, and finance. The paper here tries to generate a procedural study to provide a systematic review of the evolution of behavioral finance theories and concepts. The study tries to explain how the assumptions of standard finance theories fail to provide an explanation of various anomalies, which led to an evolution of Behavioral Finance.

Keywords: Behavioral Psychology, Biases, rational decision, anomalies, Traditional Finance.

1. STANDARD/TRADITIONAL FINANCE: AN INTRODUCTION

Standard finance has tried to explain the financial decisions based on two concepts only i.e. risk and return. According to standard finance theories, every individual tries to maximize return and minimize risk through their decisions and they are very rational in this procedure. Traditional finance says that financial decisions are based on strict

mathematical calculations or standard financial theories already available. In addition, traditional finance theories are based on four basic assumptions:

- ❖ Investors are rational
- ❖ Investment markets are efficient
- ❖ Investors design their portfolio on the basis of mean variance
- ❖ Expected returns are a function of risk

The foundation for traditional finance theories is assumed to be conceptualized in the mid of nineteenth century in the year 1844, **John Stuart Mill** introduced the concept of rational economic man or *homo-economics* who tries to maximize his economic well being within the constraints he faces. The three underlying assumptions for this are perfect rationality, perfect self-interest and perfect information (John Stuart Mill, 1844)¹. These assumptions became the basis of the traditional financial framework that sought equilibrium solutions by maximizing marginal utilities of individuals subject to situational constraints. This concept later act as an assumption for most of the economic theories came later. Daneil Bernoulli in the year 1738 and later in 1954 studied decision making under risk by comparing expected utilities (Daneil Bernoulli , 1738)². Later Von Neumann and Morgenstern in the year 1944 used this concept for development of *“Expected Utility Theory”*. According to them, a rational investor tries to maximize his expected utility by calculating the weighted sum of utility values multiplied by their respective probabilities (Von Neumann and Morgenstern, 1944)³. A theory also categorizes the investor three categories as risk adverse, risk neutral and risk taker.

In the 1952, Harry Markowitz introduced the portfolio selection model and named it as *“Markowitz portfolio theory”*. Theory describes the process of optimal portfolio construction by selecting a combination of risky securities with risk free assets by maximizing the expected return and minimizing the risk (Harry Markowitz, 1952)⁴. Later come the concept of *“Capital Asset Pricing Model”* with various

contributors named as Jack Treynor, William F. Sharpe, John Lintner and Jan Mossin worked from 1962 to 1966 (Mossin,1966)⁵. The simplicity of the model made it the most widely accepted and popular asset pricing model (Sharpe, 1964)⁶. However, many traditional theorists were not in favor of this model because of various anomalies regarding market efficiency (Lintner, 1965)⁷. In order to overcome these anomalies a new asset pricing theory was introduced by Eugene Fama in the year 1970, which is known as *“Efficient Market Hypothesis”*. Efficient Market Hypothesis talked about the impact of any type of news or information into market and hence interpreting the efficiency of market and the expected return (Eugene Fama, 1970)⁸. Eugene Fama has categorized efficiency of market into three categories:

- ❖ A *weak* efficient market is one where a small news or information affect the market returns and create abnormalities into the market.
- ❖ A *semi strong* efficient market uses publicly available information but it fails to create superior returns.
- ❖ A *strong* efficient market is one where even insider trading cannot provide abnormal returns. (Eugene Fama, 1992)⁹

After Efficient Market Hypothesis (EMH), one more economist named Stephen Ross in the year 1976 come up with a concept of arbitraging in the form of a new theory named as “*Arbitrage Pricing Theory*”. The theory talked about greed of investor where he tries to create return by taking benefit of price fluctuations. According to arbitraging model, the investor purchases security from the place where it is cheaper and tries to sale it at a place where it is costlier (Stephen Ross, 1980)¹⁰.

Figure 1 below provides a comprehensive review of traditional finance theories available.

FIGURE 1

Source: Self Compiled

2.BEHAVIORAL FINANCE: A BRIEF REVIEW

Since last 20-30 years, these traditional financial theories have played an important role in explaining the investor decision-making process but a major setback came when theories fail to explain irrational behavior of investor. Various researchers studying stock market have seen various market bubbles, which were difficult to be explained by traditional finance theories. This led to the emergence of a new field of finance, which tries to explain the psychology, irrationality and biased nature of investors.

The assumptions of this new financial field differ from traditional one. This new branch of finance known as *behavioral finance* is

based on assumptions that investors do behave irrationally sometimes, investment markets are not always efficient and investors don't always follow mean variance rule for designing their portfolio.

The studies in the area of neuroscience and psychology has already interpreted that people mind is a complex thing to study. Human brain is considered as the most complicated organ People are sometimes **rational** in their decision making but at times, they also behave stupidly. In addition, people are aware about the weaknesses of others, they try to use it in exploiting them, and here comes the other prospect of **morality**. People here have developed a particular system of various principles to distinguish between right and wrong as ethics.

A Systematic Literature Review on Evolution of Behavioral Finance

Source: *Evolution of behavioral finance, model edited from: Schindler, 2007.*

It is in the mid of 18th century; in the year of **1759** when a Scottish economist, moral philosopher and professor from Stanford University named **Adam Smith** in his work named "*Theory of Moral Sentiments*" talked about morality and selfishness (Smith, 1759)¹¹. He interpreted that people generally take decision for their own benefit. In addition, people love to be praised by others and sometimes their decision making depends on the psychology that whether that decision will be praiseworthy or not. Praiseworthy decision gives them pleasure and they consider it as correct decision (Smith, 1776)¹².

"*The Wealth of Nations*" names to be the next work of Adam Smith; first published in 1776. The book offers one of the world's first collected descriptions of what builds nations' wealth, and is today a fundamental work in the field of economics (Smith, 1991)¹³. Another author named Bentham emphasized on the role of sentiments and emotions like pride, shame, insecurity, egotism etc. and highlighted the psychological aspects of utility function (Bentham J, 1789)¹⁴.

This work was then restrained to mid of twentieth century when many other researchers criticized the concept of *homo economicus* and argued that human beings cannot be completely informed of every situation in order to maximize their expected utility. Instead, they advocate the "*Theory of the Bounded Rationality*" given by Herbert Simon in the year 1955. This theory assumes that rationality of individuals depends on various information they have and the cognitive limitations of their minds. Bounded rationality explains that individuals have upper and lower limit of constraints within which they try to maximize their utility and find an optimal way (Herbert Simon, 1955)¹⁵.

The credit for an ice-breaking work in behavioral finance goes to a pair of Israeli psychologists named Daniel Kahneman and Amos Tversky (Kahneman D& Tversky A)¹⁶. These two trailblazing psychologists turned the world of decision science upside down. They introduced the concept of "*Prospect Theory*" in the year 1979 for interpreting decision making under risk (Kahneman D& Tversky A, 1979)¹⁷. This theory is considered

most influential literature in the field of behavioral finance. The theory tries to explain how individual evaluate gain or losses (Kahneman D& Tversky A, 1973)¹⁸. According to prospect theory:

- ❖ People sometimes show risk aversion and sometimes risk seeking behavior depending on the nature of the prospects and relative probability of outcomes. Hence, they act as risk averse for decisions in which they assume sure gains while risk lover for decisions with probability of sure losses.
- ❖ People assign value to gains and losses. They try to find out various alternatives (or prospects) they have and then rank the based on rules of thumb (heuristics) (Kahneman D& Tversky A, 1974)¹⁹. Later they evaluate these prospects in relation with a reference that generally provides a relative basis for determining their gains and losses.
- ❖ The theory says that the weightage given to losses is always higher than the gains for the same amount because people are more averse to losses than gains (Kahneman & Tversky, 1981)²⁰. This is known as *loss aversion*. Later they have introduced various behavioral biases that affect the financial decision making of individuals (Kahneman D, 1992)²¹.

In the year 1981 an author named Robert J Shiller during his study regarding stock market volatility presented the contradictions for standard financial theories. In his bestselling book *Irrational Exuberance* (Shiller RJ, 2005)²², he tries to explain the movements in US stock market with the help of behavioral approach of market

participants. He explained the impact on investor's perception, psychological and cultural factors in creating the market bubble during late 1990's (Shiller RJ, 1981)²³.

In the year 1994 two economists Meir Statman and Shefrin developed a new pricing model called as "*Behavioral Asset Pricing Model (BAPM)*". This model categorizes investor into informational traders and the noise traders. Information traders are the rational investors who follow the CAPM model whereas noise traders do not follow the CAPM and traditional financial concepts (Shefrin and Statman, 1994)²⁴.

Later in the year 2000 they also developed a new portfolio theory, named as the "*Behavioral Portfolio Theory (BPT)*". The Behavioral Portfolio Theory takes into account the behavioral biases of investors to construct their portfolios in relation with associated risk tolerance (Shefrin and Statman, 2011)²⁵.

Another significant contribution in justifying market anomalies was given by Barberis and Thaler in the year 2003. According to them Behavioral finance has two building blocks: *limits to arbitrage*, which argues that it can be difficult for rational traders to undo the dislocations caused by less rational traders; and *psychology*, which catalogues the kinds of deviations from full rationality. They studied individual trading behavior to explain behavioral finance applications in stock market average returns.

The figure 3 below explains the systematic development in various behavioral finance theories until the starting of 21st century.

FIGURE 3

• *Behavioral Asset Pricing Model (BAPM) (1994)*
 • *Behavioral Portfolio Theory (BPT) (2000)*

Source: Self Compiled

3. BEHAVIORAL FACTORS/ BIASES:

Hersh Shefrin in the year 2000 has talked about various factors associated with psychology of investors which are also known as behavioral biases. He has broadly classifies these biases into heuristic driven and frame dependent biases (Hersh Shefrin, 2000) ²⁷.

- **Heuristics** are defined as the rules of thumb, which makes decision making easier, especially in complex and uncertain environments. Heuristics includes overconfidence, anchoring, adjustment, reinforcement learning, excessive optimism and pessimism.
- **Frame dependent biases** influence people by the way they frame their mindset with the options available. It includes biases like narrow framing, mental accounting and the disposition effect.
- Michael M Pompian gave one more categorization for behavioral biases in the year 2011. He categorized the behavioral

biases into two categories named cognitive and emotional biases (Pompian M, 2011)²⁸.

- **Cognitive biases** are the systematic deviations from rationality because of the individual perceptions. It includes overconfidence, representativeness, anchoring and adjustment, framing, cognitive dissonance, availability, mental accounting biases.
- **Emotional biases** are the behavioral pattern of a person which is affected by their particular emotion that gives them pleasant feeling. It includes endowment bias, loss aversion, optimism and status quo.

4. CONCLUSION:

Behavioral finance literature has grown to its heights in recent years. The literature here tries to shed specific light on how the concept evolved and later developed to various stages and helped to understand various market anomalies and the psychology of individuals in the form of behavioral biases. Behavioral finance tries to explain the logic behind applying of heuristics or shortcuts by investors to take investment decisions, which still need to be extensively studied.

An analysis of the available literature also revealed that a very little work has been done in India in comparison to global level. As behavioral biases are associated to the psychology of human beings, therefore the implications are also very wide. Hence, it is going to help a lot to the financial practitioners as well as those seeking a growth in the field of financial advisory. It will definitely help financial advisors to effectively understand the client's psychology and will aid them to develop a behaviorally modified portfolio best suits them. Behavioral finance concepts are going to help investment bankers to understand the market sentiments before going for public issues and will help them to make contingency financial strategists to handle adverse situations.

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